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Cover page: Sofonisba Anguissola, Bernardino Campi painting Sofonisba Anguissola, c.1559, Pinacoteca Nazionale, Siena

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EDI TOR IAL

Lund, August 2025

Dear ISHA members,
Dear readers,

When I started preparing this edition of *Carnival*, I became fascinated with a painting by Sofonisba Anguissola (c.1532-1625), which I put on the cover of this edition. At first glance it might seem like a self-portrait of the male artist depicted. He is the one portrayed working at the easel, in a format very common in auto-portraits. Even the title, “Portrait of Bernardino Campi Painting Sofonisba Anguissola”, suggests his authorship, but it is her work. She is the one determining everything, shadowing over him, and, as a restoration uncovered in 1996, she even painted a version in which her hand is meeting his, guiding his brush through the painting.

Anguissola chose this format for reasons art historians still debate. Is it a comment on how women were more likely to be objects than subjects in Renaissance painting? Is it an homage for her former teacher, or maybe a jab at him, making him paint her jacket, a task usually given to apprentices? With its mysteries and ambiguities, this painting seemed appropriate for this journal. As our first Editor-in-Chief, Sakari Saaritsa, wrote, the journal was named *Carnival* because when students publish an international journal of their own, the moment is carnivalistic, in that “commoners become kings”. So in celebration of those who subvert where they are expected to stay, who take their teacher’s hands and create a place for themselves, we now bring you the 24th edition of *Carnival*.

This was my third edition as a member of the *Carnival* board, and the first as Editor-in-Chief. It also marked my third year as an ISHA official, and the third year of my PhD in Central European University, spent mostly abroad in a series of fellowships. It was not easy to take time for everything and prepare a journal, but *Carnival* has remained one of the most rewarding experiences I had as a student, and one of the places where I have learned the most.

EDI TOR IAL

I hope to have made it a good learning opportunity also for my colleagues at the editorial board and for the authors who trusted us with their work, and I would like to thank you all immensely for all the hard work that was put into this edition. Our editors continued to provide critical, but constructive feedback, and fiercely advocated for papers they believed would be a good addition to Carnival. If an editor wrote a million comments on your paper, it might have seemed frustrating, but that usually means that they felt strongly about your work. I am very proud of the high level of papers submitted for this edition, and with the diversity brought by the authors, both in academic journey, since we have students from BAs to PhDs, and in topics. This edition opens with Rohan Basu's work with coffeehouses, and how they can give us a post-colonial take on cosmopolitanism, moving to Fanny Olsson's treatment of Swedish guidebooks and how they construct a gaze of Romania. Then, Mihajlo Srdanović and Nikola Ristić's work provides an insight on how three Belgrade newspapers reported on the Second World War, while Robin Thomas' work is focused on the use of elephants as a propaganda tool in the Mughal empire. Finally, we close with Yevhen Yashchuk's analysis of the 'Eastern Question' in the British penny press.

Thank you to all readers, and I wish all of you a very pleasant reading experience.

Julia Boechat Machado
Editor-in-Chief

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Julia Boechat Machado is a PhD Candidate at Central European University, and currently a visiting PhD in Lund University. In 2024-25, she also served as Vice-President in ISHA. She is interested in cultural history, especially concerning the Soviet Union, and researches topics in Book History and Publishing History.

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The 'World' Across Coffee-Houses

The Case for Conviviality: Public sphere and Cosmopolitan praxis in the writings of Mirza Abu Talib Isfahani

Rohan Basu

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Abstract

This essay aims to explore the histories of the public sphere and ideas of cosmopolitanism from a 'global perspective', as they emerged with the closure of the eighteenth and the beginning of the nineteenth century. This period is crucial to understanding imaginations and practices of the same because in this period, the universalism of European cosmopolitanism was faced by the utilitarianism of imperialism abroad for industrial modernity within. So far, in the cannon of modern intellectual history, ideas of cosmopolitanism have been traced back to Kant. In pointing out the Eurocentric bias of such a vision, postcolonial critiques have questioned the very ideals of the Enlightenment and paved way for politico-cultural provincialisms. To avoid such trappings, I will examine the writings of late eighteenth century scholar-traveler Mirza Abu Taleb who wrote extensively of his travels across Europe and West Asia between 1799-1803. By focusing on his comparison of coffee-house cultures across London, Paris and Istanbul, I shall destabilise Saidian notions of Orient and Occident. Thus reapproaching the Habermasian analysis of the public sphere that was limited only to European coffee-houses, that did not take into account and comparison the Ottoman and Arabic coffee cultures, this paper shall reclaim

the concerns of Kantian cosmopolitanism, albeit from a decolonial perspective, and finally argue that a global historical approach can make way for both multiplicity and the enlightenment universalism which is at the core of much of the modern world.

Keywords: Imperialism, Decolonial, Cosmopolitanism, Enlightenment, Public Sphere, South Asia, Travel Writing.

Introduction

Coffee-house is free to all Comers, so they have Humane shape, where a Liquor made of an Arabian Berry called Coffee is drunk. Six or seven years ago was it first brought into England, when the Palats of the English were as Fanatical, as their Brains. Like Apes, the English imitate all other people in their ridiculous Fashions. As Slaves they submit to the Customs even of Turkey and India. Doth the Frenchman wear Feathers in his Hat, and Pantaloons to hide his straddling? Believe it, the Englishman will be a la mode de France. With the Barbarous Indian he smokes Tobacco. With the Turk he drinks Coffee. A character of Coffee and Coffee-Houses, by M. P., 1661 A.D.¹

The above excerpt from a 17th century English treatise on Coffee Houses would seem peculiar to the lay person in the times of contemporary globalization when even in Communist China, people go to Starbucks for coffee. It might seem stranger even to the people of ‘The West,’ where Coffee-houses are an intrinsic part of the urban landscape, making cities like Paris unimaginable without its Cafés. The very same caricatured image is reproduced within pop culture by films like ‘Midnight in Paris’ – people sitting at numerous cafes, sipping coffee, smoking, and talking about all the on goings of politics and art – which takes up the aspirational

¹ "A character of coffee and coffee-houses by M.P." In the digital collection *Early English Books Online*. <https://name.umdl.umich.edu/A56639.0001.001>. University of Michigan Library Digital Collections.

imagination of ‘culture’ in the minds of young people in postcolonial Calcutta.² The comment on the British emulating the Turks in drinking coffee would seem even stranger to people in the postcolonial world – where Coffee is a cash crop representing the uneven development of capitalism and a luxury produced from the invisible exploitation of labourers in plantations, a remnant of European colonialism. Yet, the production of coffee, and coffee drinking as a social act did not have a ‘Western’ origin. European travellers first encountered coffee and coffee houses in Constantinople, between the late 16th and early 17th centuries,³ the word Coffee itself being derived from the Turkish ‘*kaveh*’. Ali Al-e Dawud also gives an informative account of Coffee Houses which proliferated and flourished in Persia during the Safavid times.⁴ It seemed like a place for intellectual discussions among scholars, Sufis, and even high-ranking officials, and at the same time a place for performance for poets and artists. The 17th century travel writer and Fellow of the Royal Society John Fryer noted that the Persians were very particular about their coffee, and they would spend time in the coffee houses for both leisure and business: he even compared the coffee houses to English theatres, as a place where poetry and entertainment had as much import as news.⁵

It becomes significant then, to think of the theoretical impact that these histories might have – because the Coffee House is one of the central motifs in Jürgen Habermas’s reading about the emergence of the ‘Public Sphere’ in 18th century Europe, especially England. Habermas looks at the coffee house as a discursive space, where private individuals met on a neutral ground to discuss, and debate matters of society and politics and reach a rational conclusion about the same – thereby making public opinion.⁶ Habermas’s proposition of ‘rational debate’ between ‘rational individuals’ towards the formation of a greater collective makes obvious the Kantian

² In his essay on Adda (casual conversation) in Bengal, Dipesh Chakrabarty shows how indigenous forms of conversation such as adda, while having its own history, tried to ‘civilise’ itself in early 20th century Calcutta by imitating European Café culture. The homogenizing tendency of modernity still continues to perpetuate the same in middle class aspirations of public conversations which can be seen through the proliferation of a certain kind of cafeteria aesthetic. See Chakrabarty, Dipesh. "Chapter 7. Adda: A History of Sociality" In *Provincializing Europe: Postcolonial Thought and Historical Difference - New Edition*, 180-213. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781400828654-010>.

³ Ellis, Markman. “The Wine of Islam Discovered.” In *The Coffee House: A Cultural History*, 19–27. Orion Publishing, 2011.

⁴ Ali Āl-E Dāwūd. “Coffeehouse.” Encyclopaedia Iranica, December 15, 1992. <https://www.iranicaonline.org/articles/coffeehouse-qahva-kana>.

⁵ Fryer, John. “New Account of East India and Persia Vol.3.” 34-35. Internet Archive, January 1, 1672. <https://archive.org/details/in.gov.ignca.6071/page/n47/mode/2up>.

⁶ Jürgen Habermas, ‘The Public Sphere’, in *Jürgen Habermas on Society and Politics: A Reader*, ed. Steven Seidman (Boston: Beacon Press, 1989).

underpinnings of the same.⁷ While Habermas places the development of the ‘rational public sphere’ in Europe and especially 18th century England, the fact that coffee as not just a commodity but also that the Coffee House as a phenomenon was encountered in the Ottoman Empire and then imported to Europe, points to the obvious development of a kind of public sphere, or rather, public culture in the Ottoman Empire during the 16th and 17th century. The lack of print capitalism and the specifics of bourgeoisie society in the Ottoman Empire at that time did not fit the normative form of a Habermasian public sphere that according to Habermas was ‘attained in England, France and to some extent in Germany after the Enlightenment.’⁸ Yet, if questions of the public sphere are approached without the presuppositions of this particularist form of ‘Enlightenment rationality,’⁹ it is interesting to notice that the Ottoman Coffee House did offer a public space where socio-cultural performance met political concern. In such a place, to differentiate between rational critique, and critique in a theatrically performative form such as political satire lends to nothing more than denying the nature of this particularist difference, which ends up reinforcing the normative form of the Habermasian public sphere.¹⁰

By recognizing the discourse of intellectual and political exchange characterising European Coffeeshouses as a form of Kantian cosmopolitanism, and the place of Kant in the canon of ideas of cosmopolitanism, in this essay I shall reapproach the Habermasian analysis of the public sphere that was limited only to European coffee-houses. To address the problem of the Eurocentric normative history of the public sphere and the conceptual limitation it creates, I will examine the writings of late eighteenth century scholar-traveller Mirza Abu Talib, focusing especially on Talib’s comparison of coffee-house cultures across London, Paris and Istanbul, about which he wrote extensively in the record of his travels across Europe and West Asia between 1799-1803. Born around 1752 into a Persianate service elite straddling the courtly worlds of Lucknow and Murshidabad in eighteenth century Mughal India, Mirza Abu Talib Khan

⁷ Kant: Idea for a universal history from a cosmopolitan point of View. Accessed April 27, 2025. <https://www.marxists.org/reference/subject/ethics/kant/universal-history.htm>. See the second, fourth and fifth thesis.

⁸ Siviloglu, Murat R. *The Emergence of Public Opinion: State and Society in the late Ottoman Empire*, 13-20. Cambridge, United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press, 2020.

Karababa, Emnegül, and Gülz Ger. “Early Modern Ottoman Coffeehouse Culture and the Formation of the Consumer Subject.” *Journal of Consumer Research* 37, no. 5 (February 1, 2011): 737–60. <https://doi.org/10.1086/656422>.

⁹ Here I am noting Enlightenment rationality as a historically produced and ideologically specific project, and not as an abstract form which might be traced cross-culturally despite of, and within local cultural peculiarities.

¹⁰ Kömeçoğlu, Uğur. “The Publicness and Sociabilities of the Ottoman Coffeehouse.” *Javnost - The Public* 12, no. 2 (January 2005): 5–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13183222.2005.11008885>.

was educated in the Indo-Persian intellectual tradition and served in administrative roles under both the remnants of the Mughal state and the expanding East India Company. His family history was marked by political turbulence, and his own career reflected the uncertainties of a time when Mughal sovereignty was giving way to British dominance. In 1799, facing diminished prospects, he accepted an offer from his English friend, David Thomas Richardson, to journey to Britain. Over the next four years, Abu Talib travelled through the Indian Ocean and Cape of Good Hope to England and Ireland, and returned via Southern Europe, the Ottoman Empire, and Persia—finally arriving in Calcutta in 1803. His Persian travelogue—later translated into English as *Travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan*—is a remarkable document that blends ethnographic observation, political commentary, and philosophical reflection. Far from conforming to the epistemic binaries of colonial Orientalism, Abu Talib’s work exhibits a historically grounded cosmopolitanism. He engages not only with the curiosities and spectacles of Europe, but with its political institutions, economic structures, and sociability—offering both appreciation and critique. His ambition for a universal history, expressed in works like *Lubb-us-Siyar*, places Islamic, European, and even American histories within a shared world-historical horizon, underscoring his commitment to global enquiry beyond civilizational essentialism.¹¹

By bringing Abu Talib’s accounts of the Ottoman coffee cultures into comparison with their European counterparts, this paper destabilises Saidian notions of Orient and Occident, and reapproaches the concerns of Kantian cosmopolitanism from a decolonial perspective, testing it against what Walter Mignolo has called *decolonial cosmopolitanism*: a vision of planetary conviviality not grounded in European universals, but articulated through the ‘pluriversal’ experiences of those historically positioned “on the other side of the line.”¹² Finally, I shall read Abu Talib’s comparativist view of coffee-house cultures through Gurminder Bhambra’s framework of *connected sociologies*, in which she argues against multiple modernities confronting each other but rather calls for the study of a global modernity that must be understood through reconstructing dominant universal concepts such as ‘cosmopolitanism’ and its manifestation through obfuscated histories.¹³ It is achieved not just by fitting such histories

¹¹ Hasan, Mushirul. “Resistance And Acquiescence In North India: Muslim Responses To The West.” *Rivista Degli Studi Orientali* 67, no. 1/2 (1993): 83–105. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/41880771>.

¹² Mignolo, Walter. “The Many Faces of Cosmo-Polis.” *The Politics of Decolonial Investigations*, July 9, 2021, 181–228. <https://doi.org/10.1215/9781478002574-008>.

¹³ Bhambra, Gurminder K. *Connected Sociologies*, 1-16. London, England: Bloomsbury Academic, 2015.

into the existing theories, but by re-theorizing existing theoretical concepts from the vantage point of these histories. To address this, I will place Abu Talib's commentary on coffee-house cultures and cosmopolitanism within a history of the public sphere and ideas of cosmopolitanism from a 'global perspective', as they emerged with the closure of the eighteenth and the beginning of the nineteenth century. This period is crucial to understanding imaginations and practices of the same because in this period, the universalisation of European political imaginations and social ordering was achieved through the expansion of the imperial reach of the British and French empires – which at the same time were confronted by the differences of social conditions in the many colonies across the world, further perpetuated by the politics of imperialism.¹⁴ In pointing out the Eurocentric bias of such a vision, postcolonial critiques have questioned the very ideals of the Enlightenment and paved way for politico-cultural provincialisms, which focused on culturalist reactions to European colonialism.¹⁵ Yet, even if the values of modern civilization were denied to the colonies, in turn imperial governance of the British was critiqued by the Orientalists and figures like Edmund Burke who argued for the cultural specificities of the British colonies and tried to affirm their coevalness with British culture. Strangely enough, Burke's critique of British imperialism mirrors the postcolonial critique of the same – the British civilizing mission's tendency to locate and identify colonial society on a general schema of societal development, dubbed as the "cosmopolitanism of reason," is pit against Burke's "cosmopolitanism of sentiments" which is predicated upon "recognition" of the "sentiments, feelings and sense of location" formed by the religious, archaic and premodern society of India.¹⁶

This fails to identify how people in the colonies encountered the realities of colonialism and Europe, adopting, transforming and responding to the 'enlightened' concepts of 'European civilization' and the realities they represented. Abu Talib's reflections are not composed at a distance but formed through a process of bodily and intellectual traversal from the Indo-Persianate world he was familiar with to imperial metropolises of Europe and the varied rhythms of these public cultures. His movements generated a deeply reflexive mode of

¹⁴ Mehta, Uday Singh. *Liberalism and Empire: A Study in Nineteenth-Century British Liberal Thought*, 2-8. University of Chicago Press, 1999.

¹⁵ Carey, Daniel, and Sven Trakulhun, 'Universalism, Diversity, and the Postcolonial Enlightenment', in Daniel Carey, and Lynn Festa (eds), *The Postcolonial Enlightenment: Eighteenth-Century Colonialism and Postcolonial Theory* (Oxford, 2013; online edn, Oxford Academic, 3 Mar. 2015), <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:osobl/9780199677597.003.0008>.

¹⁶ Mehta, Uday Singh. *Liberalism and Empire: A Study in Nineteenth-Century British Liberal Thought*, 17-23. University of Chicago Press, 1999.

comparison – one that registered not just cultural differences, but the shared forms of sociability, critique, and deliberation embedded in urban coffeehouse life. His writing becomes a historical enactment of Ulrich Beck’s formulation of *methodological cosmopolitanism*.¹⁷ Beck calls for a decisive shift away from normative, nation-state-centred understandings of society and towards a recognition of the embodied, lived experiences of individuals who move through and negotiate multiple cultural worlds. Rather than abstract ideals, cosmopolitanism for Beck is grounded in *bodily encounters* – it is a way of being-in-the-world that emerges from the affective, sensory, and reflexive navigation of entangled global spaces. This is not merely about inhabiting different locations, but about encountering and internalising the contradictions, connections, and uneven proximities that constitute modern life. Such cosmopolitanism is not disembodied, but enacted through practices, movements, and negotiations with difference. It is through this lens that we might approach Abu Talib, whose journey across the metropolises of Eurasia renders him not merely an observer of Europe, but a historical actor shaped by the cosmopolitan condition he experiences thus theorising cosmopolitanism by transcending particularistic barriers.

To demonstrate all of this, I will proceed to answer the following question: If the European/British Coffee House is a distinctive cultural space with a set of discursive practices that led to the development of the bourgeois public sphere in England, France and Germany in the 18th century, then how does an ‘Oriental’ character – the Indo-Iranian traveller Mirza Abu Talib – engage with such spaces in his travels across Europe, and understand public culture and cosmopolitanism, given that he was familiar with the coffee-houses of Delhi in Mughal India where people gathered to discuss matters of culture and society?¹⁸ For this, let us consider one of the most notable features of the English Coffee Houses – the reading and circulation of journals and newspapers. Among the various kinds of papers produced in Coffee House encounters in London,¹⁹ there were *The Tatler*, *The Guardian* (still active and currently one of the most popular newspapers read not just in the UK but across the English-speaking world) and *The Spectator*. To quote Joseph Addison writing in *The Spectator*, in March 1711,

¹⁷ Beck, Ulrich. “Mobility and the Cosmopolitan Perspective.” *Exploring Networked Urban Mobilities*, October 20, 2017, 140–51. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315201078-9>.

¹⁸ Blake, Stephen P. *Shahjahanabad: The sovereign city in Mughal India, 1639-1739*, 55-57. Cambridge England: Cambridge University Press, 2002.

¹⁹ Ellis, Markman. “The Philosopher in the Coffee-House.” In *The Coffee House: A Cultural History*, 134–147. Orion Publishing, 2011.

It was said of Socrates, that he brought Philosophy down from Heaven, to inhabit among Men, and I shall be ambitious to have it said of me, that I have brought Philosophy out of Closets and Libraries, Schools and Colleges, to dwell in Clubs and Assemblies, at Tea-Tables and in Coffee-houses.²⁰

In fact, as Ellis notes, these publications were trying to not just circulate ideas and happenings and help discussion, but also a notion of civility – the cultivation of a higher form of ‘politeness’ is to improve ‘human nature.’²¹ Habermas also notes the same about English Coffee Houses in London:

When Addison and Steele published the first issue of the *Tatler* in 1709, the coffee houses were already so numerous and the circles of their frequenters already so wide that contact among these thousand-fold circles could only be maintained through a journal. At the same time, the new periodical was so intimately interwoven with the life of the coffee houses that the individual issues were indeed sufficient basis for its reconstruction. The periodical articles were not only made the object of discussion by the public of the coffee houses but were viewed as integral parts of this discussion; this was demonstrated by the flood of letters from which the editor each week published a selection. When the *Spectator* separated from the *Guardian* the letters to the editor were provided with a special institution: on the west side of Button’s Coffee House a lion’s head was attached through whose jaws the reader threw his letter.²²

²⁰ Addison, Joseph. “The Spectator, Issue 10, Monday, March 12, 1711.” *Literature in Context*. Accessed April 22, 2025. <https://anthologydev.lib.virginia.edu/work/Spectator/addison-spectator-10>.

²¹ Once again, this invokes, or rather, pre-empts Kant’s vision of cosmopolitan civilization.

²² Habermas, Jürgen. *The Structural Transformation of the Public Sphere: An Inquiry into a category of Bourgeois Society*, 42. Cambridge: Polity Press, 1989.

Thus, what emerged in this space might be termed as a ‘republic of letters.’²³ On this count, let us turn to Abu Talib’s comment on the printing of newspapers and subsequent circulation of newspapers in the English Coffee Houses that cut across classes, giving evidence of broad readership:

Of the inventions of Europe, the utility of which may not appear at first sight to an Asiatic, the art of printing is the most admirable. By its aid, thousands of copies, of any scientific, moral, or religious book, may be circulated among the people in a very short time; and by it, the works of celebrated authors are handed down to posterity, free from the errors and imperfections of a manuscript. To this art the English are indebted for the humble but useful publication of Newspapers, without which life would be irksome to them. These are read by all ranks of people, from the prince to the beggar. They are printed daily and sent every morning to the houses of the rich; but those who cannot afford to subscribe for one, go and read them at the coffee-rooms or public-houses.²⁴

Touching upon the ‘Utility of the Art of Printing,’ Abu Talib goes on to explain that these newspapers could be accessed by any person, and they contain information of everything happening in the world – events and matters of political significance, the economy, and cultural happenings.²⁵ Abu Talib’s appreciation of the English Coffee House is, therefore, remarkably like what Habermas is pointing to – it is based on the utilitarian advantage of spreading knowledge, civility and promoting discussion in society. This becomes even more interesting if read against Abu Talib’s own intention in writing his travelogue, which he stated to be so in the Introduction:

²³ Solleveld, Floris. "Afterlives of the Republic of Letters: Learned Journals and Scholarly Community in the Early Nineteenth Century", *Erudition and the Republic of Letters* 5, 1 (2020): 82-116, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1163/24055069-00501003>.

I’m calling it a ‘republic of letters’ because access to this world of discourse was still limited by access to newspapers and coffeehouses – the ‘demise’, or rather transformation of the ‘republic’ into the modern world of the dissemination of knowledge was built through institutions and the standardization of learning and spread of literacy which became much more widespread in the second half of the nineteenth century.

²⁴ Abu Talib ibn Muhammad, Isfahani, (Daniel O’Quinn, and Charles Stewart). *The travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan in Asia, Africa and Europe, during the years 1799, 1800, 1801, 1802, and 1803.*, 157. Peterborough, Ontario: Broadview, 2009.

²⁵ Abu Talib ibn Muhammad, Isfahani, (Daniel O’Quinn, and Charles Stewart). *The travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan in Asia, Africa and Europe, during the years 1799, 1800, 1801, 1802, and 1803.*, 157-158. Peterborough, Ontario: Broadview, 2009.

It therefore occurred to him, that if he were to write all the circumstances of his journey through Europe, to describe the curiosities and wonders which he saw, and to give some account of the manners and customs of the various nations he visited...many of the customs, inventions, sciences, and ordinances of Europe, the good effects of which are apparent in those countries, might with great advantage, be imitated by the Mohammendans.²⁶

This evinces three things – a curiosity of the unknown, the willingness to familiarize and understand, and a desire to spread knowledge. Once again, we may locate a Kantian notion of cosmopolitan civilizational aspirations working beneath such an impetus as a logic, just as it does in discursive practices of English Coffee Houses and Habermas’s reading of the same. One might even want to consider that not many years after Abu Talib’s sojourn, Mīrzā Muhammad Ṣāliḥ Shīrāzī, one of the five Persian students who studied in England between 1815 to 1819 under the patronage of Abbas Mirza, crown prince of Iran, learnt the ‘art of printing’, brought back with him a printing machine to Persia. In 1837, Shīrāzī printed the first Persian newspaper – the ‘Khagaz-i-Shirazi’.²⁷ The same can also be noticed in India: in 1822, Raja Rammohan Roy started the weekly Persian newsletter ‘Mīrat-ul-Akhbar’,²⁸ which was published every week. The fact that these were published in Persian makes it obvious that Shīrāzī and Roy believed that there would be readership for printed media in the larger Indo-Persianate world. One might make the case for technological transmission from Europe, but against that, one can as easily argue that printing technology was first invented in China in the 11th century A.D. from where it travelled to Europe. Besides, technological determinism is suggestive of a linear conception of history caught within the telos of ‘development’ – rather, the making and usage of the printing press in 15th century Europe and early 19th century Persia and South Asia is part of larger societal processes already unfolding in these places, and the printing press as a technology and social phenomenon

²⁶ Abu Talib ibn Muhammad, Isfahani, (Daniel O’Quinn, and Charles Stewart). *The travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan in Asia, Africa and Europe, during the years 1799, 1800, 1801, 1802, and 1803.*, 59. Peterborough, Ontario: Broadview, 2009.

²⁷ Green, Nile. “Journeymen, Middlemen: Travel, Transculture, and Technology in the Origins of Muslim Printing.” *International Journal of Middle East Studies* 41, no. 2 (2009): 203–24. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40206102>.

²⁸ Codell, Julie F. “Introduction: The Nineteenth-Century News from India.” *Victorian Periodicals Review* 37, no. 2 (2004): 106–23. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/20084001>.

become both symptomatic and emblematic of the unfolding of aforementioned societal processes.²⁹

Coupled with this, the fact that Abu Talib was writing for an audience back at home (even if he was cynical about the possible reception of his work and readership) gives further evidence to the fact that among a certain class of people in the Indo-Persianate world, realizing the possibility of a sphere of intellectual discussion on society and politics at large between individuals, was not a strange occurrence.³⁰ Habermas has noted that the ‘republic of letters’ formed around English coffee houses and French salons had a problem of exclusion which might be linked to education and class-based opportunities, but he also noted that the ideal of the acceptance and debate between people and ideas, regardless of differences in power was ingrained in the making of such spaces.³¹ This also echoes what Ellis notes about the writing and circulation of newsletters and magazines in coffeehouses and how an ‘idea of civility’ operated in its functioning.³² Yet, what remains and becomes important in the case of Mirza Abu Talib and the European Enlightenment, is the idea of a utopia, where strangeness, both in terms of strangers/people and as ideas, can be encountered, debated, and accepted through mediation. This is at the centre of the globalizing drive of European modernity – to create a ‘world’ of ‘universal civilization’. Through a character like Mirza Abu Talib, and especially his understanding of Coffee Houses between London, Paris, Constantinople and Baghdad, it becomes apparent that it is possible to locate the drive to realise such a world order on a shared notion of civilizational values that was not local to Europe, but ‘Global’ despite of particularities. To ascertain this, let us look at what Abu Talib had to say about the Coffee Houses in Paris, Istanbul, and Baghdad, and what can be drawn out of his conclusions on them.

In Paris, Abu Talib notes:

²⁹ “The Technology and the Society (1974).” *Raymond Williams on Culture and Society: Essential Writings*, 2014, 139–60. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781473914766.n9>.

³⁰ I’m borrowing from C.A. Bayly’s characterisation of pre-colonial India as a ‘literacy-aware society’. Bayly, C.A. “Prologue: Surveillance and communication in early modern India.” In *Empire and Information: Intelligence gathering and social communication in India, 1780-1870*, 39. Cambridge University Press, 1996.

³¹ “Not that this idea of the ‘public’ was realised in earnest in the coffee houses, the *salons*, and the societies; but as an idea it had become institutionalized and thereby stated as an objective claim. If not realised, it was at least consequential” (Habermas 1989).

³² Ellis, Markman. “The Philosopher in the Coffee-House.” In *The Coffee House: A Cultural History*, 134–147. Orion Publishing, 2011.

In Paris, the coffee-houses are innumerable, but in general are very filthy; and as many of the French smoke segars or cheroots in them at all hours of the day, they smell shockingly of tobacco. A person is also much annoyed by beggars at these places: they follow a gentleman into the room and sometimes even take hold of his hand, to move his compassion, or rather to tire him by their importunity: they are, however, content with a trifle, and will sometimes be satisfied by a piece of bread: to obtain this favour, they have frequently to contend with a surly rival, in the form of a dog, whose filth is lying about in different parts of the room.³³

One might at the very onset notice his dislike of begging and be reminded of his critique of the same in context of Awadh – thus it is not a simple matter of denigrating the French in favour of the British. The mode of his critique though, becomes even more telling when one is to look at his impression at Coffee Houses in Constantinople:

The coffee-house and barbers' shops in this city are innumerable. The Turks, though very indolent, are not fond of retirement or solitude: they, therefore, immediately after breakfast, go to one of these places, where they sit smoking, drinking coffee or sherbet, and listening to idle stories, the whole day. Their conversations are carried on in a loud tone of voice, and sometimes eight or ten persons talk at the same time; it is therefore impossible for a foreigner to understand what they are saying; and, in short, the societies of these coffee-houses are little better than an assembly of brutes. The rooms are also exceedingly dirty and seldom afford anything but thick coffee, and tobacco cheroots or pipes.³⁴

In the case of both Paris, and Constantinople, the Coffee Houses are dirty, and full of smokers, with a general unwelcoming veneer. This is also the case in Baghdad: "Baghdad abounds with

³³ Abu Talib ibn Muhammad, Isfahani, (Daniel O'Quinn, and Charles Stewart). *The travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan in Asia, Africa and Europe, during the years 1799, 1800, 1801, 1802, and 1803.*, 242. Peterborough, Ontario: Broadview, 2009.

³⁴ Abu Talib ibn Muhammad, Isfahani, (Daniel O'Quinn, and Charles Stewart). *The travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan in Asia, Africa and Europe, during the years 1799, 1800, 1801, 1802, and 1803.*, 280. Peterborough, Ontario: Broadview, 2009.

coffee-houses, and rooms for smoking tobacco; but are even darker and filthier than those of Constantinople.”³⁵ The general critique of filth is something he also extends to the entire city of Baghdad, and the inns of Constantinople, which are: “Horrid places, the only good accommodation for a traveller in this city is at the French and English hotels in Galata.”³⁶

On this note, it is interesting to notice how Paris, Constantinople and Baghdad are placed in one coordinate when it comes to Coffee House cultures, whereas when it comes to hospitable places in Constantinople for a stranger, Abu Talib says that it is French and English hotels that are most welcoming. This breaks down the East-West binary ingrained in Saidian histories of Asia-Europe encounters. While all the Coffee Houses promote a culture of socialization, French and Ottoman Coffee Houses become sites that are unwelcoming due to filth and tobacco smoke, and also because the Ottomans converse in a manner that excludes the stranger. In comparison, English coffeehouses served as welcoming spaces where individuals gathered to socialize while reading newspapers and exchanging news and ideas. According to Abu Talib, this atmosphere encouraged participation and made it easier for strangers to feel included. This also recalls his comment on the Irish on the matter of acceptance and hospitality: “In...hospitality and prodigality, freedom of speech and open heartedness, they surpass the English and the Scotch...the landlady and her children soon comprehended my broken English...”³⁷

and how they went out of their way to “make themselves useful” to a foreign stranger.³⁸ In contrast, Paris, and to a greater degree, Constantinople, fail to inculcate a concourse of different people who can share ideas and mediate difference, thus becoming unwelcoming as places to Abu Talib. By making a stranger such as Abu Talib unwelcome, the figure of the stranger in the Coffee House becomes merely ornamental – a token gesture that becomes a metaphor for multicultural coexistences of cultures which are not in dialogue. Through his critique of the

³⁵ Abu Talib ibn Muhammad, Isfahani, (Daniel O’Quinn, and Charles Stewart). *The travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan in Asia, Africa and Europe, during the years 1799, 1800, 1801, 1802, and 1803.*, 350. Peterborough, Ontario: Broadview, 2009.

³⁶ Abu Talib ibn Muhammad, Isfahani, (Daniel O’Quinn, and Charles Stewart). *The travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan in Asia, Africa and Europe, during the years 1799, 1800, 1801, 1802, and 1803.*, 280. Peterborough, Ontario: Broadview, 2009.

³⁷ Abu Talib ibn Muhammad, Isfahani, (Daniel O’Quinn, and Charles Stewart). *The travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan in Asia, Africa and Europe, during the years 1799, 1800, 1801, 1802, and 1803.*, 111. Peterborough, Ontario: Broadview, 2009.

³⁸ Abu Talib ibn Muhammad, Isfahani, (Daniel O’Quinn, and Charles Stewart). *The travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan in Asia, Africa and Europe, during the years 1799, 1800, 1801, 1802, and 1803.*, 111. Peterborough, Ontario: Broadview, 2009.

ornamental figure of the foreigner in the Coffee-houses of Paris and Constantinople as opposed to the ones in London from a position that valorises encounters between strangers and a convivial exchange of knowledge (as exemplified by his description of the Irish whom he contrasted with the English and the Scots), Abu Talib makes a case for universal abstract notions of hospitality and cosmopolitanism that he realised through his praxis of travel and encountering strangeness.

While Abu Talib's critique of the French has been read as evidence of his imbibing the cultural stereotypes given by the British,³⁹ with whom it is easy to imagine a certain kind of collusion on his part, there is much that he said that can contradict such a reading. The lack of a circulation in knowledge in both France and Ottoman Turkey, is something that Abu Talib critiques based on the fundamental purpose of the pursuit and circulation of knowledge and understanding of the world, which are the motivations for him to undertake his journey and to record his sightings and findings in writing for others to read. This may also shed light on the comment on Turkish 'indolence' – indolence is not an essentialist character that Abu Talib assigns. In fact, he critiques it among his countrymen: *"The want of energy and the indolent dispositions of my countrymen, and the many erroneous customs which exist..."*⁴⁰

Most importantly, echoes of the same are found in the critique that he offers on the character of the English:

The fourth of their frailties is a desire of ease, and a dislike to exertion...it prevents them from perfecting themselves in science and exerting themselves in the services of their friends...the sixth defect of the English is their throwing away their time...⁴¹

³⁹ Smith, Blake. 2018. "The French are weak degenerates: An Indian voyager's account from Paris in early 19th century." *Scroll.in.* <https://scroll.in/magazine/865107/the-french-are-apatetic-and-feeble-an-indian-voyagers-account-from-paris-in-early-19th-century>.

⁴⁰ Abu Talib ibn Muhammad, Isfahani, (Daniel O'Quinn, and Charles Stewart). *The travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan in Asia, Africa and Europe, during the years 1799, 1800, 1801, 1802, and 1803.*, 59. Peterborough, Ontario: Broadview, 2009.

⁴¹ Abu Talib ibn Muhammad, Isfahani, (Daniel O'Quinn, and Charles Stewart). *The travels of Mirza Abu Talib Khan in Asia, Africa and Europe, during the years 1799, 1800, 1801, 1802, and 1803.*, 209. Peterborough, Ontario: Broadview, 2009.

In this broad critique of the English character based on what Abu Talib identifies as their desire for ease, (lining up with his critique of Turkish indolence), it is possible to locate Abu Talib's critique of the shallow quality of British engagement with Indian knowledge systems, as well as their failure to be as good in friendship as the Irish. This is done based on the same reasons he gives to explain the unwelcoming propensity of the Ottoman coffee houses to both strangers and knowledge, and the general decay of society in India. By focusing on knowledge, and how indolence is antithetical to the pursuit of the same, we can locate Abu Talib's pursuit of knowledge within an Islamic tradition of travelogues genres of *safarnama* and *rihla* as a way of venturing into the 'unknown'. These genres were marked by conception of curiosity and a drive to understand the 'natural world' – thus placing his travelogue on the same plane as that of its counterparts in Enlightenment humanism.

Finally, through the conscious act of travelling, knowing and engaging with what is strange or foreign, Abu Talib creates a framework of engaging with the world through certain values that cut across cultural lines and are applicable anywhere, thus making way for both multiplicity and the Enlightenment universalism. It is through this system that Abu Talib's critique of the Coffee Houses in Paris, Constantinople and Baghdad, and his preference of the same in case of the British must be understood. In establishing so, not only do I ascertain his critique and worldview as cosmopolitan – but through his focus on understanding and the stress on knowledge, the vision of an 18th century Indo-Persian intellectual converges seamlessly with the European Enlightenment's vision of knowledge and planetary cosmopolitanism. At the same time, this also answers Walter Mignolo's call for "decolonial cosmopolitanism(s)"⁴² which calls for engaging with knowledge from the 'margins': by analysing the writings of Mirza Abu Talib, a character from the colonial periphery, or 'margins' of the British Empire, not only do we find evidence of an exemplary praxis of cosmopolitanism from a non-western tradition, but it is also clear that Abu Talib himself did not operate within a mould of 'metropole and colony.' Abu Talib's writings neither exoticize nor idealize; rather, he recognised in these transregional coffeehouse cultures a shared potential for public deliberation and sociability. Thus, Abu Talib unsettles the neat opposition between the 'cosmopolitanism of reason,' which presumes the universal

⁴² Mignolo, Walter. "The Many Faces of Cosmo-Polis." *The Politics of Decolonial Investigations*, July 9, 2021, 181–228. <https://doi.org/10.1215/9781478002574-008>.

applicability of abstract norms, and the ‘cosmopolitanism of sentiments,’ which rests on affective recognition of cultural particularity. Abu Talib’s thought and practice move through and beyond this binary. His appreciation of the rational institutions of English public life –especially the coffeehouse and the newspaper –reveals his commitment to reasoned enquiry and universal ideas of sociability and improvement. Yet, this is never detached from an ethical attentiveness to context, sentiment, and embodied experience: whether in his critique of the exclusionary noise of Ottoman coffeehouses or his praise for Irish warmth and generosity, his judgments are always mediated by the relational ethos of travel and dialogue, making Abu Talib a practitioner of “methodological cosmopolitanism.”⁴³ In this sense, Abu Talib offers a mode of cosmopolitanism in which reason and sentiment are not opposed but braided –each grounding the other in his vision of a world where knowledge, hospitality, and self-reflection are shared civic virtues. In doing so, Abu Talib reorients the discourse of cosmopolitanism by demonstrating that such forms of theorising public life and cosmopolitanism were not exclusive to Europe, nor did they originate there in isolation, but through historical encounters shaped by the currents of imperialist globalisation.

In this regard, Mirza Abu Talib’s theoretical engagement with cosmopolitanism offers a compelling instantiation of what Gurinder Bhambra identifies as the need for *connected sociologies* –a mode of social analysis that recognises global modernity as the product of shared, imperial, and interconnected histories rather than as an endogenous European achievement. Abu Talib’s travels unfolded during a moment of profound transformation, when imperial expansion, shifting commercial circuits, and new technologies of communication were bringing distant peoples and institutions into intensified contact. His reflections thus emerge not from the margins of modernity, but from within its formative, global processes. Crucially, Bhambra reminds us that such transformations –often attributed solely to internal European development –were in fact co-constituted through imperial entanglements that linked Britain, South Asia, the Ottoman world, and beyond. Abu Talib’s observations of coffeehouse cultures, and his comparative reflections on public discourse, sociability, and governance across cities like London, Paris, Constantinople, and Baghdad, exemplify how individuals from colonised or semi-colonial

⁴³ Beck, Ulrich. “Mobility and the Cosmopolitan Perspective.” *Exploring Networked Urban Mobilities*, October 20, 2017, 140–51. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315201078-9>.

societies were actively engaging with, interpreting, and contributing to these transformations. His writings make visible the very global interconnections that Bhambra argues social theory must foreground: rather than treating colonial actors as peripheral to the making of modernity, Abu Talib's account demands we situate them as central interlocutors in its intellectual and institutional formation. His cosmopolitanism is not an imitation of European reason, but a historically grounded expression of worldliness shaped by the very structures of empire that enabled his movements and reflections.

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A Journey in the Land of Contradictions: The depiction of Romania in Swedish guidebooks 1964–1981

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Abstract

In the construction of countries as tourist destinations, travel literature – such as guidebooks – plays an integral role in deciding what places to visit and how these should be perceived. The Socialist Republic of Romania began a large-scale investment in its tourism industry in the 1950s, with ambitions of improving both its economic situation and international image. This initiative initially proved successful, as the country saw an increase in tourism from Western Europe, not least from Scandinavian countries. This paper focuses on how Swedish guidebooks published between 1964 and 1981 depicted Romania as a desirable tourist destination. These guidebooks were analysed qualitatively through the use of thematization and comparative analysis, taking into account their context of production. Using the theoretical frameworks of the tourist gaze and Balkanism, this study shows that the guidebooks construct a gaze of Romania as a semi-place – where Western influences meet Eastern, and the ancient meets the modern. The perspective of the tourist is of great importance in the construction of the gaze, as it determines which aspects of the country, modern versus ancient, are perceived as positive or negative. The perceived authenticity of the countryside, where time has seemingly stood still and where traditions are upheld, is a prominent and integral part of this gaze in the analysed guidebooks. Furthermore, similarities can be observed between the depiction within the guidebooks and the official image pushed by the Romanian tourism industry, both in the focus on the authentic

countryside, as well as in the emphasis on the authentic countryside and the nation's historical narrative centered on its Roman legacy. As this was a formative period for the Romanian tourism industry, it was equally guiding in the shaping of the Western tourist gaze of the country. By analyzing these guidebooks, this study contributes to the existing scholarship on Western perceptions of Eastern Europe, offering new insights into how Romania was depicted as a tourist destination during the Cold War era.

Keywords: Romania, tourist gaze, guidebooks, Sweden/Swedish

Introduction

“Not so many years ago, Romania was one of Europe's most neglected countries from a tourism perspective. It seemed remote and isolated. Now, Romania has opened its gates wide to tourists and will surely rank among the top tourist destinations of the 1970s.”⁴⁴

In the construction of a tourist destination, guidebooks play an integral part in deciding what places to visit and how these should be perceived.⁴⁵ The role of the guidebook is to guide the tourist through their destination by means of planned routes, telling them which destinations are worth visiting and how these places should be experienced. In their choices of what to include and what to exclude, the authors create their own version of the destination. The quote above comes from a Swedish guidebook about travels to the Socialist Republic of Romania, published in 1969 – a mere decade after Romania had begun its large-scale investments in its tourism industry.⁴⁶ Together with other guidebooks from this time, it serves to give insight into how this relatively new travel destination was marketed, and thereby constructed, to a group of tourists that the country paid certain attention to. Drawing upon the theoretical framework of

⁴⁴ Dagmar Hellstam, *Rumänien – En reseguide* (Stockholm: Aldus/ Bonniers, 1969), 5. ”För inte så många år sedan var Rumänien ett av Europas ur turistsynpunkt mest försummade länder. Det verkade avlägset och isolerat. Nu har Rumänien öppnat sina portar på vid gavel för turisterna, och kommer med all säkerhet att räknas till 70-talets främsta turistländer.”

⁴⁵ Victoria Peel and Anders Sørensen, ed., *Exploring the Use and Impact of Travel Guidebooks* (Bristol: Channel View Publications, 2016); Scott Laderman, “Guidebooks”, in *The Routledge Companion to Travel Writing*, ed. Carl Thompson (London: Routledge, 2016), 259.

⁴⁶ The Socialist Republic of Romania will from now on be referred to as Romania.

Tourist gaze and Balkanism, this article will show how Romania was marketed in Swedish guidebooks during a formative period of its tourism industry.

The development of the tourism industry in Romania was not unique to its time.⁴⁷ The 1950s saw the establishment of charter trips to Southern Europe, offering inexperienced travellers a safe, easy and affordable way of going abroad where food, transportation, accommodation and a knowledgeable guide was included in the price.⁴⁸ The accessibility of charter trips would become the starting point of mass tourism within Europe, which in popular holiday destinations such as Mallorca meant a rapid development of their tourism infrastructure – hotels, restaurants and other tourist-oriented facilities being built at a high rate. However, these extensive constructions meant that the destinations lost their local and “authentic” atmosphere. Combined with the large crowds of tourists, it created a demand for new, less exploited destinations – a demand that many Southeastern European countries hoped to fill.⁴⁹ Countries such as Yugoslavia, Albania, Bulgaria and Romania became attractive destinations for those seeking sunny beaches with less crowds, also often to lower prices.⁵⁰ While resorts already existed in these places, catering tourists from their own and neighbouring countries, the aim of attracting Westerners came with a rapid construction of more beach resorts.⁵¹ In Romania – under the Nicolae Ceaușescu regime – Western tourists were targeted for their economic benefit, and in pursuit of improving Romania’s international profile.⁵² The state-run travel agency Carpați (ONT) had extensive responsibilities over the tourism industry, both in its infrastructure in Romania and in the contact with other countries. Historian Adelina Stefan, who has done significant research on the tourism industry of socialist Romania, has shown that apart from sun

⁴⁷ For previous research on tourism industry in Eastern Europe, see Sune Bechmann Pedersen and Christian Noack, ed., *Tourism and travel during the Cold War: negotiating tourist experiences across the Iron Curtain* (London: Routledge, 2020); Anne E. Gorsuch and Diane P. Koenker, ed., *Turizm: The Russian and East European Tourist under Capitalism and Socialism* (New York: Cornell University Press, 2006). For Yugoslavia, see Hannes Grandits and Karin Taylor, ed., *Yugoslavia’s Sunny Side: A History of Tourism in Socialism (1950s–1980s)* (Budapest: Central European University Press, 2010).

⁴⁸ Orvar Löfgren, *On Holiday: a history of vacationing* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1999), 170.

⁴⁹ Löfgren, *On Holiday*, 178.

⁵⁰ Löfgren, *On Holiday*, 180; Francesco Zavatti, “The Stalinist utopia of the Adriatic: Swedish tourists in communist Albania”, in *Tourism and Travel during the Cold War: negotiating tourist experiences across the Iron Curtain*, ed. Sune Bechman Pedersen and Christian Noack (London: Routledge, 2020).

⁵¹ Adelina Stefan, “Vacationing in the Cold War: Foreign Tourists to Socialist Romania and Franco’s Spain, 1960s–1979s” (PhD diss., University of Pittsburgh, 2016), 90.

⁵² Stefan, “Vacationing,” 2; Juliana Maxim, “Emblems of Socialism: Romania’s Black Sea Resorts, 1950s–1960s” in *Coastal Architectures and Politics of Tourism: Leisurescapes in the Global Sunbelt*, ed. Sibel Bozdoğan, Panayiota Ioanni and Petros Phōkaidēs (Taylor & Francis Complete 2022 eBooks, 2022).

holidays, ONT marketed the country on the basis of its “rich folklore and traditions.”⁵³ This is also discussed by human geographer David Turnock, who showed that contemporary tourist maps published by ONT focused on places of cultural and historical significance.⁵⁴ While many Western tourists may have initially been drawn to Romania for their sun holidays, ONT made sure to also emphasise the vast possibilities for cultural tourism.⁵⁵ As Stefan has shown, these topics were also mirrored in Western travel material on Romania, which often favoured narratives of a rich folk culture combined with Roman legacy, one source going as far as presenting the Romanians as the “Romans of the East.”⁵⁶

To reach their prospective tourists, ONT made large advertisement campaigns, publishing guidebooks, magazines, brochures and flyers in foreign languages.⁵⁷ Stefan has shown that ONT had a particular focus on attracting tourists from West Germany and Scandinavia, as they were considered promising markets.⁵⁸ Drawing attention to the Scandinavian and thereby the Swedish market was not unique to Romania. Putnik, the Yugoslav state travel agency, signed tourist agreements with five foreign tourists agencies based in different Western countries in 1947, one of which being Sweden – At first glance a seemingly peculiar choice given the country’s small population.⁵⁹ However, research has shown that Scandinavians were particularly productive travellers, as the package-tour markets of Scandinavia were the largest in Europe per capita in the mid-1960s.⁶⁰ In the case of Sweden, this can be explained by the economic growth the country saw after the end of the Second World War paired with its avoidance of devastation during the war, as it remained officially neutral throughout. Additionally Sweden remained a

⁵³ Stefan, “Vacationing,” 60.

⁵⁴ David Turnock, “Romania” in *Tourism and economic development in Eastern Europe and the Soviet Union*, ed. Derek R. Hall (London: Bellhaven Press, 1991), 207.

⁵⁵ Dragoş Petrescu, “Closely Watched Tourism: The Securitate as Warden of Transnational Encounters, 1967-9,” *Journal of Contemporary History* 50, no. 2 (2015): 337–53, 343, <http://www.jstor.org.ludwig.lub.lu.se/stable/43697378>.

⁵⁶ Stefan, “Vacationing”, 139; Adelina Stefan, “Unpacking Tourism in the Cold War: International Tourism and Commercialism in Socialist Romania, 1960s–1980s,” *Contemporary European History* 32 (2023): 381, doi:10.1017/S0960777321000540.

⁵⁷ Stefan, “Unpacking,” 378.

⁵⁸ Adelina Stefan, “The lure of capitalism: Foreign tourists and the shadow economy in Romania, 1960–1989,” in *Tourism and Travel during the Cold War: negotiating tourist experiences across the Iron Curtain*, ed. Sune Bechman Pedersen and Christian Noack (London: Routledge, 2020), 49.

⁵⁹ Igor Tchoukarine, “The Yugoslav Road to International Tourism: Opening, Decentralization, and Propaganda in the Early 1950s,” in *Yugoslav Sunny Side: A History of Tourism in Socialism (1950s-1980s)*, ed. Hannes Grandits and Karin Taylor (Budapest: Central European University Press, 2010), 110.

⁶⁰ Thomas Kaiserfeld, “From Sightseeing to Sunbathing: Changing Traditions in Swedish package tours; from Edification by Bus to Relaxation by Airplane in the 1950s and 1960s,” *Journal of Tourism History* 2 (3) (2010): 152, doi:10.1080/1755182X.2010.523147.

“neutral” country, and thus largely non-problematic country to associate with, thanks to it being part of the Non-aligned Movement during the Cold War. Furthermore, the increase in international tourism was made possible by the introduction of paid vacation, which in Sweden was legislated at two weeks in 1938, extended to three weeks in 1951, four weeks in 1963 followed by five weeks in 1978.⁶¹ This meant that going abroad became increasingly accessible not only for the upper and middle classes, but also for the working class.⁶² Perhaps due to the marketing strategies of ONT, many Swedish tourists decided to visit Romania. As historian Sune Bechmann Pedersen points out, Scandinavia accounted for 10% of tourists who visited Romania in 1974 – a disproportionate amount given the size of its population.⁶³ Given the overrepresentation of Swedish tourists to Romania, the travel material they had access to thus makes up for an interesting case study for the overall Western tourist gaze, and is also a perspective that has not been researched before.

While many Swedish tourists decided to visit Romania, it must be noted that trips to authoritarian countries did not come without controversy. For example, the Swedish travel agency Reso faced criticism for including non-democratic countries in its programmes. However, excluding these countries would mean removing some of the most popular destinations such as Francoist Spain. The supply of charter trips was therefore determined by the demands of the customers rather than the political conditions of the country.⁶⁴ For the tourist, there was thus a certain normalisation of overlooking the political conditions prevailing in their destination. The political conditions were also in general not used as a selling point for tourism.⁶⁵ Unlike what has been popularised in post-communist spaces, Bechmann Pedersen pointed out that apart from Berlin, destinations in Eastern Europe were not marketed for being places to experience the East-West divide.⁶⁶ In the case of Romania, Stefan gives an example from a French guidebook,

⁶¹ Riksdagen, Knas, SOU 2001:91, Kurt Eriksson, *Frågor om arbetstidens längd och förläggning*, 2001, <https://data.riksdagen.se/fil/3F5E65C9-C268-4675-9443-F399C728B114>, 9.

⁶² Löfgren, “On Holiday,” 170.

⁶³ Sune Bechmann Pedersen, “A Paradise behind the Curtain: Selling Eastern Escapes to Scandinavians,” in *Eden för jeden?: Touristiske Sehnsuchtsorte in Mittel- und Osteuropa von 1945 bis zur Gegenwart*, ed. Bianca Hoening and Hannah Wadle (Göttingen: V&R unipress, 2019), 228.

⁶⁴ Carina Gråbacke, *När folket tog semester: studier av Reso 1937–1977*, (Lund: Sekel Bokförlag, 2008), 211.

⁶⁵ Still, political tourism existed, often related to a quest for political gains. For an article on Folkturist, a travel agency owned by the Communist Party of Sweden, see Sune Bechmann Pedersen, “Eastbound tourism in the Cold War: the history of the Swedish communist travel agency Folkturist,” *Journal of Tourism History* 10 (2) (2018), doi: 10.1080/1755182X.2018.1469679. On the topic of ‘friendship tourism’ to Albania organised by KMFL, a splinter party of the Swedish Left Party–The Communists, see Zavatti, “Stalinist Utopia.”

⁶⁶ Bechmann Pedersen, “A Paradise,” 228.

which assured its readers that they would not even notice being “behind the Iron Curtain.”⁶⁷ The political conditions were hence largely ignored or overlooked in the marketing of Eastern Europe.

Drawing upon the existing research on the Romanian tourism industry, combined with research on the Scandinavian marketing of trips to Eastern Europe as a greater region, this article shows how Romania was marketed to Swedish tourists in the formative years of the communist rule, 1947—1989.⁶⁸ The source material consists of all eight guidebooks on Romania published in Swedish during this period, the first one in 1964 and the last in 1981.⁶⁹ Apart from one, which also covers Bulgaria, they all focus solely on Romania. They all have short and informative titles such as “Romania in your pocket”, “Romania – A guide” and “The Black Sea Riviera.” While of varying lengths and structure, all guidebooks include both practical information regarding traveling to and in the country, as well as more in depth descriptions of the culture, food, and various regions of interest. These have been analysed through a thematic approach, wherein the initial readings focused on finding commonalities and irregularities in the content. The most prevalent themes have become the basis of the structure of the article, as seen in the two main themes *Romania as a melting point of different cultural influences* and *A blend of modern and ancient*. The construction of these themes has also been influenced by the theoretical framework of the paper, being *tourist gaze* and *Balkanism*. The tourist gaze, a theory developed by John Urry and Jonas Larsen, refers to the fact that tourists see their destination with a learnt gaze, which has been constructed in the interaction between their own experiences and societal perceptions. As previously mentioned, guidebooks play an important role in the construction of these perceptions, as their presentation creates an own version of the destination, which will be the one that the tourist seeks to experience.⁷⁰ Furthermore, Urry and Larsen argue that tourists

⁶⁷ Stefan, “Vacationing,” 140.

⁶⁸ For those interested in similar studies focused on post-communist Romania, I recommend Rodica Dimitriu, “When ‘we’ are ‘the other’. Travel books on Romania as exercises in intercultural communication,” *Perspectives* 20 (3) (2012), doi: 10.1080/0907676X.2012.702400.

⁶⁹ The guide books, in chronological order, are Arne Häggqvist, *Svartahavsrivieran : med utflykter i Rumänien och Bulgarien : badorter : sevärtheter : hotell : mat och dryck : shopping* (Stockholm: Bonnier, 1964); Kerstin Lundberg, *Rumänien – en vägledning* (Stockholm: Tidens Förlag, 1965); Ingemar Eile, *Rumänien i din ficka* (Växjö: Carl Svanberg AB, 1969); Hellstam, *Rumänien*; Agneta Uddenberg, *Rumänien* (Stockholm: Generalstabens Litografiska Anstalt, 1971); Rüdiger von Wechmar, *Turen går till Rumänien* (Stockholm: Almqvist & Wiksell Förlag AB, 1971); Per Olof Ekström, *Hälsokällornas land – Rumänien* (Göteborg: Zindermans 1975); Heinz and Peter Göckeritz, *Rumänien* (Lund: Generalstabens Litografiska Anstalt, 1981).

⁷⁰ John Urry and Jonas Larsen, *The Tourist Gaze 3.0* (London: Sage Publications Ltd, 2012), E-book, 3.

seek out what is extraordinary in relation to their everyday lives. Therefore, their gaze is shaped by what they perceive as different.⁷¹ In this way, the gaze structures and regulates the relationship with the “other,” dictating where the dividing lines are drawn and creating a greater distance between “us” and “them.”⁷² The social imaginaries that construct the tourist gaze of Romania, include what Maria Todorova calls *Balkanism*. Definitions of the Balkan region and what countries it consists of vary according to whether one has a historical, political or geographic approach. This article follows Todorova’s definition, which includes most of former Yugoslavia, Albania, Bulgaria, Greece and Romania.⁷³ According to Todorova, the Balkans is a construction of the West, created and maintained in Western journalistic and quasi-journalistic works, not least in travel material. The Balkans is supposed to act as a bridge between ‘the West’ and ‘the Orient’, a place where aspects of these supposed opposites could meet and interact. An image is constructed of a region riddled with ambiguity and contradictions, a ‘semi-place’ that is neither fully civilised nor uncivilised, not fully modern but not fully ancient.⁷⁴ In this article, I will argue that a Balkanist discourse can be identified in the guidebooks’ depictions of Romania.

Romania as a melting point of different cultural influences

Roman heritage and the Other

Roman heritage is largely present in the depiction of Romania in the guidebooks. Reference is made to the rich history of various places – health springs that have been in use ever since the Romans, vineyards that have existed since their time, and ruins of city walls that offer glimpses of bygone times.⁷⁵ In one of the guidebooks, the Roman conquest is even used as the starting point of the country’s history.⁷⁶ When recommending sights, the Roman heritage is often emphasized. This is the case for Constanța, a coastal town where “traces of Roman times remain in many parts of the city.”⁷⁷ Two authors give a detailed presentation of a statue of Ovid, a Roman poet who lived in the city as an exile. They also point out that there are plenty of other

⁷¹ Urry and Larsen, *Tourist*, 5.

⁷² Urry and Larsen, *Tourist*, 13.

⁷³ Maria Todorova, *Imagining the Balkans* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1997), 32.

⁷⁴ Todorova, *Imagining*, 19.

⁷⁵ Eile, *Rumänien*, 29; Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 74; Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 51.

⁷⁶ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 9.

⁷⁷ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 66. ”spår från romartiden finns kvar på många håll i staden.”

statues in the city, yet both end up giving a detailed presentation only of the statue of Ovid.⁷⁸ The focus on the Roman legacy is part of a general fondness for the ancient world. The authors gladly refer to towns by their ancient Greek names – Constanța becomes Tomis and Mangalia becomes Callatis.⁷⁹ The ruins of Histria, a colony of ancient Greece, are presented as an important and fascinating site, where traces of the country's earliest settlements can be seen.⁸⁰ The greatness of this site is even more evident in the description of it as the “Pompeii of Romania.”⁸¹ These recurring references give the reader the impression of a country with a history that is alive, where the ancient heritage can be sensed at every corner. In one guidebook, this is almost explicitly stated, as it refers to Constanța as a “living museum.”⁸² As Roman heritage plays a vital role in Western history, this particular focus on it has a way of connecting Romania to the West. It also interacts with the way that the Romanian regime wanted to portray the history of the country. Zavatti argues that giving value to Romanian national history and vast cultural heritage was one of many offsprings of a strategy of political legitimisation aimed at building internal consensus in Romania, and a global partnership for the Romanian communist leadership.⁸³ While Roman heritage was an important part of the Romanian identity even before the rise of communism, this heritage was further emphasised by Nicolae Ceaușescu, who used it to consolidate his own power.⁸⁴

⁷⁸ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 66; Lundberg *Rumänien*, 43–44.

⁷⁹ Lundberg *Rumänien*, 43; Eile, *Rumänien*, 27.

⁸⁰ Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 90; Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 77.

⁸¹ Lundberg *Rumänien*, 41. ”Rumäniens Pompeji.”

⁸² Ekström, *Hälsokällornas*, 43. ”ett levande museum”.

⁸³ Francesco Zavatti, “Writing History in a Propaganda Institute: Political Power and Network Dynamics in Communist Romania”, (PhD diss., Södertörn University, 2016), 268-270.

⁸⁴ Zavatti, “Writing History,” 87.

Moskén och Ovidius staty

Image 1: Constanta Mosque with statue of Ovid in the forefront. Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 1981, 27.

Beyond the Roman heritage, the guidebooks make some reference to Turkish influences. The local mosque is highlighted as an important sightseeing spot and referred to as the “Echo of the East” – East in this context referring to the Orient.⁸⁵ A similar depiction referring to the Orient is found in another guidebook:

If you walk from the beach up to the hillside behind it, you get a flavour of the oriental atmosphere that was typical of the city in the distant past. There is a cluster of old Turkish-style houses with carved wooden balconies and bay windows.⁸⁶

Constanța is thus presented as a mixture of East and West – an example of the meeting points that can be seen within Balkanist discourse. This meeting point becomes even more telling

⁸⁵ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 44–45. ”Ekot från öst.”

⁸⁶ Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 87. ”Om man från stranden går uppför sluttningen bakom får man en fläkt av den orientaliska atmosfären som var typisk för staden i gångna tider. Där finns ett gytter av gamla hus i turkisk stil med snidande träbalkonger och burspråk.”

in an image from the 1981 guidebook, where one is shown the mosque with the silhouette of the Ovid statue in front of it.

There are major differences in the presentation of Roman and Ottoman heritage, partly reflected in its scope. While Roman influence is a recurring theme, Ottoman heritage is not mentioned as often. To the reader, the frequent presence of the Roman heritage makes it seem like a natural part of Romanian history, like something that should belong in the Romanian identity. There are mentions of “Dacian and Roman ancestry”, where the Romans become as obvious ancestors as the Dacians.⁸⁷ This is even more evident in the way this heritage is approached. For example, one author describes how the Dacian kingdom was “incorporated” into the Roman empire, resulting in the use of the Latin language. In contrast, the author goes on to say that the language was then “subjected” to Turkish and other influences.⁸⁸ Unlike the natural legacy of the Romans, Ottoman influence is a result of threat and occupation. The guidebooks tell of fortifications built to keep out the “Turks” and of the violence and conquest the country has endured from Turkish forces.⁸⁹ Portraying the Turk/Ottoman as an enemy distanced the country from that part of its heritage, while creating a clearer belonging with the West. Just as the Orient is ‘the Other’ for the West, it is also not perceived as a natural part of Romania’s historical and cultural background. Here, the authors of the guidebooks continue to follow the official Romanian narrative. As Stefan has pointed out, guidebooks written by Romanian authors emphasised Romania’s role in defeating and stopping the Ottomans in the high Middle Ages, being part of and protecting Christian Europe.⁹⁰ Similarly, these guidebooks also heavily pushed the ancient Greek and Roman legacy.⁹¹

A, for the most part, southern people

The encounter with locals can in many cases be an aspect of selling a destination. It can bring a certain sense of authenticity to the trip, and a (perceived) insight into the culture and daily life of the country. In one of the guidebooks, this encounter is described as follows:

⁸⁷ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 111–112. ”dakiska och romerska förfäder.”

⁸⁸ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 38. ”inkorporerades,” ”utsättas.”

⁸⁹ Von Wechmar, *Turen*, 32, 37; Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 60. ”turkarna.”

⁹⁰ Stefan, “Unpacking,” 377-378.

⁹¹ Stefan, “Unpacking,” 377.

One is astonished to find a lively, sociable Romanesque people, where the gentlemen kiss the ladies' hands as if it were a given, and the joie de vivre and temperament come dangerously close to that of the Italians.⁹²

When reading this description, one can sense a certain level of surprise, perhaps because the author did not expect to meet a so-called Romanesque people given their Slavic neighbours. Nevertheless, similarities with people of other Romance cultures is a recurrent theme within the guidebooks. Just as the Roman legacy has left its marks on the country, it has on the people.⁹³ At concerts, their “southern way” of showing appreciation for music is said to be noticeable.⁹⁴ Their passion and temperament is also brought up in another guidebook, making reference to their “Latin temperament.”⁹⁵ Within Balkanist discourse, one can also find stereotypes of a hot temperament, then linked to being of Slavic or Turkish descent.⁹⁶ This difference can be explained by the fact that the temperament described in the guidebooks is presented as something positive, hence Latin, whilst the Balkanist temperament is negative and connected to violence.⁹⁷

For those seeking romance, the advice given by the guidebooks is also based on the Latin roots of the people. The women are said to be beautiful and flirtatious, but the reader is advised against attempts of arranging a meeting, as they are unlikely to show up. The reason why is that they supposedly have a “morality that – despite the low importance of the Church in the country – is very similar to that we know of hyper-Catholic countries of Spain and Italy.”⁹⁸ This claim is rather peculiar, given that the Orthodox church has played a significant role in the country throughout most of its history, including the communist period.⁹⁹ However, it reflects the regime's policy at the time of the publication, which sought to weaken the role of the Church in

⁹² Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 38. ”Man finner till sin häpnad ett livligt, sällskapligt romanskt folk, där herrarna kysser damerna på hand som en självklarhet och livsglädjen och temperamentet kommer farligt nära det italienska.”

⁹³ Von Wechmar, *Turen*, 6.

⁹⁴ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 52. ”sydländska sätt.”

⁹⁵ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 7. ”latinska temperament.”

⁹⁶ Todorova, *Imagining*, 123–124.

⁹⁷ Todorova, *Imagining*, 122.

⁹⁸ Häggqvist, *Svartahavsriveran*, 8. ”en moral som – trots kyrkans ringa betydelse i landet – mycket liknar den vi känner från de hyperkatolska länderna Spanien och Italien.”

⁹⁹ Kurt Treptow and Marcel Pope, *Historical Dictionary of Romania* (London: The Scarecrow Press, 1996), 154.

Romanian society.¹⁰⁰ The author goes on to describe Romanian men, who in contrast to the women have “neither the impulsive impetuosity of the Italians nor the erotic calculation of the French.”¹⁰¹ In other words, “they are correct or shy and do not chase foreign girls.”¹⁰² These comparisons depend on the reader sharing the same gaze of Spain and Italy as highly religious countries, and stereotypes of Italian and French men as romantically savvy. The fact that the comparison is continued with stereotypes of other Latin peoples, even when the stereotypes in question do not fit the image of Romanians, suggests that they as a people belong together. It should also be emphasised that these kinds of comparisons are never made with stereotypes of Slavs, perhaps to not disturb or contradict the continuous connections made with the supposed Latin roots. At the same time, the guidebooks do mention encounters with more than just Latin temperament in the country:

And the people themselves – those who stand out most clearly after a tour become a diverse collection: the little farmer up north with a Tolstoy beard, who with a dignified bow declines a tip after a favour; peach-skinned nuns who show us around the monasteries and politely converse in French and English; the gypsy musician’s big velvet eyes as he caressingly plays out melodies next to the restaurant table...¹⁰³

The reader is presented with a picture of a country with a diverse population where one can encounter several different groups. This image fits well with the Balkanist construction of the Balkans as an area with an “inextricable medley of disparate races.”¹⁰⁴ Yet the minorities of the country rarely appear in the guidebooks. While the Hungarian and German groups are given some amount of space, the above quote is the only time the Roma minority is mentioned. An explanation to this may be the long history of discrimination and negative stereotypes towards

¹⁰⁰ Cristina Rada Irmire, “Religion and political identification in Communist Romania,” *Revista de Stiinte Politice* 2 (4) (2014): 52, <https://www.ceeol.com/search/article-detail?id=287520>.

¹⁰¹ Häggqvist, *Svartahavsriveran*, 8. “vare sig italienarens impulsiva gåpåighet eller fransmännens erotiska beräkning.”

¹⁰² Häggqvist, *Svartahavsriveran*, 8. ”De är med andra ord korrekta eller blyga och jagar inte utländska flickor.”

¹⁰³ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 7. ” Och människorna själva – de som framträder klarast efter en rundresa blir en brokig samling: den lille bonden med Tolstojkägga uppe i norr, som med en värdig bugning avböjer drickspenning efter en tjänst; persikohyade nunnor som visar runt i klostren och belevat konverserar på franska och engelska; zigenarmusikantens stora sammetsbrunnar till ögon då han smeker fram melodier vid restaurangbordet...”

¹⁰⁴ Todorova, *Imagining*, 34.

the minority in Sweden, making them a group that is not desirable to bring up when trying to market a tourist destination. The overall depiction is nevertheless of Romania as a varied and multicultural country, where the Latin roots show the clearest of all.

Transylvania as a multicultural place

In addition to Roman and Ottoman influences, Romania also shows traces of the rule of various German, Slavic and Hungarian groups throughout its history. Compared to the Roman and Ottoman, these other legacies are not as visible in the depiction of the country. The exception is the depiction of Transylvania. The region encapsulates the tumultuous history of the country, as it has for long periods been under both German and Hungarian rule. There is mention of the still existing Hungarian minority in the region, with their own distinct culture and traditions.¹⁰⁵

The importance given to the German heritage in Transylvania varies in the guidebooks. What should be noted here is that two of the guidebooks were originally written and published in German by German authors, and later translated and reworked for a Swedish audience. In these two, one notices a larger emphasis on German heritage, especially in the descriptions of the towns that were founded by them, claiming that strong cultural links still exist there.¹⁰⁶ If visiting Sibiu, one is advised to visit the German-language city theatre as well as the Brukenthal Museum, a museum with Saxon roots, claimed to be one of the most interesting museums in the country.¹⁰⁷ Similar emphasis is not found in the guidebooks originally published in Swedish. As an example, the role of the Saxon settlers in building a thriving community in Sibiu is briefly mentioned, but more attention is paid to the Roman heritage of the city.¹⁰⁸ The fact that German connections are found in German guidebooks reflects how these were originally written for a different readership, who would have been much more interested in the aspects that create a sense of community for them with Romania. Hence, one can see here a gaze constructed for a different audience than the Swedish.

¹⁰⁵ Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 63.

¹⁰⁶ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 56; von Wechmar, *Turen*, 5.

¹⁰⁷ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 57.

¹⁰⁸ Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 59.

Due to Transylvania being a “mixture of German, Hungarian and Romanian”, one of the guidebooks calls it the most genuine part of Romania.¹⁰⁹ This description is a telling example of the presence of the Balkanist discourse. Romania is not only a meeting point of East and West, but also a place where different cultures meet and interact, despite their differences. By linking multiculturalism and authenticity, the constructed gaze is one that makes the reader expect to encounter a multicultural land, similar to how other Balkan countries are described. What is not included in this gaze, however, is the conflicts that have led to said multiculturalism. Transylvania is a region that has been disputed between Romania and Hungary since the Middle Ages.¹¹⁰ By not providing this context, the idyllic image of an interesting, multicultural place, where different groups live in harmony, can be created.

A blend of modern and ancient

Modern seaside resorts

Sol och sommar över stranden vid Mamaia, en av de populäraste badorterna vid Svarta havet

Image 2: Illustration of Mamaia, with the description “Sun and summer across the beaches at Mamaia, one of the most popular seaside resorts along the Black Sea”. Von Wechmar, *Turen går till Rumänien*, 1971, 3.

¹⁰⁹ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 116. ” en blandning av tyskt, ungerskt och rumänskt.”

¹¹⁰ Treptow and Popa, *Historical*, 202.

During the 1960s, Romanian charter tourism was on the rise. The Black Sea coast had been a popular tourist destination for the Romanian upper class throughout the 1900s.¹¹¹ In the 1950s, the state made large-scale investments for the construction of hotels and leisure environments along the coastline. This development was part of a more wide-scale democratization of vacation that began in the 1930s throughout Europe.¹¹² Hence, the Romanian seaside went from an exclusive site for the Romanian elite to a destination for the larger masses.¹¹³ A decade later, attention started to significantly be put more towards Western tourists – both for the possibility of greater revenue and international recognition, but also as an attempt to showcase how great life could be under socialism.¹¹⁴ The development of these socialist resorts are chronicled in the contemporary Swedish guidebooks, which describe how magnificent and modern hotels, restaurants, theatres and cinemas sprung up along the coast.¹¹⁵ Mamaia was the most established seaside resort at this time, and the place to which most of the charter holidays went.¹¹⁶ Enough Scandinavian tourists travelled here for the establishment of a number of hotels where only Swedes, Danes and Norwegians stayed.¹¹⁷ The rapid development of the town is described in the 1965 guidebook as follows:

The monumental, matte-white silhouette of *Hotel Parcs* introduces the hotel complex of this modern seaside resort. Before the Second World War, Mamaia had only one hotel. Now there are around thirty, almost all of the same standard. Mamaia is a town steeped in legend, but you don't need a fairytale to enjoy its charm. The soothing waves of the Black Sea lulls you to sleep in the evenings and reawakens the spirit of life in the early hours of the morning. The air is clear and fresh, the water crystal blue and cooling, leaving behind a saturated saltiness in the skin.¹¹⁸

¹¹¹ Maxim, *Emblems*, 74, 83.

¹¹² Maxim, *Emblems*, 74.

¹¹³ Maxim, *Emblems*, 74.

¹¹⁴ Stefan, "Vacationing," 2; Maxim, *Emblems*, 72.

¹¹⁵ Häggqvist, *Svartahavsrivieran*, 27.

¹¹⁶ Eile, *Rumänien*, 20.

¹¹⁷ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 30.

¹¹⁸ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 29. "Hotell Parcs monumentala, mattvita silhuett introducerar den moderna badortens hotellkomplex. Före andra världskriget hade Mamaia endast ett hotell. Nu finns där ett trettioal, alla av nästan samma standard. Mamaia är en legendomspunnen ort, med det behövs inga sagor till för att njuta av traktens charm. Svarta havets sövande bränningar vaggas till ro om kvällarna och väcker livsandarna på nytt tidiga morgontimmar. Luften är klar och frisk, vattnet klarblått och svalkande och lämnar efter sig en mättad sälta i skinnet."

Mamaia is depicted as a beautiful and peaceful place. Similarly, the 1964 guidebook showcases the town's first-class hotels and excellent beaches.¹¹⁹ The “monumental” *Hotel Parcs* was one of many newly built hotels, all in the same style and stucco as determined at state level, described as ultramodern by many of the authors.¹²⁰ However, it is not portrayed as a perfect paradise, and its flaws are linked – albeit not explicitly – to the socialist rule. These hotels are described as “standardised” and are admitted at first sight to give a “sterile impression”, referring to their ultramodern architecture and uniform furnishing.¹²¹ Even the restaurants are described as standardised, as they all have identical interiors and menus. This is also reflected in later guidebooks, which describe the hotels as “too functional.”¹²² In all of these cases, the standardisation is seen as something negative which makes the resorts lose their charm.

The last guidebook, published in 1981, also takes issue with the standards of the resorts. The high quality described in the 1960s does not seem to have been maintained. The 1981 guidebook warns its reader that they should not hope for “Western European standards” but must rather “expect things to take time to be repaired, for example, you may encounter burnt-out lightbulbs, broken wallpaper and other things you have to overlook.”¹²³ The stagnation in quality mirrors the timeline provided by Stefan – Romania investing heavily in its tourism industry until the late 1970s, when the investments saw a downturn due to both the general economic stagnation and as the regime had been unable to achieve the goals they had hoped for.¹²⁴

One issue of the seaside resorts that persists throughout the period is the lack of authenticity. This is especially remarkable, as many tourists chose countries like Romania as they hoped to have a more authentic experience than what was offered at more mainstream and popular destinations. It also clearly shows the problematic nature of the demands of “authenticity” when choosing to travel to a place solely built for tourism. By demanding what they deem as authentic, the tourist is also exoticising their destination by seeking out for it to be more different and thereby be up to their expectations. Of course, these kinds of reflections fall outside the scope of

¹¹⁹ Häggqvist, *Svartahavsriveran*, 19.

¹²⁰ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 30; Eile, *Rumänien*, 20; Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 62.

¹²¹ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 30. ”standardiserade”, sterilt intryck.”

¹²² Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 24. ”för funktionella.”

¹²³ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 24–25. ”räkna med att det tar tid innan saker och ting lagas, man kan t ex råka ut för utbrända glödlampor, trasiga tapeter och annat man måste överse med.”

¹²⁴ Stefan, “Vacationing”, 74.

the guidebooks. In the 1965 guidebook, the atmosphere in Mamaia is described as “entirely continental and very little Romanian.”¹²⁵ The authors are careful to emphasize that one should expect nothing but intercontinental food at the hotel restaurants and recommend their readers to seek out smaller restaurants where they might actually experience genuine Romanian cuisine.¹²⁶ In the search for authenticity, however, there is one seaside resort in particular that is said to go against the trend: Mangalia. Mangalia is described as an “authentic community with a Romanian population.”¹²⁷ One of the 1969 guidebooks states that the resort is intended to be a new, larger version of Mamaia.¹²⁸ Yet in the 1981 guidebook, it is clearly stated that Mangalia is not a “hotel village” but rather a “charming small town with numerous historical remains.”¹²⁹ This statement is especially remarkable given the extent of demolition and construction that occurred in Mangalia. Architectural historian Juliana Maxim points out that the region, while described in state propaganda as a savage and uncultured land, was one of the most culturally diverse places in Europe before the construction of the resorts.¹³⁰ Mangalia in specific was the longest continuously inhabited city in Romania, with a large Turkish and Tatar population whose histories were largely removed from the urban space in favour of the construction of the resorts.¹³¹ Meanwhile, the remains of the Greek colony of Callatis were heavily emphasised, even more so as the guidebooks referred to Mangalia by the name of the ancient colony. It becomes clear that the depiction of Mangalia as a more authentic alternative had little to no actual basis in reality. As with any other resort town, any perceived “authenticity” was rather the result of the state trying to meet the needs and expectations of the tourists. In the case of Mangalia, this meant the removal of its contemporary cultural diversity in favour of exhibiting the ruins of ancient times. As the guidebooks also highlight the town as authentic, they continue the narrative of the Romanian state.

¹²⁵ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 30. ”helt kontinental och mycket lite rumänsk.”

¹²⁶ Eile, *Rumänien*, 17; Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 13; Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 104.

¹²⁷ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 76. ”ett autentiskt samhälle med rumänsk befolkning.”

¹²⁸ Eile, *Rumänien*, 27.

¹²⁹ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 36. ”hotellby”, ”charmig småstad med talrika historiska lämningar.”

¹³⁰ Maxim, *Emblems*, 82.

¹³¹ Maxim, *Emblems*, 82.

Health spas – Modern science with historic legacy

Just as seaside resorts were popular destinations, the Romanian thermal spas were of great interest to the Western tourist – interesting enough for there to be a guidebook with them as its sole focus.¹³² Their popularity reflects the investments made by the Romanian state in its health resorts after the Second World War, precisely with the aim of attracting more tourists.¹³³ In the presentation of the health resorts, there is a strong emphasis on the scientific basis of the treatments and the involvement of specialists, ensuring that all of them are run by “specially trained doctors.”¹³⁴ “Health-giving” springs are promised to benefit those struggling with everything from rheumatism and heart disease to digestive problems and liver disorders.¹³⁵ The clinics are supposedly modern with equipment that is up to date.¹³⁶ The authors also emphasize the cooperation between Swedish and Romanian doctors, which gives a further boost in confidence to the treatments.¹³⁷

The history of the spas is also of great importance to the authors. The treatments performed are not “some new miracle method” but rather techniques that supposedly go back over 2000 years.¹³⁸ Baile Herculane is marketed as one of the country’s most traditional spas. There, one can bathe in the same thermal springs that were used by the Romans, while overlooking a statue of Hercules.¹³⁹ The marketing creates an image of spas that are both ancient and modern, an interplay between the old and the new, reinforcing this common theme.

Bucharest – A capital in transition

A trip to the country’s capital is a staple in the guidebooks, all of which have a dedicated section on Bucharest. In their depictions, the city is a mixture of opposites – old meets new, greenery meets industry, and Parisian elements meet Stalinist architecture.

¹³² Ekström, *Hälsokällornas*.

¹³³ George Erdeli, Ana Irina Dincă, Aurel Gheorghilaş, Camelia Surugiu, “Romanian Spa Tourism: A Communist Paradigm in a Post Communist Era,” *Journal of Studies and Research in Human Geography* 5 (2) (2011): 43, doi: 10.5719/hgeo.2011.52.41.

¹³⁴ Von Wechmar, *Turen*, 19. ”specialutbildade läkare.”

¹³⁵ Von Wechmar, *Turen*, 19. ”Hälsobringande.”

¹³⁶ Ekström, *Hälsokällornas*, 25.

¹³⁷ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 55.

¹³⁸ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 55.

¹³⁹ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 70.

The authors are not shy of calling the city the “Paris of the Balkans” or “Little Paris.”¹⁴⁰ The city – with its wide avenues and boulevards, and a triumphal arc – has a “continental flavour” supposedly similar to Paris.¹⁴¹ The use of this epithet is not unique to the guidebooks, as the city has been compared to Paris since the nineteenth century. Bucharest has been the capital of Romania since its independence in 1878. Notwithstanding the multiple rulers with different ideologies that came to power, the development of the city has since then been constant.¹⁴² These developments were made with great inspiration from the latest urban and architectural trends in France and Italy, to continue showcasing the alleged Latin roots and historical ties with Western Europe.¹⁴³ Similarly, Bucharest acted as an important cultural centre, where French culture was particularly sought after.¹⁴⁴ The guidebooks provide the same image of a highly cultural city, with an unusual number of museums and a vibrant opera and theatre scene.¹⁴⁵ Hence, the authors support and thereby continue the image constructed by the Romanian state.

Another sign of the Parisian city planning is the labelling of Bucharest as a green metropolis.¹⁴⁶ The first impression is of “greenery, light, airiness”, in a city where cleanliness is said to have been a priority, with a successful anti-litter law and streets washed daily.¹⁴⁷ The guidebooks emphasise the many parks and lakes, which give the city a certain sense of calm.¹⁴⁸ When new neighbourhoods are built, they are designed with the preservation of green spaces in mind.¹⁴⁹ However, this seemingly verdant city is also said to be an industrial centre, accounting for 20% of the state’s industrial output.¹⁵⁰ It is mentioned that some 50 new industries had been built since 1948.¹⁵¹ This remark becomes one of the clearest references to the prevailing

¹⁴⁰ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 59.

¹⁴¹ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 59; Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 29; Häggqvist, *Svartahavsriveran*, 38; von Wechmar, *Turen*, 25. ”kontinental prägel.”

¹⁴² Maria Raluca Popa, “Bucharest,” in *Capital Cities in the Aftermath of Empires*, ed. Emily Gunzburger Makaš and Tanja Damljanović Conley (Taylor & Francis e-Library, 2009), E-book, 62.

¹⁴³ Popa, “Bucharest,” 62.

¹⁴⁴ Roxana Verona, “Bucharest at the crossroad” *Publications of the Modern Language Association of America* 122 (1) 76, <http://ludwig.lub.lu.se/login?url=https://www.jstor.org/stable/25501688>.

¹⁴⁵ Von Wechmar, *Turen*, 25; Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 69.

¹⁴⁶ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 16.

¹⁴⁷ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 59; Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 81. ”grönska, ljus, luftighet.”

¹⁴⁸ Häggqvist, *Svartahavsriveran*, 38.

¹⁴⁹ Eile, *Rumänien*, 33.

¹⁵⁰ Häggqvist, *Svartahavsriveran*, 38; Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 59; Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 81.

¹⁵¹ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 81.

industrialization that Romania underwent during the period, a significant part in their process of modernisation.¹⁵² It also stands as a clear contradiction to the imagery of the city as green.

In 1965, Bucharest was described as a “changing city with a pleasant mixture of old and new”, where “old unsanitary residential areas are being demolished to make way for new complexes with central heating and all the modern conveniences” and where neighbourhoods are growing at an “explosive speed.”¹⁵³ In the guidebooks, Bucharest is generally portrayed as a relatively young city, where culturally significant buildings are no older than 400 years.¹⁵⁴ The city is said to be devoid of Romanesque and Gothic styles, as much of it had been destroyed by war and earthquakes.¹⁵⁵ The buildings mentioned in the various books show influences from several places and periods – neo-Gothicism, French Renaissance and Greek Church art.¹⁵⁶ Socialist rule is also presented, with descriptions of buildings in Stalinist style.¹⁵⁷ Overall, the impression is of a city in transition, with influences from many directions, which is in many ways similar to how the country is generally portrayed. In the construction of the new, the memory of the old prevails. The reader is left with a conflicting picture of the Romanian capital, a supposedly green, cultural and beautiful Balkan-version of Paris with its older architecture, while simultaneously being a city full of industry and construction. In a sense, the authors capture the process of transition that not only the capital was undergoing, but also the entire country.

A countryside stuck in the past

Beyond the polished surface of the seaside resorts and the complexity of its capital, one finds the Romanian countryside. According to the authors, the countryside is where it is possible to experience the most authentic version of Romania. The authenticity experienced in Transylvania, as discussed earlier, is largely based on the region’s multiculturalism, but also concerning how it has preserved its traditions and a more old-fashioned way of life. In smaller communities across

¹⁵² Eric J. Hobsbawm, *Ytterligheternas tidsålder: det korta 1900-talet: 1914–1991* (Stockholm: Rabén Prisma, 1997), 298, 331–332.

¹⁵³ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 60. ”föränderlig stad med behaglig blandning av gammalt och nytt”, ”Gamla osanitära bostadsområden rivs för att lämna plats åt nya komplex med centralvärme och alla moderniteter”, ”explosiv fart.”

¹⁵⁴ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 16.

¹⁵⁵ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 16.

¹⁵⁶ Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 35; Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 19.

¹⁵⁷ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 20.

the country, it is possible to see a simpler way of life, steeped in tradition. It is an experience recommended to all kinds of travellers, even those whose plans might just be to visit the beach, as a trip to the countryside is the best way to get closer to the country.¹⁵⁸

In the countryside, the tourist will encounter a very different world to that they are used to back in Sweden, one that seems to have been isolated from the development of the rest of the world.¹⁵⁹ The traffic on the roads consist of “all kinds of carts, sheep, geese, cows, and little girls, who in the villages use the country road as a place for community.”¹⁶⁰ The architecture is different depending on the region, and is said to be a “manifestation of the collective, deeply rooted in everyday material” – a spiritual, social, and cultural environment.¹⁶¹ In the description of Maramureş, one author goes as far as likening someone’s home to an ethnographic museum:

The old-fashioned villages are characterised by small wooden houses, built of horizontal logs, with high thatched or shingled roofs and finely sculpted verandas with lots of flowers. Cross the threshold of the house and you enter a small ethnographic museum. The people have a deep love for fabrics. They cover floors, tables, beds and walls.¹⁶²

¹⁵⁸ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 20.

¹⁵⁹ Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 63.

¹⁶⁰ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 20. ”alla tänkbara kärror, får, gäss, kossor och små gummor, som i byarna använder landsvägen som ett enda gemensamt sällskapsrum.”

¹⁶¹ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 111–112. ”manifestation av kollektivet, djup rotfast vid vardagsmaterial, andlig, social och kulturell miljö.”

¹⁶² Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 67–68. ”Byarnas ålderdomliga bebyggelse karaktiseras av små trähus, byggda av liggande stockar, med höga halm- eller spåntak och fint skulpterade verandor med mängder av blommor. Går man över husets tröskel kommer man in ett litet etnografiskt museum. Människorna har en djup kärlek till vävnader. De täcker golv, bord, sängar och väggar.”

Image 3 (on the left): Cover of Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 1971, an illustration of men in traditional clothing playing instruments and dancing.

Image 4 (on the right): Cover of von Wechmar, *Turen går till Rumänien*, 1971, an illustration of a woman in traditional clothing and a headscarf.

This portrayal reflects the tourist gaze we have, and create, around the countryside as an old-fashioned place steeped in folk culture. The houses, which are likened to museums, become objects for the tourist to enjoy. Similarly, one can look towards the portrayal of the people, who are repeatedly described as wearing folk costumes on a daily basis.¹⁶³ Traditional clothing often appears in the illustrations and images in the guidebooks, and can be seen on the covers of many of them. The use of something as traditional as folk costumes, which are even said to be worn while working in the fields, becomes an affirmation of their gaze, and therefore an important part of their narrative.¹⁶⁴

¹⁶³ Von Wechmar, *Turen*, 10; Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 7; Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 67.

¹⁶⁴ Von Wechmar, *Turen*, 10.

Similarly, the culture and way of life of the people are presented in a way that confirms this view. Romania is described as the country with the richest folklore in Europe, where folk music and dance permeate everyday life.¹⁶⁵ A picture is painted of an utmost vibrant countryside, where people feel a strong connection to music, culture and tradition. According to one of the authors, this strong bond stems from the many centuries of external threats and invasions that the country has endured, periods when culture was the only thing that could hold the Romanian people together.¹⁶⁶ Traditions have been preserved, not least in terms of wedding celebrations. Wedding ceremonies have supposedly not lost any of their originality, still faithful to old traditions.¹⁶⁷ In one of the guidebooks, one can read about the wedding garments, emphasising the great details of these home-made costumes:

The groom, the bride and the entire bridal party are dressed in their hand-woven and home-stitched traditional costumes. Trousers, skirts, blouses, aprons, hats, shoes and boots – everything is embroidered and embellished, sometimes in muted colours, but usually in bright colours, giving free reign to the anonymous creative spirit of the people.¹⁶⁸

The author goes on to describe an ancient tradition that is said to still be followed, where the man hires, “according to custom, a group of men to guard her [the bride] against ‘evildoers’ who want to ‘steal’ her away.”¹⁶⁹ This traditional peasant wedding can be contrasted with a wedding experienced by another author at a restaurant in Bucharest, who disappointedly tells their reader that the wedding couple was very Westernised in their attire.¹⁷⁰ She goes on to point out that one has to go to the countryside to experience the weddings that follow old traditions – those that are

¹⁶⁵ Von Wechmar, *Turen*, 10; Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 7; Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 112.

¹⁶⁶ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 7.

¹⁶⁷ Von Wechmar, *Turen*, 10.

¹⁶⁸ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 99. ”Såväl brudgummen som bruden och hela brudföljet är klädda i sina handvävda och hemsömmade folkdräkter. Byxor, kjortlar, blusar, förkläden, hattar, skor och stövlar – allt är broderat och utsmyckat, ibland i nerdämpade färger, men oftast i granna kulörer, där befolkningens anonyma skaparlynnne fått fritt utlopp.”

¹⁶⁹ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 99–100. ”enligt hävd en skara män att vakta henne mot ’illasinnade’, som vill ’röva bort’ henne”.

¹⁷⁰ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 32.

authentically Romanian.¹⁷¹ In the eyes of the authors, Romanian weddings should clearly not have any signs of Western contact. As the countryside, they should preserve their own culture and traditions, keeping a sense of authenticity for the tourists to experience.

A modernity in the making

Romania's attachment to its traditions stood out as an important selling point for the Swedish tourist. As 'the hustle and bustle' had not yet reached this seemingly untouched land, it offered an escape from modernity and everything that it brought. Romania presented an opportunity to experience a simpler, more traditional way of life, where people still dressed in traditional clothing in their everyday lives. While romanticising this image, the authors also raise concerns about how long this kind of life will continue, since Romania was also a country in transition. Hence, they express a certain sense of urgency for those who want to experience this authenticity: "You have to hurry to experience the old before the hustle and bustle of time, modernisation and industrialisation have erased the still existing patina, charged with historical memories."¹⁷²

Modernisation and industrialisation are portrayed as a threat to the ancient culture and traditions that the country has to offer. Remarkably, it is the 1981 guidebook, published after two decades of rapid modernisation and industrialisation, that raises this concern.¹⁷³ Thus, it becomes questionable how truthful this representation was, and if it was not rather about what the author wanted Romania to be. Romania, as a place where modernity has not yet reached, fits well into the Balkanist discourse of a semi-civilised region who has not come as far as the Western sphere. The process of modernisation becomes something negative, as it goes against what the country should be – without its antiquity it loses its authenticity. Rather than highlighting the positive effects of modernisation, they romanticise the aspects of a 'simpler' life, without the stresses of modernity experienced at home. Romania thus takes on a symbolic role of the longing for simpler times.

¹⁷¹ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 32.

¹⁷² Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 4. "Man måste skynda för att få uppleva det gamla innan tidens jäkt, moderniseringen, industrialiseringen suddat ut den patina, som ännu finns, laddad av historiska minnen."

¹⁷³ Hobsbawn, *Ytterligheternas*, 298, 331–332.

Unlike at home

In selling a destination, it is also important that the guidebook can recognise any shortcomings and things to be prepared for that might be of importance in the planning of the trip. In the case of Romania, this mainly concerns consumer goods and their availability. On the topic of what one should bring with them from home, some suggest items such as nylon stockings and cosmetics, as these are said to be both expensive and of low quality in Romania.¹⁷⁴ Others highlight that consumer products like those make excellent gifts for the helpful service staff, as they are sought-after items that are otherwise difficult to obtain for Romanians.¹⁷⁵ Through these recommendations, the authors reflect the reality of living in contemporary, communist Romania, which completely de-prioritised the production and import of consumer goods.¹⁷⁶ Likewise, the reader is discouraged from buying clothes in the country, as its fashion is described as very different from what one would expect at home:

However, if you want to experience the latest fashion, be up to date by reading Swedish newspapers and have everything that you are used to at home, Romania may not be on your mind. Romania is an Eastern state where much differs from what is available at home.¹⁷⁷

In the quote above, the differences encountered are explicitly explained by the country being an Eastern state – a term that is rarely encountered otherwise. In general, Romania being a communist and *Eastern* state seems like something that the authors seek to avoid. Apart from concise introductory information on the governing of the country, it is a topic that is only brought up in relation to fashion and consumer goods.¹⁷⁸ It is only relevant when it affects the tourist. Simultaneously, the lack of consumer goods and differences in fashion become further evidence of the difference in modernity between Romania and Sweden. In contrast to the negative

¹⁷⁴ Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 10.

¹⁷⁵ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 37; Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 119.

¹⁷⁶ Stefan, "The lure", 51–52.

¹⁷⁷ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 4. "Däremot har man kanske inte Rumänien i tankarna om man vill uppleva senaste modet, följa med vad som händer i svenska tidningar och ha allt som man är van vid hemifrån. Rumänien är en öststat där mycket avviker från det man har på hemmaplan."

¹⁷⁸ Häggqvist, *Svartahavsriveran*, 7; Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 24; Von Wechmar, *Turen*, 6.

attitudes towards the modernisation that ‘threatens’ the countryside, it is also an example of how the country could actually benefit from some level of modernisation. Once again, one can see how the depiction of Romania – in what is perceived as positive and negative – solely relies on the needs and expectations of the tourist.

Romania as a Balkanist blend of contradictions

In this article, the main aspects of the tourist gaze, created and maintained by the contemporary Swedish guidebooks, have been discussed. These aspects reflect the Balkanist discourse that was assumed to be the basis of the gaze. In the interplay between East and West, and the ancient and modern, the authors of guidebooks construct an image of a semi-place that, with its Western influences, is reminiscent of one’s own, yet has enough differences to not be considered fully part of it. As the Balkanist discourse proposes, the depiction of Romania is of a place where the Western and Eastern influences meet – Oriental influences interact with reminders of ancient Western history to make cities like Constanța be sold as interesting destinations. Similarly, German and Hungarian minorities are portrayed in a way to depict a country of great multiculturalism. Yet, it is precisely Roman heritage that becomes the most evident in the guidebooks – both in their portrayal of people and places. By focusing on the heritage shared with the West – just like other Western guidebooks did – a sense of commonality is created. This is furthered by the depiction of the Orient as an enemy – for Romanians, the Ottoman legacy is not voluntary but rather the result of violence and occupation. As Francesco Zavatti has shown in his research, contemporary Romanian historiography also pushed the Roman legacy. According to Zavatti, the regime was able to consolidate its power by creating an image of a nation that was “ancient, unchanged, independent, and united”, wherein Nicolae Ceaușescu was responsible for protecting this.¹⁷⁹ Adelina Stefan has shown that this was also pushed in the state-published guidebooks written in foreign languages, where much emphasis was put on Romanian folk culture as well as the Roman heritage.¹⁸⁰ With this in mind, one can question the role the Romanian state played in the construction of the gaze pushed by the Swedish guidebooks. Given the total monopoly that ONT had over the Romanian tourism industry, it is undeniable that the

¹⁷⁹ Zavatti, “Writing history,” 2016, p.268.

¹⁸⁰ Stefan, “Unpacking,” 377.

authors would have encountered it – also evident by them repeatedly making reference to them.¹⁸¹ Similarities can also be seen in terms of how the guidebooks present culture and tradition. Just like Stefan and Turnock argue that folk culture was an important selling point for ONT, it played an essential role in the depiction of ‘authentic’ Romania in the guidebooks.¹⁸² There is a clear overlap between how Romania wanted to present itself and how it was subsequently presented in the guidebooks. To gain more insight into the connections between ONT and the Swedish travel material, future research could consult archival material both from Sweden and Romania, investigating material from diplomatic missions and World fairs.

The Balkanist discourse is most evident in the way that the authors treat the interplay between the old traditions and the modern. In their gaze, it is precisely Romania’s continued strong connection to traditions and their seemingly ‘simpler’ lives that become important aspects of the ‘genuine’ Romania, which is also what the guidebooks argue must be experienced. By describing country roads mainly used by carriages and animals, and villagers still dressed in traditional clothing who live in houses described as museums, the authors create an image of a countryside where time has stood still. This image is heavily romanticised, symbolising what has been lost in the West. In this way, the ‘own’ is reflected in the description of Romania. The old-fashionedness of Romania must be preserved, shown by their rejection of modernisation as a threat to what the country *should* be. When modernity is portrayed in a positive way, it is done solely from the perspective of the tourist – spa treatments being based on state-of-the-art science clearly strengthens the confidence in them, as do modern hotel facilities at seaside resorts. This creates an ownership of the country, dictating when modernity is positive and negative based on what is favourable to the tourist rather than the citizens.

In the search for what the authors emphasise in their representations of the country, it also becomes clear what they choose to exclude. In line with what Sune Bechmann Pedersen writes about Eastern Europe as a whole, and as Adelina Stefan has shown to be true in the example of a French guidebook covering Romania, the communist rule is not marketed as a reason to visit the country.¹⁸³ Rather, it is a topic that for the most part is avoided – briefly mentioned in the introductions and to then barely be noticeable. As Carina Gråbacke argues, many tourists did not

¹⁸¹ For mentions of ONT in the guidebooks, see Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 37, 49, 92; Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 19, 23; Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 22; Eile, *Rumänien*, 16; Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 8.

¹⁸² Turnock, “Romania”, 207; Stefan, “Vacationing”, 60.

¹⁸³ Bechmann Pedersen, “Paradise”, 244–245; Stefan, “Vacationing”, 140.

care too much about the political situation in their chosen destination, as the most popular charter trips by the travel agency Reso were those going to places such as Francoist Spain.¹⁸⁴ Furthermore, as Bechmann Pedersen points out, this may be because guidebooks preferred to avoid controversial topics that could make the publication of the book more difficult, or merely because it could negatively affect the image of the country.¹⁸⁵ Despite its distancing from the Soviet Union, Romania was after all a country belonging to the Eastern bloc during a relatively uncertain period of European history. By sparingly using terms related to this contemporary division of Europe, the authors may have given the impression that it was of little importance for the tourist. The reader is most likely to realise that it is a communist country they are reading about when on the topic of what they should bring from home, as the authors emphasise the lack of certain consumer goods. The only depiction of the results of the communist rule were those that could affect the tourist.

Overall, this study has given insight in the construction and maintenance of the tourist gaze of Romania, evidently permeated by Balkanist discourse. As often is the case with travel literature, the authors take ownership of the country in question and depict it with the intended audience in mind. It is therefore not exceptional that these different guidebooks all offer quite a homogenous depiction and description of Romania, being as they are all having the same nordic-germanic audience in mind. The findings on how Romania is depicted in these guidebooks also goes in line with previous research on other Western European gazes. While guidebooks play a vital role in the construction of a gaze of a country, they are not lone actors in this. For a more encompassing image of the construction of the tourist gaze of Romania, future research should both examine a wider range of travel material – such as travelogues, travel posters, advertisements and charter programmes – as well World fairs and other official state representations abroad.

¹⁸⁴ Gråbacke, “När folket,” 211.

¹⁸⁵ Sune Bechmann Pedersen and Christian Noack, “Crossing the Iron Curtain: an introduction,” in *Tourism and Travel during the Cold War: negotiating tourist experiences across the Iron Curtain*, ed. Sune Bechman Pedersen and Christian Noack (London: Routledge, 2020), 3.

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The Second World War and the Winter War in the newspapers *Politika*, *Pravda* and *Vreme*

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Abstract:

This paper examines how three Serbian/Belgrade newspapers—Politika, Vreme, and Pravda—reported on the onset of World War II and the Winter War, focusing on the period up to early 1940. The analysis also considers how these newspapers covered the political crisis leading up to the German invasion of Poland. By investigating articles, editorials, and reports, the study aims to shed light on how these publications, as reflections of a society shaped by an anti-German sentiment following World War I, responded to the possibility and outbreak of another major European conflict with Germany as the central actor.

Special attention is given to the ownership and ideological affiliations of these newspapers, which influenced their portrayals of international events. While Politika maintained a more balanced perspective, Vreme—aligned with the pro-government Radical Party—and Pravda, closer to conservative circles, offered distinct interpretations of the developing crisis. The paper includes a mutual analysis of three main Belgrade newspapers and an attempt to explain certain regularities in their work.

By contextualizing these narratives within the broader sociopolitical climate of interwar Yugoslavia, this paper aims to contribute to the understanding of the role of media in shaping public opinion during times of geopolitical tension. The findings are expected to demonstrate the

interplay between political alignment and journalistic framing, offering insights into the media's role as both an observer and participant in historical processes. This study underscores the importance of historical newspapers as valuable sources for understanding the dynamics of public discourse in times of crisis.

Keywords: *Yugoslavia, Germany, Soviet, Finland, Politika, Pravda, Vreme, newspaper*

Introduction

When we talk about modern history, the press is one of the most important sources. The source captures the spirit of its time, encompassing political propaganda and personal opinions. It also offers valuable insights essential for understanding the past. When discussing the research of diplomacy, culture and sociology of society between the two wars, the press is certainly indispensable. In Serbian historiography, the most comprehensive work on the interwar press was written by Vuk Dragović. This work from 1956 still provides much valuable information about the structure of ownership and functioning of almost all interwar newspapers.¹⁸⁶ A more detailed analysis and view of the press was given by Dušan Popov.¹⁸⁷ Branko Cisarž, Milan Vesović, Živan Ćirić, Irena Mandić and others will also contribute to this topic.¹⁸⁸ Although the press is the most used historical source, there are few works or monographs that analyze a certain event according to how the press reported it, especially the interwar press. This paper attempts to show the value of the press as a historical source and on how many levels it can be analyzed.

This paper deals with the depiction of the Winter War and the beginning of the Second World War in the main Belgrade and important Serbian and Yugoslav newspapers: *Politika*,

¹⁸⁶ See: Вук Драговић, *Српска штампа између два рата I – основа за библиографију српске периодике 1915-1945*, (Београд), 1956

¹⁸⁷ See: Dušan Popov, *Srpska štampa u Vojvodini između dva rata: (1918-1941)*, (Novi Sad: Matica Srpska), 1983; Душан Попов, *Српска штампа у Румунији*, (Нови Сад: Матица Српска), 1994; Душан Попов, *Кикиндска српска штампа између два рата (1918-1941)*, *Банатска периодика XIX и XX века*, 1995, 69-76.

¹⁸⁸ See: Бранко А. Цисарж, *Црквена штампа између два светска рата*, (Београд), 1970; Милан Весовић, *Студентска штампа између два светска рата*, (Београд: Универзитет у Београду), 1988; Милан Весовић, *Илегална комунистичка штампа у Србији између два светска рата*, (Светозарево: Марксистички центар "Светозар Марковић"), 1982; Живан Л. Ћирић, *Ужичка омладинска штампа између два светска рата: прилог проучавању културне баштине Титовог Ужица*, (Титово Ужице: Вести), 1987; Ирена Мандић, *Штампа у Горњем Милановцу између два рата*, (Горњи Милановац: Музеј рудничко-таковског краја), 2009

Pravda and *Vreme*. *Politika* was founded by Slobodan F. Ribnikar in 1904 in Belgrade. After the First World War, *Politika* was the most eminent and respected daily newspaper in the Kingdom of Yugoslavia.¹⁸⁹ With the Ribnikar family at the helm, *Politika* continued to gain reputation, associates and readers. The newspaper is not affiliated with any party and does not take any side for the purpose of providing good and timely information.¹⁹⁰ As a newspaper with the largest circulation but also with a significant state share, *Politika* has sometimes been criticized as a "regime-controlled media" due to its frequent promotion of government views and avoidance of publishing content that could challenge the authorities. *Pravda* was founded by a member of the Serbian Progressive Party, Pavle Marinković, but since 1913 it has been owned by the Sokić family.¹⁹¹ This opposition and progressive paper was pro-Western oriented and very often attacked by the regime. *Pravda* faced financial problems for most of its existence (1904-1941). In the selection of these three, *Vreme* is the youngest newspaper, opened in 1921. From the beginning, *Vreme* was considered a regime paper especially after Milan Stojadinović (1888-1961) and his family took over the complete ownership of this paper. Minister of Finance (1924-1926), Minister of Foreign Affairs and Prime Minister of the Kingdom of Yugoslavia (1935-1939), Stojadinović was known as an extremely corrupt person, a court-friendly conservative and a sympathizer of the Axis Powers.¹⁹² Through the *Vreme* newspaper, he confirmed most of those accusations, considering the bias in reporting and the ownership structure of the paper, which consisted entirely of members of Stojadinović's family.

In the analysis of the reporting of these three papers on the Winter War and the beginning of the Second World War, the context of the political and diplomatic situation in the Kingdom of Yugoslavia is also necessary. Due to growing ethnic conflicts that culminated in the murder of three members of the Croatian Peasant Party in parliament in 1928, King Aleksandar I Karađorđević introduced a dictatorship the following year and abolished parliamentarism. Because of this move, and during unresolved ethnic issues, King Alexander was assassinated in Marseilles in 1934. As Prince Petar II Karađorđević was still a minor, the administration of the state was taken over by Aleksandar's brother, Prince Pavle. He made a sharp turn in foreign

¹⁸⁹ Миодраг Симић, „Породица Рибникар и њена улога у штампи“, *Годишњак града Београда*, XXIII (1976): 240

¹⁹⁰ Симић, *Породица Рибникар*, р. 240

¹⁹¹ Драговић, *Српска штампа*, р. 128

¹⁹² Вук Драговић, *Српска штампа између два рата I – основа за библиографију српске периодике 1915-1945*, Београд, 1956, р. 53

policy, abandoning France and moving closer to Germany and Italy.¹⁹³ The shift in Yugoslav policy towards Germany, instead of the Western allies, the increasing conflicts between Croats and Serbs, and the grouping of the opposition against the corrupt government of Milan Stojadinović, are a picture and a circumstance of the political life of the country.¹⁹⁴ In February 1939, Prince Pavle dismissed Milan Stojadinović and appointed Dragiša Cvetković as Prime Minister (1939-1941) with a special mandate to resolve the "Croatian question". In this attempt to calm ethnic tensions in the country, an agreement was reached between Prime Minister Dragiša Cvetković and Croatian opposition leader Vlatko Maček. With that agreement, Vlatko Maček became the Deputy Prime Minister (1939-1941) and Banovina Hrvatska was formed.¹⁹⁵ ¹⁹⁶ The aim of the agreement was to calm political and ethnic tensions in the country, but in fact it only further deepened them. Parallel to the political and ethnic crisis, Yugoslavia was also hit by an economic crisis, and during the Winter War and the Second World War, the whole country was in a very difficult position.

Second World War

How the Yugoslav Newspaper *Politika* Reported on the Outbreak of World War II

The Yugoslav newspaper *Politika* provided its readers with a detailed and carefully curated overview of events at the start of World War II, reflecting the political, social, and geopolitical circumstances of the time. An analysis of issues from 2nd, 18th, and 30th September 1939, reveals how the newspaper shaped public perception of the war, balancing between relaying crucial information and subtly shaping a narrative aligned with Yugoslavia's neutral but cautious stance toward the global conflict.

Depicting the German Perspective and the Role of Propaganda

In its September 2 issue, *Politika* published Adolf Hitler's entire speech delivered in the Reichstag on September 1, 1939, granting significant space to the German perspective on the war's outbreak. Hitler's speech, translated into Serbian, which justified Germany's aggression against Poland, was presented without commentary, signaling a neutral tone while

¹⁹³ Branko Petranović, *Istorija Jugoslavije 1918-1988, I*, (Beograd: Nolit), 286-297.

¹⁹⁴ Branko Petranović, *Srbija u Drugom svetskom ratu*, (Beograd: Vojnoizdavački i novinski centar), 1992, p. 26

¹⁹⁵ Banovinas were administrative units in the Kingdom of Yugoslavia headed by a ban. Until 1939, they were named exclusively by geographical terms (Vrbaska – after the Vrbas River, Dravska – after the Drava River...) to avoid national conflicts in the country. With the creation of the Banovina of Croatia, the principle of "interethnic tolerance" and "Yugoslavism" was practically abandoned.

¹⁹⁶ Branko Petranović, *Istorija Jugoslavije 1918-1988, I*, p. 296

simultaneously offering German propaganda a platform to legitimize its actions.¹⁹⁷ Notably, Hitler's appeal to Western states to refrain from interfering in the conflict was highlighted, underscoring Germany's apparent desire to localize the conflict.¹⁹⁸

Focus on Neutrality and Geopolitical Balance

Politika carefully covered other nations' reactions to the war. It reported on Italian leader Benito Mussolini's declaration of non-involvement in the conflict, showing Hitler's telegram thanking Mussolini for his stance.¹⁹⁹ Additionally, *Politika* highlighted the mobilization of neutral states such as Switzerland and Romania, suggesting a spreading sense of caution across Europe. On the sixth page, the newspaper reassured its readers by stating that the Adriatic coast remained "the safest," offering a sense of stability in the Yugoslav region amidst global uncertainty.²⁰⁰

The Soviet Entry into Poland – Neutral Analysis with Propaganda Undertones

The 18th September issue shifted focus to the Soviet Union's role in the war. It published Vyacheslav Molotov's speech and noted that Soviet troops had entered Poland to "protect the Ukrainian and Belarusian populations," as claimed by the Soviets.²⁰¹ Interestingly, the term "Russian troops" was occasionally used, reflecting the traditional perception of the Soviets as successors to the Russian Empire.²⁰²

At the same time, *Politika* reported on Lithuania's fear of a potential Soviet invasion, subtly pointing to the expansionist ambitions of the Soviet Union. This cautious tone reflected an awareness of the complexities of the Soviet-German pact and its potential consequences for Eastern Europe.²⁰³

The End of the Polish State and a New World Order

By September 30, 1939, the narrative surrounding the war's outbreak had shifted. *Politika* openly stated that Poland no longer existed as a state, so *Politika* failed to accomplish its own goal, which was its own claimed neutrality, and featured the headline "The War Is No Longer Meaningful," signaling acceptance of Poland's partition between Germany and the Soviet Union. Significant attention was also given to the reactions to the agreement between the two powers. Particularly the celebrations in Rome, suggesting an effort to portray the triumph of the fascist and Soviet alliance.²⁰⁴

This interpretation of events offered readers a sense of closure to one phase of the war while hinting at a temporary stabilization of the conflict. However, the inclusion of Franklin D.

¹⁹⁷ „Јуче у зору почеле су борбе на целој пољско-немачкој граници“, *Политика*, Београд 1939, 11226, XXXVI, 1.

¹⁹⁸ „Хитлер жели да се сукоб с Пољском локализује“, *Политика*, Београд 1939, 11226, XXXVI, 2.

¹⁹⁹ „Италијански министарски савет, под претседништвом г. Мусолинија, одлучио је да Италија не предузима „никакву иницијативу“ у смислу војних операција“, *Политика*, Београд 1939, 11226, XXXVI, 1.

²⁰⁰ „Најмирнији европски сектор јесте Јадранско море“, *Политика*, Београд 1939, 11226, XXXVI, 6.

²⁰¹ „Оружана интервенција совјетске Русије у источној Пољској“, *Политика*, Београд 1939, 11242, XXXVI, 1.

²⁰² „Руске трупе ушле 60км на пољску територију“, *Политика*, Београд 1939, 11242, XXXVI, 1.

²⁰³ „Неспокојство у Литванији и Естонији“, *Политика*, Београд 1939, 11242, XXXVI, 2.

²⁰⁴ „Споразум у Москви“, *Политика*, Београд 1939, 11254, XXXVI, 1.

Roosevelt's appeal to avoid bombing cities and the continued mobilization of neutral states demonstrated fears of escalation.

How the Yugoslav Newspaper *Vreme* Reported on the Outbreak of World War II

The Yugoslav newspaper *Vreme* adopted a distinct approach to reporting on the early days of World War II, balancing international coverage with an emphasis on Yugoslavia's preparedness and neutrality. Its issues from 2, 18, and 30 September 1939, revealed a combination of romanticized narratives, selective focus on German and Soviet perspectives, and efforts to reassure the domestic audience.

2nd September: Romanticized German Perspective and Domestic Preparedness

The September 2 issue of *Vreme* opened with a striking headline quoting Yugoslav Minister of War Milan Nedić, declaring that Yugoslavia was ready to defend itself against any aggressor. This positioning emphasized national strength and stability, which contrasted with the turmoil in Europe.²⁰⁵

Like *Politika*, *Vreme* published Hitler's speech in full, but with a more dramatic framing, including the headline "I Will Wear My Uniform Until I Die." This romanticized portrayal aligned with *Vreme's* tendency to present Germany's actions in a sympathetic light.²⁰⁶ The newspaper stressed that Germany only bombed military targets and dismissed Polish claims of civilian bombings as rumors originating from "Polish circles in "Paris"." The extensive attention given to German denials of bombing civilian areas demonstrated a clear inclination to present Germany in a favorable light.²⁰⁷

The headline "Great Britain Disrupted Mr. Hitler's Good Intentions" further emphasized this bias, portraying Britain as the primary obstacle to peace. While *Vreme* reported on general developments such as Danzig's annexation by Germany and the mobilization of Britain and France, these details were secondary to narratives emphasizing German restraint and Yugoslav readiness.²⁰⁸

18th September: Shifting Focus and Commercial Influences

By the 18th September issue, *Vreme* had begun to shift its focus. Advertisements dominated the second page, illustrating the newspaper's commercial priorities even during a time of crisis.

Notable international developments, such as the Soviet Union's growing pressure on Romania, were reported but not explored in depth. This reflects a tendency to prioritize Yugoslav-related matters and avoid overly detailed discussions of Soviet actions, which might

²⁰⁵ „Наша војна сила мора да буде спремна да стане на браник Југославије“, *Време*, Београд 1939, 6325, XIX, 1.

²⁰⁶ „Униформу ћу скинути тек после победе или нећу доживети крај“, *Време*, Београд 1939, 6325, XIX, 3.

²⁰⁷ „Бомбардовање војних циљева у преко 20 пољских градова“, *Време*, Београд 1939, 6325, XIX, 4.

²⁰⁸ „Енглеска и Францу а зах вају да се немачке трупе одмах повуку из Пољске“, *Време*, Београд X, 6.

have been politically sensitive. The relative brevity of this coverage suggests an effort to maintain neutrality while still informing readers of broader geopolitical threats.²⁰⁹

30th September: Calls for Peace and Strategic Ambiguity

The 30th September issue of *Vreme* featured a bold headline: “Germany and Russia Propose Peace.” This headline framed the Soviet-German alliance as a stabilizing force, subtly endorsing their actions as an opportunity for resolution. The article delved into the details of the four agreements signed between Germany and the Soviet Union, alongside speculation and analysis about territorial divisions and spheres of influence.²¹⁰ The prominence given to these treaties reflects *Vreme*’s focus on presenting these powers as dominant forces shaping the new European order.

A recurring theme in this issue was Yugoslavia’s preparedness. Reports emphasized the country’s readiness to defend itself, reflecting an ongoing effort to reassure the domestic audience. Similarly, the claim that Americans did not intend to join the war ignored the debates occurring within the United States at the time.²¹¹ This omission suggests a selective presentation of facts to align with Yugoslavia’s stance of neutrality and distance from the conflict.

How the Yugoslav Newspaper *Pravda* Reported on the Outbreak of World War II

The evening newspaper *Pravda* distinguished itself from other Yugoslav publications by maintaining a neutral but subtly critical tone toward both Germany and the Soviet Union. Its reporting on the events of early World War II, particularly in issues from September 2, 18, and 30, 1939, reflects a focus on British perspectives and a commitment to providing detailed contextual analysis.

Unlike other newspapers, *Pravda* rarely published full speeches, opting instead for summaries and commentary. It reprinted the full text of the document annexing

“Danzig to Germany but avoided dramatizing Hitler’s rhetoric”

As an evening paper, *Pravda* addressed the outbreak of war earlier than its counterparts, with a September 1 headline: “Great Britain at War with Germany.” This early coverage highlighted the paper’s reliance on British sources and its tendency to frame events through a British lens.²¹²

The 2nd September issue featured the headline “Planes Over Warsaw,” offering a clear reference to the devastation in Poland.²¹³ While other Yugoslav newspapers leaned toward

²⁰⁹ „Преко Пољске Галиције совјетска војска избила на румунску границу“, *Време*, Београд 1939, 6341, XIX, 3.

²¹⁰ „После поделе Пољске...“, *Време*, Београд 1939, 6353, XIX, 1.

²¹¹ „Сједињене Америчке Државе неће ступати у рат“, *Време*, Београд 1939, 6353, XIX, 1.

²¹² „Велика Британија у ратном стању са Немачком“, *Правда*, Београд 1939, 12510, XXXV, 1.

²¹³ „Јутрос је Варшава двапут бомбардована“, *Правда*, Београд 1939, 12510, XXXV, 1.

presenting German denials or justifications for their actions, *Pravda* adopted a more skeptical stance, often expressing criticism of both Germany and the Soviet Union. The newspaper's antitotalitarian position was evident in its broader reporting, which implicitly sympathized with Western democracies.

18th September: Soviet Threats and International Reactions

By 18th September, *Pravda* focused on the Soviet Union's actions in Eastern Europe. It highlighted the threat posed to Ukraine and Belarus, warning that Soviet ambitions could lead to their occupation. This coverage reflects a deeper skepticism of Soviet motives compared to other Yugoslav publications, which often adopted more neutral tones when reporting on the USSR.²¹⁴

The issue prominently featured the headline "What Does Reuters Say," emphasizing the newspaper's reliance on British and Western sources. This reliance reinforced *Pravda*'s framing of events through a pro-British perspective, contrasting sharply with the more German-leaning narratives in *Politika* or *Vreme*.²¹⁵

September 30: Peace Proposals and Occupation Narratives

The September 30 issue carried the headline "The War in Poland Is Over," signaling the end of Poland as an independent state. While other Yugoslav newspapers described these developments in neutral or pragmatic terms, *Pravda* frequently used the term "occupation", particularly in reference to German and Soviet actions. This word choice underscored its critical stance toward the partition of Poland.²¹⁶

The headline "Germans and Russians Propose a Peace Conference" hinted at skepticism toward the intentions behind the Soviet-German alliance, contrasting these proposals with ongoing debates in the United States about maintaining neutrality. By mentioning American discussions, *Pravda* presented a more nuanced and global view of the war, acknowledging the broader implications of the conflict beyond Europe.²¹⁷

Winter War

The beginning of the war

In the front pages from November 29, 1939, the day before the start of the war, *Politika*, *Pravda* and *Vreme* referred to the note from the Soviet government to Finland. The note criticizes the refusal of the Finnish government to take responsibility for the border conflicts. The note states

²¹⁴ „Украјина и Белорусија које Совјетска Русија хоће да окупира“, *Правда*, Београд 1939, 12524, XXXV, 1

²¹⁵ „Информације агенције Ројтерс о држању Русије према пољско-немачком рату“, *Правда*, Београд 1939, 12524, XXXV, 2.

²¹⁶ „Текст споразума Немачке и Русије“, *Правда*, Београд 1939, 12536, XXXV, 1

²¹⁷ „Борба у Сједињеним Државама око неутралности“, *Правда*, Београд 1939, 12536, XXXV, 3.

that the Soviet government is terminating the non-aggression pact with Finland. The most objective and least sensationalist approach in reporting is seen in *Politika*. The front page of the newspaper simply states:

“Tensions between Soviet Russia and Finland”

“The Soviet Government has terminated the non-aggression pact with Finland”

The commander of the Leningrad Military District has ordered the army to ‘*respond to fire in the event of repeated Finnish provocations*’²¹⁸

At the bottom of the page is a caricature of Justice walking over corpses with her eyes covered, and the text below the image reads: *They took away my sword and scales, they are killing the innocents I defended with them with the sword, and on the scales they are measuring the requisitioned food.* This caricature of Pravda speaks of the fact that *Politika* does not take sides in the conflict but rather emphasizes the lack of justice that is omnipresent.

A somewhat different, sensationalist approach can be observed among *Pravda* journalists. This newspaper was founded by a progressive, Pavle Marinković, and at the time, it was managed by the Sokić family.²¹⁹ The director of *Pravda* himself, Manojlo Sokić, was a

²¹⁸ „Совјетска Влада је раскинула пакт о ненападању са Финском“, *Политика*, Београд 1939, 11314, XXXVI

²¹⁹ Драговић, *Српска штампа*, p. 128

deputy of Democratic party in the Čačak district until 1929.²²⁰ With an oppositional tone, *Pravda* first looks at comments from France, and then from Moscow and Helsinki:

"In Paris, it is not believed that there will be a war between Soviet Russia and Finland. **The Moscow press calls the Finnish government a 'warmonger'**. In Helsinki, it is declared that Germany will remain neutral in the event of a conflict with Soviet Russia."²²¹

Notably less informative than the headline in *Politika*, this one is more focused on the analysis of the Finnish government's response. The lack of news from Moscow can be explained by the lack of reporters and the reliance on the Western press.

Vreme deals much more with local than with world issues, so on the front page from November 29 the news about Soviet-Finnish relations take up less than a quarter of the page. In the next day's issue, *Vreme* deals with Soviet-Finnish relations only on page four, and that on less than half a page. On November 29, the title in *Vreme* is:

"Finland rejects protest from Soviet Russia

A large concentration of planes and tanks is **taking place in Leningrad**."²²²

While the title from November 30, on fourth page is:

"Russia cancels Soviet-Finnish pact"²²³

The first thing we notice is a much more sensational approach to entice the reader to buy the newspaper. Although they are much more modest than the headlines of the modern tabloid press, *Vreme's* headlines clearly demand attention, and the most provocative things are marked. In this regard, it should be emphasized that on the fourth page, in addition to the main headline, there is a smaller more modest headline "Finnish Fleet"²²⁴, which analyzes the status and modernization of the fleet in Finland from 1924 to 1938.

In the news of November 30, the day before the start of the war, the newspapers reported on the severance of Soviet-Finnish diplomatic relations and the deployment of troops on the

²²⁰ Милош Тимотијевић, Заборављене српске грађанске породице, accessed January 15, 2025, (<https://www.poreklo.rs/2021/11/11/zaboravljene-srpske-gradjanske-porodice-braca-sokici-iz-ivanjice/>)

²²¹ „Московска штампа назива финску владу 'изазивачем рата“, *Правда*, Београд 1939, 12597, XXXV

²²² „Финска одбија протест Совјетске Русије“, *Време*, Београд 1939, 6413, XIX

²²³ „Русија отказује Совјетско-фински пакт“, *Време*, Београд, 1939, 6413, XIX, 4

²²⁴ „Финска флота“, *Време*, Београд 1939, 6413, XIX, 4

border. Of all three newspapers, only *Politika* reported the speech of Soviet Foreign Minister Vyacheslav Molotov.²²⁵ *Pravda* reported the same speech only the next day²²⁶, while *Vreme* didn't report it at all.²²⁷ *Politika* writes the most about the Soviet-Finnish issue and is not only the best informed but also reports the most news from Moscow itself.²²⁸ The director of *Politika at the time*, Vladislav S. Ribnikar, was a sympathizer and agitator of the Communist Party of Yugoslavia, and from June 1941 he would be a member.²²⁹

It can be concluded, based on the director's views, that *Politika* reported news from Moscow as a form of communist agitation. However, there are several reasons why this possibility should be rejected. First, most of the contributors, authors and editors in the company were not members or sympathizers of the Communist Party of Yugoslavia.²³⁰ Second, the Ribnikar family is the founder of the paper and it is true that a person from that family is the director of the paper, but it should still be borne in mind that the company is also owned by the other families²³¹, and that the tendencies of the director or even the entire family cannot be reflected in the editorial policy of the paper in this way. Finally, it should be emphasized that *Politika*, as the largest and most widely circulated paper in the country, had large funds and many reporters and external collaborators. So, it makes sense that this newspaper is the most informative and well-informed of the three mentioned.

In this regard, the position of *Pravda* and *Vreme* is worth mentioning. In the articles of November 30, *Pravda* again pays special attention to the French view of Soviet-Finnish relations and once again deals more with the Finnish than the Soviet vision of the conflict.²³² In part, this is because of the lack of reporters in the Soviet Union. Although well informed about the position of Paris, *Pravda* says surprisingly little about the position of Rome and Berlin on these issues. References to French newspapers or the positions of the French government can be seen in the headlines and in the text. Only a few lines have been written about the ways in which the

²²⁵ „Ноћас у 22.30 часова Совјетска Русија прекинула је дипломатске односе са Финском“, *Политика*, Београд 1939, 11315, XXXVI

²²⁶ „Финска има да прихвати совјетске услове или да се брани оружјем, вели се у јутрошњим иностраним коментарима“, *Правда*, Београд 1939, 12598, XXXV

²²⁷ „Сукоби на руско-финској граници“, *Време*, Београд 1939, 6414, XIX

²²⁸ *Политика*, „Ноћас у 22.30“, 11315, XXXVI

²²⁹ Симић, *Породица Рибникар*, р. 243

²³⁰ Драговић, *Српска штампа*, р. 125

²³¹ Драговић, *Српска штампа*, р. 125

²³² *Правда*, „Финска има да прихвати“, 12598, XXXV

German press reports. Even when *Pravda* report about Berlin's position towards the Soviet-Finnish conflict, French sources are cited. Rome's position is not even mentioned in the November 30 issue. On the other hand, *Vreme* pays most attention to the view of the conflict from Berlin and Rome, that is, the question of whether the Axis Powers will join the war on the side of Finland or the Soviet Union or will they maintain neutrality.²³³ What is interesting in this issue, dated November 30, is the fact that *Vreme* even reports Madrid's position on the Soviet-Finnish conflict.²³⁴ In March 1939, Francisco Franco conquered Madrid, the former capital and symbol of resistance of the Spanish Republic.²³⁵ Considering Franco's policy of alliance with Germany and Italy, it seems logical that only *Vreme*, a conservative newspaper favoring the Axis Powers, reports Madrid's position.

Finally, it is worth looking at the photographs in the press. In its issue dated November 30, *Politika* has three photographs related to the news about the Soviet-Finnish conflict²³⁶, *Vreme* has two photographs on the same day²³⁷, and *Pravda* has none²³⁸. On the front page of *Politika*, photographs of the Soviet Minister of Foreign Affairs, Vyacheslav Molotov, and the Prime Minister of Finland, Kyesto Kalia, are presented. The third photograph is the capital of Finland, Helsinki. In *Vreme* like *Politika*, there is a photograph of Kyesto Kali, but instead of Vyacheslav Molotov there is a photograph of Joseph Stalin. It has already been said that *Politika* has many reporters and collaborators. Based on that number of these associates and better information, the financial advantage of *Politika* can be seen, especially in relation to *Pravda*. This is additionally proven by analyzing the number of photos and what is shown on them.

In the issues from December 1, 1939, the front page is filled with news about the twenty-first anniversary of the proclamation of the Kingdom of Serbs, Croats and Slovenes. Thus, photographs of the still minor King Peter II Karađorđević were prominently featured on the front pages of all newspapers. As for the part of the front page about the Soviet-Finnish conflict, the situation is as follows: *Politika* devoted approximately a third of its front page to

²³³ *Vreme*, „Сукоби на руско-финској граници“, 6414, XIX

²³⁴ *Vreme*, „Сукоби на руско-финској граници“, 6414, XIX

²³⁵ Pjer Brue i Emil Temim, *Revolucija i građanski rat u Španiji 1936-1939*, (Beograd: IK Filip Višnjić), 2016, p. 360

²³⁶ *Politika*, „Ноћас у 22.30“, 11315, XXXVI

²³⁷ *Vreme*, „Сукоби на руско-финској граници“, 6414, XIX

²³⁸ *Pravda*, „Финска има да прихвати“, 12598, XXXV

this issue,²³⁹ *Pravda* slightly less than half,²⁴⁰ and *Vreme* only a quarter of its front page.²⁴¹ *Vreme* and *Politika* nevertheless have a separate page dedicated solely to the Soviet-Finnish conflict, while *Pravda* has no further reports. A special news item in the first two newspapers is the fact that the USA is taking an active part in the negotiations and resolution of the crisis in northern Europe.²⁴² As emphasized earlier in the article, *Pravda* only reported Vyacheslav Molotov's speech on December 1st, which *Politika* reported on November 30th. The reason for this is the lack of reporters, and therefore the information available to *Pravda*. It is also logical that *Vreme* does not report the speech at all. In *Pravda* and *Politika*, the headlines emphasize that Soviet troops have crossed the border and that the Soviet ground army is operating.²⁴³ On the other hand, in *Vreme*, the headline refers to the Soviet bombing of Finland, and the actions of the ground army are mentioned only later in the text, probably to win over readers in the same sensationalistic manner that we have already encountered. Finally, the side headline in *Vreme*, highlighted below the main one on the third page of the newspaper, is interesting: “*Blitzkrieg*” *against Finland*.²⁴⁴ It seems that a parallel is being drawn between the German action in Poland and the Soviet action in Finland, for what reason, or rather with what tendencies, it is difficult to answer. It is possible that the superiority of German military tactics and the Axis Powers over other states should be emphasized again, and on the other hand, it may also be a matter of emphasizing the German-Soviet pact that was still in force at that time.

The First Phase of the Winter War

The Winter War was fought in two phases.²⁴⁵ The first lasted from November 1939 to the beginning of January 1940 and involved a moderate advance of the Soviet army through Finnish territory. However, the war progressed slowly and near the end of this phase, the Soviet troops

²³⁹ „Совјетске трупе на више места прешле су финску границу“, *Политика*, Београд 1939, 11316, XXXVI

²⁴⁰ „Совјетске трупе прешле су финску границу“, *Правда*, Београд 1939, 12599, XXXV

²⁴¹ „Руски авиони бомбардују Хелсинки и пристаништа у Финском заливу“, *Време*, Београд 1939, 6415, XIX

²⁴² *Политика*, „Совјетске трупе на више места“, 11316, XXXVI; See also: *Време*, „Руски авиони бомбардују“, 6415, XIX

²⁴³ *Политика*, „Совјетске трупе на више места“, 11316, XXXVI; See also: *Правда*, „Совјетске трупе прешле су“, 12599, XXXV

²⁴⁴ *Време*, „Руски авиони бомбардују“, 6415, XIX

²⁴⁵ Gregory J. Bozek, *The Soviet Finnish War 1939-1940 Getting the Doctrine Right*, School of advanced military studies, 1993, p. 30

significantly slowed down and even stopped their advance. Thus, the possibility of Finland being defeated quickly has failed.²⁴⁶ The second part of the war represents static military operations primarily on the Mannerheim Line, where the Soviet victory was ensured by numerical and material superiority.²⁴⁷ We analyzed how many times news about the Soviet-Finnish conflict appeared on the main pages of the press. It should be emphasized that the front page of *Vreme* looks much different from *Politika* and *Pravda*, it always includes a multitude of different news and never devotes the entire front page to just one news item, as the other two newspapers do. In this regard, our analysis led to the conclusion that *Pravda*, in the period from December 5 to January 1, most often wrote about the war in Finland on its front pages – as many as twenty-three times, of which nineteen times as the main news item. *Vreme* mentioned the war in Finland many times in the same period – as many as twenty-five times. Eighteen of these times were the main news items and they were placed on a quarter to half of the front page. Finally, comes *Politika*, which had the war in Finland on its front page “only” ten times in the same period. Out of those ten times, six times the events in Finland are the main news. *Vreme* reports the most about the fighting itself – twelve out of twenty-five times; then comes *Pravda* with eight out of twenty-three times and finally *Politika* with three out of ten times. The main news in all the papers, and roughly the same period, is the attitude of the League of Nations towards the Soviet-Finnish conflict and the expulsion of the Soviet Union from the organization. Now it would be useful to apply the regularities observed in the previous part of this paper. *Politika*, as the most objective about the conflicts, provides essential information in very informative texts. *Vreme* pays a lot of attention to the German position towards the events in Finland, with the proviso that they are inclined to criticize the Western Allies for their attitude towards this conflict. *Pravda* again gives primacy to the point of view of the Western Allies. The question remains unanswered as to why this paper pays so much attention to the Soviet-Finnish conflict and puts it on the front page so often, while it does not do so for World War II or events in the Kingdom of Yugoslavia.

²⁴⁶ Carl A. Quist, *The Winter War (1939-1940): An Analysis of Soviet Adaptation*, (MMS thesis, Marine Corps University), 2019, p. 8

²⁴⁷ Bozek, *The Soviet Finnish War*, p. 33

	<i>Politika</i>	<i>Pravda</i>	<i>Vreme</i>
Dates when news about the Finnish-Soviet conflict made the front page.	5, 21, 28, 31. December ²⁴⁸ 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16. December ²⁴⁹	5, 6. December ²⁵⁰ 8, 9, 16, 18, 28, 30. December ²⁵¹ 7, 11, 13, 14, 15, 17. December ²⁵² 10, 12, 21, 22, 23, 25, 29, 31. December ²⁵³ 24. December ²⁵⁴	5, 6, 7, 17, 18, 19, 22, 23, 25, 26, 28, 31. December ²⁵⁵ 8, 9, 20, 27, 30. December ²⁵⁶ 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16. December ²⁵⁷ 24. December ²⁵⁸
Total number of mentions of the Soviet-Finnish conflict on the front pages	10	23	25
Top news (out of total mentions)	6	19	18 ²⁵⁹
Side news (of total mentions)	4	4	4
News in two sentences (out of total mentions)	/	/	3

Table 1 - Mentions of the Soviet-Finnish conflict on the front pages of *Politika*, *Pravda* and *Vreme* in the period from December 5 to January 1

²⁴⁸ Reporting on battles and war activities.

²⁴⁹ Reporting on events related to the League of Nations.

²⁵⁰ Reporting on failed peace negotiations.

²⁵¹ Reporting on the potential involvement of other states and the spread of the war conflict.

²⁵² Reporting on events related to the League of Nations

²⁵³ Reporting on battles and war activities.

²⁵⁴ Reporting on the cessation of the Soviet offensive.

²⁵⁵ Reporting on battles and war activities.

²⁵⁶ Reporting on the potential involvement of other states and the spread of the war conflict.

²⁵⁷ Reporting on events related to the League of Nations.

²⁵⁸ Reporting on the cessation of the Soviet offensive.

²⁵⁹ We emphasize again that the front page of *Vreme* is significantly different from the front page of *Politika* i *Pravda*, and that "main news" in this specific case means a quarter to half of the front page.

The Second Phase of the Winter War

The second phase of the war, namely the intense long fighting, especially around the Mannerheim Line, was less well covered by the press in Yugoslavia. In early February, 1940, ministers from four members of the Balkan Alliance²⁶⁰, a pact that was supposed to be a guarantor of peace in the Balkans and was formed in 1934, met in Niš.²⁶¹ News of the agreements between Turkey, Romania, Greece and Yugoslavia dominated the press in early February, and later more attention would be paid to World War II, and on 20, 21 and 22 February the press would write extensively about the death of Ljubomir Davidović, leader of the Democratic Party and one of the most prominent Serbian political leaders.²⁶² The second phase of the war was thus covered as follows – *Pravda*, in the period from February 5 to March 3, spoke on its front pages sixteen times about the Soviet-Finnish conflict, of which 11 times it was the main news. *Vreme*, in the same period, spoke on the Soviet-Finnish conflict nineteen times, of which ten times it was the main news. Finally, there is *Politika* again, which had events from the war on its front pages only nine times, of which seven times as the main news. *Pravda* talks the most about the fighting itself – twelve out of sixteen times; then comes *Vreme* with eight out of nineteen times and finally *Politika* with four out of nine times. The main news in all the papers, and in a roughly similar period, is the strong pressure on the Mannerheim Line and the withdrawal of Finnish forces.

Peace and the End of the Winter War

The peace between the Soviet Union and Finland was signed on March 12, 1940, and the Soviet war goals were practically fulfilled. *Politika* in its issue of March 13 reported the news of peace with its usual restraint and dry reporting.²⁶³ *Vreme*, on the other hand, gave an incredibly sensationalist headline, unusual even for this newspaper:

²⁶⁰ „Четири министра иностраних послова Балканског споразума једнодушно констатују вољу својих народа да остану уједињени на чувању мира и права своје независности“, *Politika*, Београд 1940, 11379, XXXVII

²⁶¹ Petranović, *Istorija Jugoslavije*, p. 363

²⁶² Petranović, *Istorija Jugoslavije*, p. 209

²⁶³ „Јутрос је потписан у Москви споразум о миру између Совјетске Русије и Финске“, *Politika*, Београд 1940, 11416, XXXVII

“Peace signed between the Soviets and Finland

France was ready to send a corps of 50 thousand men to Finland, and Great Britain almost 100 thousand

but this decision came too late because

the Finnish delegates accepted the Soviet conditions”²⁶⁴

The most interesting is *Pravda*, however. On March 13, they raised the question of whether the peace negotiations would fail and whether the war, with the help of the Western Allies, would continue.²⁶⁵ It was not until the March 14 issue that *Pravda* reported that peace had been signed between Finland and the Soviet Union.²⁶⁶ Here, once again, it can be seen that *Pravda* has no reporters and associates through which it can report on events in a timely manner.

	<i>Politika</i>	<i>Pravda</i>	<i>Vreme</i>
Dates when news about the Finnish-Soviet conflict made the front page.	8, 9, 25, 27. February ²⁶⁷ 13, 14, 15, 17. February ²⁶⁸ 1. March ²⁶⁹	8, 9, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 19, 25, 28 February and 2. March ²⁷⁰ 10, 18, 24, 27 February ²⁷¹	5, 7, 8, 9, 12, 13, 19, 21, 22, 27. February ²⁷² 6, 10, 14, 15, 16, 23, 28. February and 2. March ²⁷³ 1. March ²⁷⁴

²⁶⁴ „Француска је била спремна да упути у Финску корпус од 50 хиљада људи, а Велика Британија од близу 100 хиљада али је ова одлука стигла касно јер су фински делегати прихватили совјетске услове“, *Време*, Београд 1940, 6515, XX

²⁶⁵ „Преговори су наишли на тешкоће и због држања великих сила Прекид преговора?“, *Правда*, Београд 1940, 12702, XXXVI

²⁶⁶ „Уговор о миру Совјетске Русије и Финске“, *Правда*, Београд 1940, 12703, XXXVI

²⁶⁷ Reporting on the potential involvement of other states and the spread of the war.

²⁶⁸ Reporting on battles and war activities.

²⁶⁹ Reporting on the peace talks proposal.

²⁷⁰ Reporting on battles and war activities.

²⁷¹ Reporting on the potential involvement of other states and the spread of the war.

²⁷² Reporting on the potential involvement of other states and the spread of the war.

²⁷³ Reporting on battles and war activities.

²⁷⁴ Reporting on the peace talks proposal.

Total number of mentions of the Soviet-Finnish conflict on the front pages	9	16	19
Top news (out of total mentions)	7	11	10 ²⁷⁵
Side story (of total mentions)	2	5	6
News in two sentences (out of total mentions)	/	/	3

Table 2 - Mentions of the Soviet-Finnish conflict on the front pages of *Politika*, *Pravda* and *Vreme* in the period from February 5 to March 3

Conclusions

The paper examines the reporting styles of three major Yugoslav newspapers—*Politika*, *Vreme*, and *Pravda*—during the outbreak of World War II and the Winter War. It reveals how each publication's ideological leanings and financial resources influenced their portrayal of global events. *Politika* maintained a neutral and fact-focused tone, often providing in-depth coverage informed by its network of reporters. This reflected its broader goal of objective journalism, despite occasional tendencies to align subtly with Yugoslavia's neutral stance. *Pravda*, a pro-Western opposition paper, leaned toward critical reporting of totalitarian regimes, especially Germany and the Soviet Union, but its financial struggles limited its scope and timeliness. *Vreme*, aligned with the pro-government and Axis-sympathetic Stojadinović regime, exhibited a sensationalist approach, romanticizing German actions while reassuring domestic readers of Yugoslavia's stability.

²⁷⁵ We emphasize again that the front page of *Vreme* is significantly different from the front page of *Politika* i *Pravda*, and that "main news" in this specific case means a quarter to half of the front page.

In this paper, we have combined, on the one hand, our knowledge of the history of these three newspapers, on their founders, directors, ownership structures and political tendencies, and on the other hand, the analysis of texts, headlines, photos and the layout of news on the front pages. The practical importance of the work, apart from the confirmation of many theses, is the contribution to the study of the press and how it can be used for a deeper analysis of the social context and writing. The contribution is particularly significant in the field of questions, which all aspects of the press can be used in the work of historians. The main text is important, but the choice of texts, the layout on the front page, the choice of titles and photos, the number of mentions of some news, represent a contribution in terms of practical work with the press.

The diversity in the structure of the work is also significant. The segment on the Second World War was analyzed according to the newspapers, first *Politika* view of the events, then *Vreme* and finally *Pravda*. The segment on the Winter War was therefore analyzed according to dates, a parallel analysis of the views of all three papers. And this represents a kind of contribution to the topic of looking at history thematically and chronologically, and in the specific case to the analysis of the press in two different ways and two different approaches.

Collectively, the newspapers reflected Yugoslavia's complex geopolitical position and the tensions of interwar Europe. This analysis underscores the critical role of the media as both observers and participants in shaping public opinion during times of crisis.

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„Преко Пољске Галиције совјетска војска избила на румунску границу“, *Време*, 18.9.1939, 6341, XIX

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Addressing the Elephant in the Room: Processions in Mughal India

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Abstract

As the advent of gunpowder and marksmanship gradually phased out the elephant from the battlefields, the Indian elephant firmly remained as an integral part of royal processions throughout the subcontinent, all the way up to the early twentieth century. On the heels of these military advancements, the Mughals from Central Asia arrived in north India in 1526. However, despite their equestrian Timurid background, the Mughals found themselves compelled to adapt to the deeply entrenched elephant-centered practices of their newly conquered domain. At the outset, this paper seeks to explore how the Mughals employed the elephant in imperial processions as a strategic tool for statecraft and propaganda, one that aimed to project imperial authority while simultaneously affirming the emperor's sovereignty and legitimacy. By attempting to offer a coherent narrative on processions in Mughal India and the role of the elephant within it, this paper will examine the symbolic significance of the elephant in the case of two broad types of royal processions - the imperial march and the Friday prayer procession, both of which placed the emperor, seated atop his caparisoned elephant, as the central focus of the procession. Through this, the study aims to shed more light on the close relationship between the elephant and kingship in India.

Keywords: *Mughal Empire, processions, elephant, kingship, Indian history*

1. Introduction

Despite the centuries of precedent of having the elephant serve as a key symbol of Indian kingship both on and off the battlefield, the sixteenth century saw an unforeseen development challenge this historical equilibrium. With the advancements and proliferation of guns and artillery, riding an elephant into battle became an easy target for skilled marksmen. Nevertheless, this new reality and the subsequent diminishing role of the elephant at the battlefield did not seem to affect its relationship with the ideas of kingship in India in the same manner.²⁷⁶ On the contrary, it was expertly adapted to fit the changing needs of representing Indian kingship, something overtly observable during the heyday of Mughal empire (1526-1707) in India, which continued well past the end of the dynasty in 1857.²⁷⁷

Arriving in India in 1526 with a background of Timurid equestrian culture from Central Asia, the Mughals found themselves in a position where they were compelled to acclimatise and subsequently adapt to the elephant-based kingship traditions that existed in the subcontinent.²⁷⁸ By the late sixteenth century, the elephant had become a state propaganda tool to not only extend and sustain imperial Mughal identity but also to represent the emperor's sovereignty and legitimacy. Through studying this changing role of the elephant in the Mughal case, particularly regarding its central role in imperial processions, this paper aims to examine an underexplored area of elephant-kingship ties in Mughal India. For this, the paper will succinctly examine the meanings attached to the elephant in broadly two types of Mughal processions where the elephant represented the Mughal Emperor - the imperial march and the Friday processions. Focusing on the elephant in these processions further allows for addressing its remarkable relationship with kingship in India.

²⁷⁶ The elephant would continue to be used for transportation and logistics. Ali Anooshahr, "The Elephant and Imperial Continuities in North India, 1200–1600 CE," *The Indian Economic & Social History Review* 57, no. 2 (2020): 139–69, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0019464620912614>, 154, 159.

²⁷⁷ Although Babur established his kingdom in 1526 in north India, Humayun, his successor, lost his kingdom briefly to Sher Shah Suri and had to seek Safavid aid. Humayun's recapture of the kingdom in 1555 followed by his untimely death in 1556 set the stage for Akbar to lead this fledgling kingdom into an empire. For detailed history of the Mughal Empire and its beginnings, please check: John F Richards, *The Mughal Empire* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1995); Richard M. Eaton, *India in the Persianate Age: 1000-1765* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2019).

²⁷⁸ Jane Buckingham, "Symbolism and Power*: Elephants and Gendered Authority in the Mughal World," in *Conflict, Negotiation, and Coexistence: Rethinking Human–Elephant Relations in South Asia*, ed. Piers Locke and Jane Buckingham (New Delhi: Oxford University Press, 2016), 92–114.

2. *Elephas Maximus Indicus*

It was not uncommon for an incoming army into north India to have to face the ruling monarch's elephantry in battle, often to their shock. This encounter has been repeatedly recorded over the centuries. Some of the prominent instances of this encounter with the Indian elephant (*Elephas Maximus Indicus*) includes Alexander the Great, the king of Macedon who began his Indian campaign in 327 BCE after his conquest of the Achaemenid Persian Empire; Mahmud of Ghazni's military expeditions into India from today's Afghanistan starting in 1001 CE; Timur, the Turco-Mongol commander from Central Asia, who captured Delhi in 1398; Babur, who came from Ferghana (Uzbekistan) to establish Mughal rule in north India in 1526, among many others.²⁷⁹ Among them, the cases that subsequently led to establishment of a state tended to also lead to a situation where many extant traditions, such as the elephant, became tools that had to be adopted and adapted to fit the changing needs of the ruling elite.

Some of the earliest known mentions of the Indian elephant in the Indian subcontinent can be found among the seals of the Indus Valley Civilization (3300 – 1300 BCE) which contain intricately carved figures of elephants, hinting at the visibility that elephants occupied in that society in order to be chosen to be depicted on their seals.²⁸⁰ Over the centuries, elephants came to be actively employed in warfare in India to the extent that by the time Alexander the Great arrived in India in 327 BCE, it is recorded that elephants instilled awe upon his troops.²⁸¹ Although Alexander won the battle, the reputation of elephants were set such that one of his successors, Seleucus Nicator, founder of the Seleucid dynasty, is reported to have ceded four provinces in 305 BCE in exchange for five hundred elephants from the Indian ruler, Chandragupta Maurya.²⁸² In that era, it is worth noting that the ruler often mounted the biggest elephant under his command and they were exclusively trained for the personal use of the ruler,

²⁷⁹ Thomas R. Trautmann, "Alexander and the Elephants," *Comparative Studies in Society and History*, April 10, 2025, 1–24, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0010417525000027>; S Jabir Raza, "Indian Elephant Corps Under The Ghaznavids," *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress* 73 (2012): 212–22, 213–214; Justin Marozzi, *Tamerlane: Sword of Islam, Conqueror of the World* (Cambridge: Da Capo Press, 2006), 238, 242, 265–269.

²⁸⁰ B P Sinha, "Elephants in Ancient Indian Army," *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress* 18 (1955): 51–57, 51.

²⁸¹ Sinha, "Elephants in Ancient Indian Army," 52.

²⁸² Sinha, "Elephants in Ancient Indian Army," 54.

with estimates claiming 9000 elephants in the stables of Chandragupta Maurya.²⁸³ However, the Indian elephant helped chart the course of history not just in the Indian subcontinent, but in places very far away from it as well. An example of this is Timur's use of war elephants in the Battle of Ankara (Türkiye) in 1402 where elephants were significant in ensuring Timur's victory over the Ottomans.²⁸⁴ It is highly possible that these war elephants were part of the war booty that Timur had captured in his sack of Delhi in 1398, which he subsequently took to his capital of Samarkand.²⁸⁵

This revered status of the elephant in warfare however did not last. In addition to its slow pace, the possibility of elephants to rout in the midst of battle, combined with the overall advancement in military technology and marksmanship by the sixteenth century caused elephants to become prime targets in the battlefield, leading them to be channelled more towards other non-military purposes, particularly in ceremonial settings.²⁸⁶ We can notice this overall shift in the following examples. During Timur's conquest of India in 1398, battle preparations were directed mostly at tackling the threat of the elephant to make them rout as early as possible.²⁸⁷ Trenches were dug strategically at estimated points of an elephant charge and camels loaded with inflammable materials were set on fire and unleashed towards the elephants in order to create havoc, aiming to make the elephants go berserk.²⁸⁸ However, by the time of Babur's conquest in 1526, due to significant advancement in gunpowder based weaponry and skilled marksmanship, the elephant was hardly the threat it was during Timur's time and instead became prime targets for the marksmen.²⁸⁹ This was evident in how despite being at a numerical disadvantage, Babur was able to defeat Ibrahim Lodi's significantly larger but technologically inferior army, which was estimated to have had hundreds of war elephants.²⁹⁰ Although cavalry formed the core of Mughal armies during Babur's campaigns, the elephant was soon incorporated into both the army as well as into Mughal culture itself. However, it is the role of

²⁸³ Paul J Kosmin, *The Land of the Elephant Kings: Space, Territory, and Ideology in the Seleucid Empire* (Harvard University Press, 2014), 34.

²⁸⁴ Dimitris J. Kastritsis, "Introduction: The Battle of Ankara and Its Consequences," in *The Sons of Bayezid: Empire Building and Representation in the Ottoman Civil War of 1402-1413* (Leiden: Brill, 2007), 1-40.

²⁸⁵ Bamber Gascoigne, *The Great Moghuls* (London: Constable, 1998), 12-13.

²⁸⁶ Andrew De la Garza, *The Mughal Empire at War: Babur, Akbar and the Indian Military Revolution, 1500-1605* (Abingdon: Routledge, 2016), 6; Sinha, "Elephants in Ancient Indian Army," 51, 56.

²⁸⁷ Gascoigne, *The Great Moghuls*, 12.

²⁸⁸ Marozzi, *Tamerlane*, 268-269.

²⁸⁹ Gascoigne, *The Great Moghuls*, 33.

²⁹⁰ Andrew De la Garza, *The Mughal Empire at War*, 41-42.

the elephant in this cultural spectrum, particularly in its representation of the Mughal Emperor in processions, that will be the focus of this article.

3. The Elephant under Mughal Kingship

Babur's Indian campaign was not an unusual occurrence for its time, especially considering that he was a direct descendent of Timur. But unlike Timur, who did not stay in India for long, the turbulent political atmosphere of Central Asia during Babur's time significantly contributed towards his decision to establish a kingdom in north India in 1526.²⁹¹ While this commenced Mughal dominion in north India, the plethora of religions, ethnicities, languages and cultures that this unique situation brought together necessitated the overall need for a stable rule brought about through adopting a syncretic approach towards ruling, one that was inherently eclectic in nature, paving the way for a composite Mughal culture and society.²⁹² This outlook contributed immensely towards the meteoric rise that the Mughals would see in the following decades, which also allowed room for bringing in the elephant as a tool to serve the needs of this newly emergent state.

Before the Mughals, the rulers of the Delhi Sultanate (1206-1526) had faced a similar predicament, which they had resolved by absorbing the existing Indian notion associated with the elephant to represent authority.²⁹³ In fact, scholars posit that the Delhi Sultanate's endurance depended somewhat on their control over the supply of elephants and horses while depriving it to their rivals.²⁹⁴ This was partly because the image of a monarch riding an elephant was viewed not only as the symbol of sovereignty but also with the understanding where the elephant itself came to represent the sovereign in large parts of India.²⁹⁵ Instead of merely repeating the same approach, the Mughals eclectically utilised this existing state of affairs to their advantage by

²⁹¹ Stephen F Dale, *The Garden of the Eight Paradises: Babur and the Culture of Empire in Central Asia, Afghanistan and India (1483-1530)* (Leiden: Brill, 2004), 292.

²⁹² Catherine B Asher and Cynthia Talbot, *India before Europe* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2006), 115.

²⁹³ Ali Anooshahr, "The Elephant and Imperial Continuities in North India, 1200–1600CE," *The Indian Economic & Social History Review* 57, no. 2 (2020): 139–69, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0019464620912614>, 147; Simon Digby, *War-Horse and Elephant in the Delhi Sultanate: A Study of Military Supplies* (Oxford: Orient Monographs, 1971), 20.

²⁹⁴ Ali Anooshahr, "The Elephant and the Sovereign: India circa 1000 CE," *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society* 28, no. 4 (October 2018): 615–44, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1356186318000093>, 618-619.

²⁹⁵ Anooshahr, "The Elephant and Imperial Continuities," 147.

adding new symbolic meanings to the image of the imperial elephant, overtly visible in their processions. However, before delving into that, it is essential to explore the relationship between the elephant and the Mughal Emperor in more detail, particularly as it evolved during the reign of Babur's grandson, Akbar.

Akbar, the third emperor of the Mughal dynasty who ruled from 1556-1605, succeeded his father Humayun at the young age of fourteen.²⁹⁶ During his nearly fifty-year reign, Akbar greatly expanded and consolidated the empire which his father had retaken only in 1555 from the Sur dynasty.²⁹⁷ In tandem with this overall expansion of territory, by the 1580s, Akbar's domains ensured him as the sole ruler with the largest number of elephants and the one with the most advanced and largest arsenal of gunpowder based weaponry in the subcontinent.²⁹⁸ This meant that he could break away from the Sultanate system of rule where the empire was ruled through tributary kings and instead rule directly as the emperor.²⁹⁹

The consolidation of Mughal realms under Akbar also made the elephant the most visible symbol of imperial sovereignty in the subcontinent once again. The magnitude of this close ruler-elephant association can be seen from the state control over elephantry. For instance, historians estimate that the total captive population of elephants in the empire was 17,000 in 1595, where the Mughal imperial stables alone are estimated to have held around 5,000 elephants.³⁰⁰ Here, the elephant served many roles when it represented the empire. Outside of imperial processions, the elephant was the imperial mount of the emperor on his hunting expeditions as well. Elephants were employed to hunt other elephants too, but unlike other animals, the elephants caught in a hunt were seldom killed and were most often captured and trained to be used for the empire.³⁰¹ Akbar himself participated in hunting and capturing elephants and the biggest and strongest male elephants captured from the hunts were trained and adopted into the imperial service as *khasa* (special) elephants (Fig. 1).³⁰² Once taken into the imperial stables, the elephants were classified into seven categories where the food, the type of

²⁹⁶ Abraham Eraly, *The Mughal Throne: The Saga of India's Great Emperors* (Phoenix, 2004), 115-116.

²⁹⁷ Smith, *The Oxford History of India*, 337.

²⁹⁸ Smith, *The Oxford History of India*, 160.

²⁹⁹ Smith, *The Oxford History of India*, 160.

³⁰⁰ Divyabhanusinh, "Lions, Cheetahs, and Others in the Mughal Landscape," in *Shifting Ground: People, Animals, and Mobility in India's Environmental History*, ed. Mahesh Rangarajan and K Sivaramkrishnan (New Delhi: Oxford University Press, 2014), 88-108, 99.

³⁰¹ Anooshahr, "The Elephant and Imperial Continuities," 149.

³⁰² Divyabhanusinh, "Lions, Cheetahs, and Others," 100.

care and servants that were assigned to these elephants were based on their respective category.³⁰³ In addition to starting a specialised breeding program for these elephants which was previously not practised in the subcontinent, Akbar also personally inspected his elephants and the *khasa* elephants were reserved to be used only by him.³⁰⁴

Royal entertainment was another major role that was fulfilled by imperial elephants. Elephant races and elephant fights (Fig. 2) were common forms of entertainment, which were reserved only for the emperor.³⁰⁵ Akbar was known to have immensely enjoyed watching elephant fights throughout his youth and is famously known to have fought in many elephant duels himself, often at considerable risk to his own life.³⁰⁶ This legendary reputation since his youth for taming and bringing rogue or drunk elephants under control was tactfully incorporated into the narrative that the emperor was able to avoid all the dangers due to his divinity and closeness to God and was portrayed as a warning to any opposition to his rule that the emperor feared nothing.³⁰⁷ This development was coupled with the fact that Akbar by this time was hailed as an emanation of the Light of God and as a superior semi-divine being specially chosen by God to rule.³⁰⁸ His lineage was traced back not only to Timur and Genghis Khan, but also to many divine religious figures and ultimately back to the Sun itself, which was applied as solar symbolisms in various avenues of Mughal art and architecture during not only Akbar's reign but also during those of his immediate successors.³⁰⁹ Through the combination of these varied factors, the image of the emperor grew more divine and less human while his famous feats in subduing unruly elephants was expertly utilised to add on to this divine narrative. This would also be interpreted as Akbar bringing the symbol of Indian kingship under his control whereby he was the undisputed ruler who could tame and bring to submission any rebellious elephant or, symbolically, any rebellious Indian ruler.³¹⁰

³⁰³ Divyabhanusinh, "Lions, Cheetahs, and Others," 101.

³⁰⁴ Buckingham, "Symbolism and Power," 9; Divyabhanusinh, "Lions, Cheetahs, and Others," 101.

³⁰⁵ Anooshahr, "The Elephant and Imperial Continuities," 161.

³⁰⁶ Anooshahr, "The Elephant and Imperial Continuities," 161.

³⁰⁷ Anooshahr, "The Elephant and Imperial Continuities," 161.

³⁰⁸ Catherine B Asher, "A Ray from the Sun: Mughal Ideology and the Visual Construction of the Divine," in *The Presence of Light: Divine Radiance and Religious Experience*, ed. Matthew Kapstein (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2004), 161–94, 170; Anna Malecka, "Solar Symbolism of the Mughal Thrones. A Preliminary Note," *Arts Asiatiques* 54, no. 1 (1999): 24–32.

³⁰⁹ Abul Fazl, *The Akbarnama of Abu'l Fazl. Vol. I*, trans. Henry Beveridge (Calcutta: Asiatic Society of Bengal, 1897), 37; Asher, *Architecture of Mughal India*, 40; Malecka, "Solar Symbolism of the Mughal Thrones", 24–32; Asher, "A Ray from the Sun," 170.

³¹⁰ Buckingham, "Symbolism and Power," 6.

Elephants were also utilised to express the emperor's power and authority through administration of the king's justice, serving as imperial executioners.³¹¹ We find the earliest recorded instance of this among the Mughals with Babur who issued this punishment to one of his cooks who tried to poison him.³¹² Using elephants to trample enemies of the state came to be actively used as imperial punishment by his successors in the years to come. Consequently, anyone found guilty of mistreating or causing harm to an elephant across the land could be sentenced to death or sold as a slave.³¹³

Taken together, this shift in accepting the elephant as the symbol of imperial power and sovereignty also implied that Akbar was embracing a part of the indigenous cultural symbolisms of the Indian subcontinent over antecedents from Central Asia, where his ancestors were originally from.³¹⁴ Owing to this, the elephant tended to be a steady presence in both Mughal art and architecture as well, generally portrayed to appear in close proximity to the emperor or the spaces that represented his authority. This is particularly evident in the case of paintings of the Mughal emperor holding court where the elephant, if included, is placed either in the audience or as sculptures immediately below the emperor's *jharokha* (balcony), upon which the attendants stood. However, the elephant was not restricted just to art. The elephant became a part of the Mughal architectural scheme too where they appeared as a decorative motif in many settings, from column capitals to even life-size sculptures made of black marble which flanked the Delhi Gate of the Red Fort in Delhi (Fig. 3). A cursory understanding of this close relationship of the emperor and the elephant opens the way to explore the case of the Mughal processions under consideration.

³¹¹ Buckingham, "Symbolism and Power," 11.

³¹² Babur, *The Baburnama: Memoirs of Babur, Prince and Emperor*, trans. Wheeler M Thackston (New York: Modern Library, 2002), 368.

³¹³ Buckingham, "Symbolism and Power," 12.

³¹⁴ Buckingham, "Symbolism and Power," 92–114.

Figure 1: Portrait of the imperial elephant called 'Alam Guman Gajraj' which was presented to the Mughal Emperor Jahangir in 1614. Artist: Bichitr, 1640. Source: The Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York. Public Domain.

Figure 2: Shah Jahan watching an elephant fight from the jharokha window (possibly at Agra Fort). Folio from Padshahnama. Artist: Bulaqi, 1639. Source: The Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York. Public Domain.

4. Elephants in Mughal Processions

This section explores the two broad types of processions that are considered in this study, which are thematically divided based on the distance that was covered and the nature of the procession. For the first category, the imperial march, the focus will be on the role of the elephant in the procession where the Mughal emperor shifts his residence from one city to another, whereas the second category will examine the festive procession, particularly the Friday procession to the Jama Masjid in Shahjahanabad (Old Delhi).

4.1. The Imperial March

In its initial decades, empire building was a laborious task which demanded constant movement of the emperor within his domains. The requirement for this movement could arise due to a plethora of reasons ranging from military campaigns, civil war, quelling rebellions and pilgrimage to Sufi shrines or just seeking a temporary respite from the harsh Indian summers. However, the resulting march meant that both the court as well as the household would be accompanying the emperor as a procession.³¹⁵ The elephant came to play an important role in this type of procession as it served as the mount that carried not only the emperor, but his core entourage, including the accompanying family (generally covered from public view), courtiers, as well as carrying the bulk of the baggage.³¹⁶ Travel accounts of this procession type are available from the time of two emperors, Shah Jahan (r. 1628-1658) and Aurangzeb (r. 1658-1707), both being eye-witness accounts by Europeans. Shah Jahan's procession from Agra to Lahore (approximately 600 km) was recorded by an anonymous Italian who observed the start of the procession, giving us the public's perspective to the spectacle, while Aurangzeb's procession was documented by François Bernier, a French physician and traveller who served the emperor and was thus a part of the procession.³¹⁷

³¹⁵ Buckingham, "Symbolism and Power," 13.

³¹⁶ Buckingham, "Symbolism and Power," 13.

³¹⁷ Aniruddha Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document on the March of Shah Jahan from Agra to Lahore in September 1638," *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress* 56 (1995): 220–26, 220; François Bernier, *Travels in the Mogul Empire, A.D. 1656-1668*, ed. Vincent A Smith, trans. Archibald Constable (London: Oxford University Press, 1934), 280.

At the outset, both these processions, which took place within a span of fifty years from each other, had significant overlaps. The similarity in the details of the processions in both travel accounts point to the fact that general rules were codified for this type of a march.³¹⁸ With its official commencement set for a time deemed as auspicious by astrologers, these processions tended to be exceptionally large in scale, with estimates in the accounts putting the total number of participants at 125,000, where the soldiers alone accounted for 40,000.³¹⁹ The general structure of this procession was composed of three broad sections, where the first section comprised workers and the emperor's guards, which was subsequently followed by the emperor, his family and important nobles, all of whom rode on elephants, while the third section was made up of women from the extended family of the emperor, women of the harem, servants and eunuchs, among others.³²⁰ The massive scale of the procession involved an equally massive entourage of elephants, horses, camels and oxen that carried people, provisions, water and baggage.³²¹

Although this procession was not one primarily aimed at exhibiting pomp and prestige of the emperor, the opportunity was not missed since this long procession clearly made for a spectacle throughout the lands through which it passed. The large army that accompanied the procession made for a display of strength while the unending train of elephants and other animals made for a spectacle which represented the sovereign and his power. This ultimately played out as a way to claim power and legitimacy in regions on the fringes of imperial power centres which were otherwise not accustomed to such grand imperial displays. Chaplain Edward Terry, who was part of the British delegation of Sir Thomas Roe (1615-1619) to the Mughal court of Jahangir, called the procession 'a walking common-wealth' and calculated that it would take twelve hours for the entire procession to pass one particular point.³²² Meanwhile, Sir Thomas Roe had posited that when the procession stopped to rest for the night, it would take an area of twenty miles in circumference, essentially resembling a small town with regular streets.³²³ The location allotted for all participants inside the camp remained identical each time they camped,

³¹⁸ Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document," 222.

³¹⁹ Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document," 220, 222.

³²⁰ Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document," 220.

³²¹ Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document," 220.

³²² Edward Terry, *A Voyage to East-India* (London: W. Cater, 1777), 399-400; Gascoigne, *The Great Moghuls*, 154.

³²³ Gascoigne, *The Great Moghuls*, 154.

so that it was easier for the people in the procession to find their way.³²⁴ To fasten the process, the emperor and the nobles used additional tents that were set up at the next camping point in advance of the procession's arrival.³²⁵ Additionally, since the elephants carried their riders at an elevated height, imperial subjects were not allowed to watch the procession from upper floors or terraces of buildings.³²⁶ The routes were also cleared in advance and the road was dusted and provided with palisades on sides to prevent crowds from coming close.³²⁷

The elephants were also tasked with carrying the dynastic insignia, where each of the six symbols of the insignia were carried on separate elephants. The symbols of the insignia included two gold fish suspended on the sides of a bow, the face of a sun with rays, the golden hand of Fatima, the head of a horse, the head of a lion-like beast and lastly an imperial umbrella.³²⁸ Raising these golden insignia on richly decorated gilt staffs from a richly caparisoned elephant ensured that the insignia would remain at one of the highest points of elevation for the entire length of the procession, making it one of the most visible elements as well in the longest distance.³²⁹

A strict hierarchy was observed throughout the procession prior to its commencement itself. The aforementioned anonymous Italian noted that the emperor determined the extent of followers that were to accompany him as well as his nobles, in addition to paying in advance for the bazaar that accompanied the procession to procure goods required in advance.³³⁰ Bernier cited that the emperor used six hundred elephants just for himself, with the biggest and highest ranked elephants being the ones he and his family rode on, while a thousand camels were used to carry the baggage and the kitchen of the emperor.³³¹ The nobles followed suit and employed their own elephants, camels and horses for themselves according to their rank.³³² The general hierarchy implied that the nobles who travelled closer to the emperor had a higher rank, suggesting that the emperor was the centre of the procession and he was always portrayed on his

³²⁴ Gascoigne, *The Great Moghuls*, 154.

³²⁵ Gascoigne, *The Great Moghuls*, 154.

³²⁶ Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document," 220.

³²⁷ Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document," 220.

³²⁸ William Dalrymple, *The Last Mughal: The Fall of a Dynasty, Delhi 1857* (London: Bloomsbury, 2006), Chapter 1. Dalrymple describes the procession of the last Mughal ruler, Bahadur Shah Zafar, in detail in this chapter.

³²⁹ Dalrymple, *The Last Mughal*, Chapter 1.

³³⁰ Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document," 222.

³³¹ Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document," 223.

³³² Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document," 223.

elephant for this type of procession.³³³ Thus, the number of elephants that each person in this procession owned could reveal their status and rank at court while their distance from the centre of the procession, i.e. from the emperor, determined their standing in the system.³³⁴

This type of procession largely disappeared after the reign of Aurangzeb as the empire began its rapid decline to the point where the Mughal Emperor started to be confined to the capital city of Shahjahanabad (Old Delhi). However, the Friday procession, which will be analysed next, continued until the very end of the dynasty. Despite the decline of the empire, the elephant still retained its symbolic meanings of kingship even when the British steadily took over administration of large swathes of India over the years. While the subsequent introduction of railways in the subcontinent by the British ended the need for the elephant to serve logistical needs to a large extent, the elephant's role in imperial processions continued well into twentieth century colonial India.

4.2. The Friday Procession

In stark contrast to the imperial march, the Friday procession was one of the shortest imperial processions in terms of distance covered while simultaneously being one of the most common in terms of frequency. The elephant played a central role in this short procession of the Mughal Emperor from his palace to the congregational mosque in his capital city on Fridays. In order to study this procession, this section will focus on this procession type in Delhi.

The walled city of Shahjahanabad was built by Shah Jahan in 1639 and became the capital of the Mughal Empire, replacing Agra which had remained one of the capitals during the reigns of his predecessors.³³⁵ One of the reasons given for this change of capital by Shah Jahan's court historian, Muhammad Salih Kanbo, was that the streets of Agra were too narrow, winding and crowded and as such were a hindrance for the proper conduct of royal processions.³³⁶ This concern was rectified in the planning of Shahjahanabad which utilised two primary ceremonial

³³³ Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document," 223.

³³⁴ Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document," 223.

³³⁵ Percival Spear, *The Delhi Omnibus*, ed. Robert Eric Frykenberg (New Delhi: Oxford University Press, 2008), 26.

³³⁶ Muhammad Salih Kanbo, *Amal-i-Šālih; or, Shāh Jahān Nāmāh, of Muḥammad Sālih Kaṃbō*, Vol. III, trans. Ghulam Yazdani (Calcutta: Asiatic Society of Bengal, 1927), 26-27.

axes to connect the Red Fort (the emperor's residence) to the two prominent gates at the outer walls of the city. Although the congregational mosque, the Jama Masjid (one of the largest mosques in India), was built by Shah Jahan in 1656 alongside the construction of the city, it was not directly placed in these two major ceremonial axes. Instead, it occupied a position between the two axes while still in close proximity to the Red Fort (within a kilometre). There was a direct ceremonial street leading to the East entrance of the Jama Masjid from the Delhi Gate of the Red Fort, which was used by the Mughal emperors for their Friday processions. The Delhi Gate of the Red Fort was also coincidentally flanked by life-size models of elephants made of marble, which still stand today (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: George V, King of England, passing through the Delhi Gate at the Red Fort in Delhi, 1911. Two life-size models of elephants made of marble can be seen in the background. Source gallica.bnf.fr / Bibliothèque nationale de France. Public Domain.

The most detailed description of the Friday procession from Shah Jahan's time was given by François Bernier. According to Bernier, prior to the Friday procession from the Red Fort to the Jama Masjid, the streets on the procession route were watered to settle the dust and reduce the heat.³³⁷ Following this, three hundred musketeers marched out and formed an avenue by lining up on both sides of the wide street up to the Jama Masjid.³³⁸ The procession proper began with up to six horsemen riding out in front to clear the path for the emperor, who subsequently rode out on top of a richly caparisoned elephant, seated under a canopy supported by gilt pillars.³³⁹ The elephant maintained a considerable distance behind the horsemen so that the dust that would be kicked up by the horses would not affect the emperor.³⁴⁰ The emperor was closely followed in procession by high-ranking members of the nobility on horseback or palanquins, along with mace bearers.³⁴¹ Bernier considered this procession to not match up to grand processions he had witnessed in Europe but nevertheless accepted it to possess a magnificence of a different character.³⁴² Therefore, it is worth noting that only the emperor used the elephant on this occasion, whereby he occupied the highest point in the procession while also occupying the middle position yet again in the arrangement, similar to the imperial march but in a much smaller scale.

In addition to the Friday processions, elephants were the imperial mount of both the emperor as well as his family on other festive occasions that involved a processional element, such as imperial wedding processions or the Eid procession, among others, which continued with all pomp and regalia even until the very end of the dynasty in the 1850s. While space constraints restrict a detailed dive into these other avenues that involved processions, what is essential to note is that despite the changes in geopolitical realities for the Mughal dynasty, brought about by its decline starting in the eighteenth century, the richly caparisoned elephant still served as the symbol of kingship through which the emperor was presented to the public during an imperial procession. Essentially, the elephant in procession functioned as a visible reminder of the

³³⁷ Bernier, *Travels in the Mogul Empire*, 280.

³³⁸ Bernier, *Travels in the Mogul Empire*, 280.

³³⁹ Bernier, *Travels in the Mogul Empire*, 280.

³⁴⁰ Bernier, *Travels in the Mogul Empire*, 280.

³⁴¹ Bernier, *Travels in the Mogul Empire*, 280.

³⁴² Bernier, *Travels in the Mogul Empire*, 280.

continuities from the heyday of the empire, even as the Mughal monarch held very little power towards the end.

5. Changing Times

The Mughal dynasty officially came to an end in India following the uprising of 1857 against the English East India Company rule.³⁴³ Bahadur Shah Zafar, the last Mughal monarch, was exiled to Rangoon (Myanmar) along with his family while the control of British India passed from the English East India Company to the British Crown.³⁴⁴ The ensuing British colonial rule led to many large scale displays of pomp and power by the British, where the elephant found itself being incorporated into these new imperial frameworks at a time of great technological advancements. The legacy of the historic association of the Indian elephant with sovereignty and power in the Indian subcontinent and all its symbolisms associated with royalty were integrated and fully utilised by these new rulers of India in legitimising and proclaiming their rule. Some of the best examples to witness this play out was in the case of the Delhi Durbar processions.

Delhi Durbars were grand coronation ceremonies held in India for the British monarch in order to bestow them with the rank of ‘Emperor/Empress of India’.³⁴⁵ Out of the three Delhi Durbars, held for Queen Victoria (1877), Edward VII (1903) and George V (1911), the elephant was featured as a prominent part of the pompous and enormous processions that took place, particularly in the 1903 Delhi Durbar (Fig. 4).³⁴⁶ The elephants shined in full regalia while carrying the representatives of the highest offices of British power as well as Indian kings in procession. It is worth noting that the British selected the elephant as the platform to display themselves from during these processions despite it taking place in an era with access to motorised vehicles. Although this could have been taken as an opportunity to convey technological superiority over their colony, it did not happen in that manner. Instead, it can be argued that the elephant was opted precisely due to its symbolism related to kingship and

³⁴³ Dalrymple, *The Last Mughal*, Chapter 1.

³⁴⁴ Dalrymple, *The Last Mughal*, Chapter 1.

³⁴⁵ Julie F. Codell, ed., *Power and Resistance: The Delhi Coronation Durbars* (Ahmedabad: Mapin Publishing Pvt. Ltd and The Alkazi Collection of Photography, 2012); Julie F Codell, “On the Delhi Coronation Durbars, 1877, 1903, 1911,” *BRANCH*, June 2012, https://branchcollective.org/?ps_articles=julie-codell-on-the-delhi-coronation-durbars-1877-1903-1911.

³⁴⁶ Codell, *Power and Resistance*; Codell, “On the Delhi Coronation Durbars, 1877, 1903, 1911.”

legitimacy. However, the Delhi Durbar of 1911 presented a unique moment to further explore how deeply the concept of kingship was intertwined with the elephant in the Indian cultural imagination. When the British monarch, George V, joined the imperial procession as part of the durbar festivities (Fig. 3), his reluctance to ride the elephant, choosing instead to ride a horse, was reported to have caused considerable confusion among the Indian onlookers, for a monarch was traditionally expected to ride the elephant in a procession, ultimately causing the king and his exalted status to be less effectively conveyed in this context when he appeared on horseback.³⁴⁷ Thus, the legacy of the elephant in these processions, which existed long before the Mughals came to India, continued long after them, demonstrating the persistence of the image of the elephant and its close association with kingship in the Indian psyche.

Figure 4: Photograph of the British Viceroy's caparisoned elephant kneeling down, likely as part of the Delhi Durbar of 1877. Photographers: Bourne & Shepherd, 1877. Source: The J. Paul Getty Museum, Los Angeles. Public Domain.

³⁴⁷ Charles W. Nuckolls, "The Durbar Incident," *Modern Asian Studies* 24, no. 3 (1990): 529–59, 535; Stephen Bottomore, "'Have You Seen the Gaekwar Bob?': Filming the 1911 De i Durba" *Historical Journal of Film, Radio and Television* 17, no. 3 (1997)

5. Conclusion

With a deeper understanding of Mughal processions that were analysed in this paper, this study demonstrated the common roles that elephants tended to serve in imperial processions. For this, the paper explored two broad types of processions that were thematically divided based on two aspects, the distance that was covered and the nature of the procession, specifically the imperial march and the Friday procession. Through examining these processions, it was noted that the elephant played a key role as the imperial mount of the emperor and his family and other important members from the court and nobility. Regardless of the type of procession, the emperor always rode on the biggest elephant from the imperial stables which held him at the highest elevated position in the procession and thus exalted his power and prestige. Additionally, the emperor tended to occupy a position close to the middle of the procession in both these cases. The second notable feature pertained to dynastic and imperial insignia, which were also displayed atop the elephant during procession, particularly in the imperial march. In addition to its role in processions, the Mughals also actively employed the elephant for other avenues of their life where the elephant remained a royal prerogative, which included royal hunts, royal entertainment, dispensation of justice etc. Through focusing on the processional element of the elephant, the study also highlighted the syncretic underpinnings behind how the Mughals, particularly during Akbar's rule, expertly adopted a tradition inherent to India to fit the needs of their growing empire. As such, this case study stands to demonstrate a unique instance where an incoming dynasty from Central Asia came to find an exceptional way to combine their background with the varied cultures that they came across while ruling over India.

The legacy of the elephant endured long after the Mughal dynasty ended, since its associations to power and legitimacy came to be absorbed and adopted by the British as they became the new rulers of India. Even in the age of motorised vehicles, using elephants in the pompous Delhi Durbar processions gave the British the symbolic gesture of wielding power over their colonial possessions in India. Today, the elephant continues to hold considerable cultural value in many parts of India where they are an integral part of processions. However, its association with Indian kingship have followed the path of the kingdoms in the subcontinent itself as they joined the newly independent states of India or Pakistan following independence

from British rule in 1947. Most of the elephant habitats mentioned in the Mughal texts do not sustain elephant populations today and though elephants have survived well into our time, unlike other species that went extinct in India after the Mughal period (Asiatic cheetah for instance), the elephant is an animal fighting for survival today as its habitats lessen and its conflicts with humans increase. Nevertheless, the elephant remains as an enduring symbol of an inherently Indian concept of kingship that has its roots since the earliest history in the region, which came to be widely adopted by both the societies that inhabited it as well as by foreign dynasties that settled to rule, of which, the Mughal case was analysed in this paper through their processions.

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**Placing the ‘Dreaded Eastern Question’ during the
International Crisis: Familiar Concept Shaped by the British Penny
Press in 1875-1878**

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Abstract

This article discusses the presence of the concept of the ‘Eastern Question’ in the British penny press during the Great Eastern Crisis of 1875-1878. Analyzing closely how the authors and editors of Victorian daily newspapers placed the concept in their texts, it articulates the changes in the concept’s meanings throughout the crisis. The article underlines the familiarity of the concept to Victorian newsmakers and its gradual introduction after the crisis started. It also indicates how the changes in articles’ titles shifted the meanings of the concept. Additionally, it asks how the crisis and omnipresent references to the ‘Eastern Question’ influenced the approaches to placing advertisements in the British penny press between 1875–1878, thus contributing to the existing literature dealing with the economy of news. Finally, pointing out how the concept was used, it argues that the newspapers’ authors presented different temporalities for the possible solution of the Eastern Question. Visions of short-term and long-term solutions intertwined, revealing the “heteroglossia,” to use Martic Conboy’s term, often evident in the same newspaper issue. Ultimately, the article defines an international crisis as a crucial point for

the historical concepts as their meanings were significantly debated and transformed in the flourishing media environment.

Keywords: *Great Eastern Crisis, penny press, Eastern question*

Introduction

On 25 March 1878, The Manchester Guardian reported that the ship Eastern Question was ready to deliver cotton from Liverpool to New York.³⁴⁸ On the same day, The Daily News published a telegram from Reuters about the situation in Greece that, according to the text, depended “upon England for an equitable solution of the Eastern Question.”³⁴⁹ Furthermore, The Standard presented the review on the book *Armenia and the Campaign of 1877* with the reviewer's comment on “more and more keen interest in the Eastern Question.”³⁵⁰ It was a single concept, the ‘Eastern Question,’ that united texts dealing with commerce, international relations, and literature.³⁵¹ This concept appeared regularly on the pages of Victorian daily press during the Great Eastern Crisis of 1875-1878, a period of instability in Europe that started from the uprising in Herzegovina and continued until the Treaty of Berlin was signed in July 1878.

Historians of media argue that the second half of the nineteenth century was marked by the development of war correspondence, emergence of new journalism, and general commodification of information in the British Empire.³⁵² Uprisings and warfare presented solid

³⁴⁸ “Clearances of Cotton Ships,” *The Manchester Guardian*, March 25, 1878, 4.

³⁴⁹ “England and Greece,” *The Daily News*, March 25, 1878, 5.

³⁵⁰ “New Books,” *The Standard*, March 25, 1878, 2.

³⁵¹ Throughout this article I approach the ‘Eastern Question’ as a historical concept, whose meanings changed throughout the times and geographies and depended on the usage of individuals, anonymized and speaking in public. Therefore, I consider the concept that appeared a given social realm that helps to understand it more thoroughly, following Reinhart Koselleck and putting this text in contrast to Holly Case’s account on “questions” vividly present in the public sphere of Europe between 1850-1950 (See Reinhart Koselleck, ‘Begriffsgeschichte and Social History’, in *Futures Past: On the Semantics of Historical Time*, transl. Keith Tribe (New York: Columbia University Press, 2004), 75–92; Holly Case, *The Age of Questions or, A First Attempt at an Aggregate History of the Eastern, Social, Woman, American, Jewish, Polish, Bullion, Tuberculosis, and Many Other Questions over the Nineteenth Century, and Beyond* (Princeton & Oxford: Princeton University Press, 2018), 4–6). With that, however, Case’s reference to Foucault in her observations on the circulation of the “questions” that had to be solved, is still essential for the part of the present.

³⁵² See, e.g., Andrew Griffiths, *The New Journalism, the New Imperialism and the Fiction of Empire, 1870–1900* (London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2015); Jean. K. Chalaby, *The Invention of Journalism* (New York: Palgrave MacMillan, 1998); Joel H. Wiener, *The Americanization of the British Press, 1830s–1914. Speed in the Age of Transatlantic Journalism* (London: Routledge, 2011); Andrew King, Alexis Easley, John Morton, eds., *The Routledge Handbook to Nineteenth-Century: British Periodicals and Newspapers* (London & New York: Routledge, 2016).

ground for sensations about the barely known Other, the subjects of the Ottoman Empire, to be highlighted. Among others, the concept of the ‘Eastern Question’ appeared as one of the most prominent in these texts. Traditionally, scholars refer to it to interpret the images of decline that the Ottoman Empire experienced between the end of the eighteenth and the beginning of the twentieth century. Historians of diplomacy frequently invoked the ‘Eastern Question’ in order to explain the struggle between the Great Powers for the heritage of the Ottomans and presented it as a relatively stable concept in history in general and during the crisis of 1875-1878 in particular, rarely pointing out the possible changes and variations in its usage.³⁵³ Recently, several scholars have gone beyond the focus on traditional diplomatic history and approached the concept from the perspective of intellectual history and the new political history of the British Empire.³⁵⁴ Although their research clarifies the complex presence of the concept in imperial public discourse, they nevertheless ignore the media aspect of the story.³⁵⁵ Attempts to generalize the attitudes toward the Eastern Question within the empire thus leave the simultaneous circulation of its meanings aside, forming the gap that this article aims to cover.

This article explores the concept of the ‘Eastern Question’ based on its placement on the pages of Victorian daily newspapers in 1875-1878. It focuses on the mass penny press, primarily London-based *The Standard*, *The Daily News*, *The Daily Telegraph*, and the regional *The Manchester Guardian*.³⁵⁶ Articles from *The Morning Post* published in 1875 are also taken into

³⁵³ See John A. R. Marriott, *The Eastern Question; an Historical Study in European Diplomacy*. (Oxford: The Clarendon Press, 1917), 1–3; Robert W. Seton-Watson, *Disraeli, Gladstone and the Eastern Question: a Study in Diplomacy and Party Politics* (New York: W. W. Norton & Company Inc., 1972), ix, 113, 479; Mikhail N. Pokrovskii, *Diplomatia i Voiny Tsarskoj Rossii v XIX Stoletii* (London: Overseas Publications Interchange, 1991), 24, 179, 230; Nina S. Kinyapkina, “Vvedenie,” in *Vostochnyj Vopros vo Vneshnej Politike Rossii: Konets XVIII – Nachalo XX v.*, ed. Nina Stepanovna Kinyapkina (Moskva: «Nauka», 1978), 3–10; Robert Blake, *Disraeli* (New York: St. Martin's Press, 1967), 602–605; Martin Swartz, *The Politics of British Foreign Policy in the Era of Disraeli and Gladstone* (London: The Macmillan Press, 1985), 38–41.

³⁵⁴ Gerald D. Clayton, *Britain and Eastern Question: Missolonghi to Gallipoli* (London: University of London Press, Ltd, 1971), 153; au Aucht Ioni “Fro th Eastern Question to the Death of r Re en ons o idd st i th V torian Period o er t i 8 no. 1 (2001 5–24 Milos Ko d New York: Oxford ive it Pr s, 1 vi i Je e beralism and the Balkans, c. 18 –1 5” D is , iv si o Lo on 20 36.

³⁵⁵ A dissertation by Leslie Schumac s, perhaps, the exception in this case. Presenting the relations between British politics, public discourse and diplomacy during the Great Eastern Crisis of 1875-1878, he pays attention to the role of the media in sharing information about the Eastern Question at the time. With that, however, he does not go beyond the fixed definition of the Eastern question as a phenomenon connected with the decline of the Ottoman Empire. See Leslie R. Schumacher, “A «Lasting Solution»: the Eastern Question and British Imperialism, 1875–1878” (PhD diss. The University of Minnesota, 2012), vi–vii, 1–3.

³⁵⁶ I worked with the digital copies of the newspapers provided by The British Newspaper Archive (<https://www.britishnewspaperarchive.co.uk/>). The issues of *The Standard* from July 1, 1876, to December 31, 1876 are absent in the archive, so I was not able to analyze them. The issues of *The Manchester Guardian* were taken from Newspapers.com digital archive.

consideration to clarify the circulation of the concept before and at the beginning of the crisis.³⁵⁷ Using online tools to work with the newspapers, I created a database for the concept's appearance in each of the newspapers, which I later used for both quantitative and qualitative analysis.³⁵⁸

My approach to the meanings of the 'Eastern Question' was informed by Reinhart Koselleck's paradigm of "futures past" and Boris Maslov and Yury Kagarlitskiy's methodological observations about individual interpretations of the concepts, which provided useful background to conceptual history.³⁵⁹ Reflecting on the categories of the "space of experience" and "horizon of expectations" as useful for historical analysis, Koselleck highlights the importance of temporalization of historical concepts and their changing character across time and argues for using analytical categories that were not articulated in the language in the past to understand historical circumstances.³⁶⁰ These categories are essential as "they provide guidance to concrete agencies in the course of social or political movement."³⁶¹ In this article, I incorporate both categories pointed out by Koselleck to underline the changes in the language Victorian daily newspapers authors applied between 1875 and 1878. The changes often occur when there is a transformation in the concepts that have a constructive role within discourses they circulate in, as Maslov and Kagarlitskiy point out.³⁶² For them, however, the discourses are first and foremost political, while this article proposes to look at the media *per se* and its role in shaping the meanings of the concept of the 'Eastern Question' during the four years of the crisis, which allows to look at the usage of the concept on a day-to-day basis. To contextualize that usage, I

³⁵⁷ *The Standard* and *The Morning Post* were conservative newspapers, while *The Daily News* remained the only prominent newspaper that supported Liberal party after the elections in 1874. *The Daily Telegraph* shifted to Conservatives during the Great Eastern Crisis. *The Manchester Guardian* became an important regional newspaper thanks to telegraph. It also mostly leaned to the thoughts of Liberal politicians (see Bourne H. R. Fox, *English Newspapers: Chapters in the History of Journalism. Volume 2* (New York: Russell & Russell, 1966), 334-335, Wiener, *The Americanization of the British Press*, 103).

³⁵⁸ To identify the concept's presence, I used online tools offered by the British Newspaper Archive and Newspapers.com. Starting with searching the keyword "The Eastern Question," I went manually through every mention of the word combination or its alterations in 1875-1878. This inquiry resulted in several tables featuring the date the concept was mentioned, the form the concept had, the place where it was put (both page and column), and the context of its appearance.

³⁵⁹ Reinhart Koselleck, *Futures Past: On the Semantics of Historical Time*, transl. Keith Tribe (New York: Columbia University Press, 2004); Boris Maslov and Yury Kagarlitskiy, "Mezhdu Frege i Fuko: Metodologicheskie Osnovy Istoricheskoy Semantiki," in *Poniatiiia, Idei, Konstruktsii*, ed. Yury Kagarlitskiy, Dmitrii Kalugin, and Boris Maslov (Moskva: Novoe Literaturnoe Obozrenie, 2019), 9-38.

³⁶⁰ Reinhart Koselleck, "«Space of Experience» and «Horizon of Expectation»: Two Historical Categories," in *Futures Past*, 255.

³⁶¹ Koselleck, "«Space of Experience»," 258.

³⁶² Maslov and Kagarlitskiy, "Mezhdu Frege i Fuko," 31-34.

also paid attention to the approaches to study Victorian journalism and print culture through the lens of sociolinguistics proposed by Lyn Pykett and Martin Conboy.³⁶³ In particular, Conboy proposes to use the concept of ‘heteroglossia’ to explain the circulation of information in the Victorian press, arguing that newspaper texts presented a dialogic space that contested the dominant social-linguistic norms.³⁶⁴ This notion was helpful for the analysis of the variability of meanings connected to the concept of the Eastern Question. At the same time, the authors’ anonymity did not allow me to identify all the writers of the texts, which is why I focus on other markers that may show the multiplicity of interpretations.³⁶⁵

Already the first glance at the appearance of the ‘Eastern Question’ reveals its presence in editorial articles, columns with international and commercial news, and sections on advertisement, which made its presence ubiquitous in the daily press between 1875-1878 (See Figure 1, Figure 2, Figure 3, Figure 4). Yet, different authors and editors granted the concept with multiple meanings, which were based on their choices of overall narratives for articles or specific connotations within a given piece of a text. That dynamic encourages one to look closer at where and how the concept appeared when the crisis that started in a small vilayet of the Ottoman Empire resonated within the European continent and beyond. To trace these appearances, I considered every instance when the concept of the Eastern Question was used, in one form or another, within the context of each of the newspapers, interpreting the newspaper as text, whose editors might have decided to combine different opinions on the same page.³⁶⁶

Analyzing how the concept was placed in day-to-day issues of five dailies, this article underlines the international crisis as a crucial point for the transformation of the meaning of the historical concept. First, it presents a variety of formulations the authors of the penny press applied to introduce the ‘Eastern Question’ to their readers. It then presents the meanings the concept was given amidst the unfolding events in the Balkans and the attempts to influence those events by the Great Powers, and pays attention to the sections of the newspapers where the concept appeared. Finally, addressing the issue of the solutions of the ‘Eastern Question’ offered

³⁶³ Lyn Pykett, “Reading the Periodical Press: Text and Context,” *Investigating Victorian Journalism*, ed. Laurel Brake, Aled Jones, Lionel Madden (London: Macmillan Press, 1990), 3-18; Martin Conboy, *The Language of Newspapers: Socio-Historical Perspectives* (New York: Continuum International Publishing Group, 2010), 1–11, 98–99.

³⁶⁴ Conboy, *The Language of Newspapers*, 5–6.

³⁶⁵ On anonymity in Victorian newspapers see Alberto Gabriele, *Reading Popular Culture in Victorian Print: Belgravia and Sensationalism* (London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2009), 69–75.

³⁶⁶ In this article, I consider separate opinions that either appeared as independent texts or were inserted as quotes together to highlight the diversity of the media discourse that influenced the meaning of the given concept.

in the newspapers, this article highlights different temporalities imagined by the authors who had to deal with the unpredictable nature of the ‘dreaded Eastern Question.’³⁶⁷

The Eastern Question: forms and formulations

It would not be hard to trace the resemblance between the classic legend of the Hydra's head and the conditions of Turkey in Europe [...] For the last few months, the minds of European diplomats have been perturbed by the complications arising out of the pretensions of the Danube Principalities to conclude treaties of commerce directly with the foreign Powers; and now, when that moot point has been settled more or less satisfactory, the irrepressible Eastern question recurs in the shape of a feud between Montenegro and Turkey.³⁶⁸

These words opened the editorial published in *The Daily Telegraph* on 21 January 1875. Half a year later, the new recursion of the Eastern Question took place after the uprising in Herzegovina started, with the deserved attention from the British press. The information flows that brought the news from the Balkans, however, were unstable, and so was the number and the nature of references to the concept.³⁶⁹ Facing the need to deal with the news from the ‘East,’ imagined and presented by the newspaper contributors, the penny press revealed a variety of approaches and forms its authors adopted to talk about the supposedly familiar concept.

The number of references to the ‘Eastern Question’ changed from the beginning of the crisis. After twenty mentions of the concept in *The Daily Telegraph* in January 1875, when the tensions between Montenegro and the Ottoman Empire were apparent, the concept disappeared from the pages of the newspaper from May to October, and the new increase in the numbers

³⁶⁷ “France.,” *The Standard*, August 23, 1875, 6.

³⁶⁸ “London, Thursday, January 21.,” *The Daily Telegraph*. January 21, 1875, 4.

³⁶⁹ I borrow the concept of “flows” from Stuart Alexander Rockefeller who presents it as “agentless movement with no starting point and no telos” (see Stuart Alexander Rockefeller, “Flow,” *Current Anthropology* 52, no. 4 (August 2011): 558). Although the news always were created by someone, thus were not “agentless,” the acceleration of information amidst the crisis made it difficult to distinguish separate news items from the general mass of notes, even though the first might have appeared in defined articles. As for the numbers, in his dissertation, Leslie Schumacher points out that the leading newspapers had several hundred articles with the title “The Eastern Question” during the Great Eastern Crisis of 1875-1878 but does not mention when and how these headlines appeared (Schumacher, “A «Lasting Solution», 169).

happened only in November.³⁷⁰ The Eastern Question was used constantly in 1876 (the total number of mentions was 302). In 1877, there were 256 mentions of the concept while the first nine months of 1878 brought 307 mentions (Figure 1). These tendencies seem to correlate with the general development of events in the Balkans at the time. The uprising in Herzegovina and later Bosnia in summer of 1875 brought back the reference to the term. Then, in spring 1876, a rebellion also happened in Bulgaria, and the Ottoman Empire used the *başibozuk*, the irregular troops, in order to put it down. Their violent actions against the civilian Bulgarian population attracted much attention in the British Empire due to the campaign against the government's alleged support for the Ottoman Empire led by the former prime-minister William Gladstone that started after his pamphlet *Bulgarian Atrocities and the Question of the East* was published in September 1876.³⁷¹ Finally, 1877-1878 were the years of the Russo-Ottoman war and the following peaceful negotiations that were also urgent events for the British public.

However, the other daily newspapers demonstrated a different dynamic in 1875. Only 22 mentions of the concept appear in *The Standard*, 19 in *The Daily News*, and 34 in *The Manchester Guardian* during January-September 1875. The number increased sharply in *The Standard* during the following month, while the rise in numbers was more moderate in the other two newspapers. The 'Eastern Question' started appearing regularly in all three from April 1876 onwards. Thus, the authors of the articles in *The Standard*, *The Daily News*, and *The Manchester Guardian* were not interested in using the concept at the beginning of the Great Eastern Crisis, and it only received much attention starting with the Bulgarian uprising in 1876 (Figure 2, Figure 3, Figure 4).

The differences in the numbers of mentions may be explained by the fact that back in January 1875, *The Daily Telegraph* introduced a separate column under the title "The Eastern Question" in the part "General Foreign News," where the telegrams from abroad were regularly published.³⁷² From mid-January 1875, 'The Eastern Question' had become a separate column

³⁷⁰ The editorial's note quoted at the start of this section refers directly to this tension. Montenegro gained a semi-independent status after winning a conflict with the Ottoman Empire in 1858 but her independence was not formally recognized until the Congress of Berlin in 1878. For a brief overview of the Ottoman-Montenegrin relations see e.g., Sumner, *Russia and the Balkans*, 132–134.

³⁷¹ William E. Gladstone, *Bulgarian Horrors and the Question of the East* (New York and Montreal: Lovell, Adam, Wesson and Company, 1876).

³⁷² See "The Eastern Question.," *The Daily Telegraph*, January 2, 1875, 3; "The Eastern Question.," *The Daily Telegraph*, January 6, 1875, 3; "The Eastern Question.," *The Daily Telegraph*, January 12, 1875, 3.

without direct connection with other news from abroad.³⁷³ The telegrams about the events in the Balkans as well as international reactions to these events were reported by special correspondents from European capitals or Reuters.³⁷⁴ This column seems to be an editor's decision to present the events from the East within the defined conceptual frame put in the title 'The Eastern Question.'³⁷⁵ At the same, neither of the collection of telegrams explained the meanings of this Eastern Question and, therefore, the authors presumed that the readers were familiar with the concept.³⁷⁶

Implicit presumption of the familiarity with the concept still left the newspapers contributors with necessity to face the uncertainties of the unfolding international crisis.³⁷⁷ Thus, the notion that the phases of the Eastern Question could change during a single day, asserted by liberal politician William Adam in January 1876, made the situation even more unstable and complicated.³⁷⁸ It uncovers the tendency toward the temporalization of concepts, typical for the modern era.³⁷⁹ The modern concepts usually described particular processes rather than static phenomena, and the Eastern Question, based on Adam's observations, marked one of such processes, with its referent being mostly outside, either at the theatre of uprising or somewhere within the channels of diplomatic communication.

³⁷³ "The Eastern Question.," *The Daily Telegraph*, January 15, 1875, 3; "The Eastern Question.," *The Daily Telegraph*, January 18, 1875, 3.

³⁷⁴ After the telegraph was nationalized in 1868, the news market in the British Empire also changed. In 1870, the Association of Provincial Newspapers signed an agreement with Reuters about the reduced price for the news from abroad in exchange for the regional news free of charge. London Newspapers *The Daily Telegraph*, *The Standard*, and *The Daily News* did not join the agreement, so the tariff for the foreign news was high. Thus, it was cheaper for them to have special correspondents in European capitals than to receive all the information from the news agency. See Jonathan Silberstein-Loeb, "The Structure of the News Market in Britain, 1870-1914," *The Business History Review* 83, no. 4 (2009): 767-775). At the same time, all three newspapers also continued to purchase information from Reuters.

³⁷⁵ Niklas Luhmann defined the editorial presentation of information as "coding." For him, every journal or newspaper issue contained particular code formed by the editors. Thus, the code transferred the foundations of editorial politics (See Niklas Luhmann, *The Reality of Mass-Media*, transl. Kate Cross (Stanford: Stanford University Press, 2000), 15-20).

³⁷⁶ In this context I refer to the ideal type of a reader who, as Martin Conboy points out, usually is constructed within the language of newspapers and, in fact, participates in the creation of senses by the newspaper (Martin Conboy, *The Language of Newspapers*, 3).

³⁷⁷ The interpretations of the events in the Ottoman Empire as the "crisis" first appeared in the penny press in mid-autumn 1875, three months after the start of the uprising in Bosnia (see, e.g., "London, Saturday, October 9, 1875.," *The Morning Post*, October 9, 1875, 4; "The Eastern Question.," *The Standard*, November 11, 1875, 5 "The Turkish Crisis," *The Daily Telegraph*, November 18, 5). The notion of the crisis, in this context, could also have different meaning, as a moment of decision as well as the prolonged stage of uncertainty, but to deal with that would require a separate article (on crisis, see Reinhart Koselleck and Michaela W. Richter, "Crisis," *Journal of the History of Ideas* 67, no. 2 (2006): 357-400).

³⁷⁸ "The Eastern Question.," *The Daily Telegraph*, January 15, 1877, 2.

³⁷⁹ Kagarlitskiĭ and Maslov, "Between Frege and Foucault, 29.

The form in which the concept was placed in the penny press was also unstable because of intended sensationalization.³⁸⁰ Throughout the crisis, the formulations that marked the concept always contained the adjective *Eastern* (sometimes *Oriental*), but the last part seemed to be a matter of choice. Along with the “Eastern Question,” the editors and contributors of all major daily newspapers also used a wide variety of expressions to sensationalize their texts: “Eastern affairs,” “Eastern matters,” “Eastern situation,” “Eastern controversy,” “Eastern complication(s),” “Eastern difficulty(ies),” “Eastern concert,” “Eastern problem,” “Eastern quarrel,” “Eastern struggle,” “Eastern troubles,” “Eastern menace,” “Eastern mess,” “Eastern deadlock,” “Eastern tragedy,” “Eastern falsetto,” “the Eastern imbroglio,” “the Eastern chaos” and “the Eastern drama.” Different forms made the whole message sound more sensational, while the concept’s meanings remained preserved.

The concept’s form was also profoundly shaped by newspapers’ special correspondents.³⁸¹ In 1875, telegrams with information about the affairs in South-Eastern Europe often contained emotional metaphors like “anxious of reopening,” “reopen of the terrible Eastern Question,” “sullen menace,” and “terrible eventuality.”³⁸² On the one hand, these expressions could mark the concerns expressed by the special correspondents. On the other hand, all of them contained the elements of sensationalism, as explained by Norman Fairclough.³⁸³ Together with emotional formulations of the concept per se, they could make the message of the article more vivid. Thus, regardless of the type of the text, the Eastern Question presented a good ground for the writers’ creativity that allowed to highlight the overly present anxieties about the future, which I will discuss later in this article.

What the sensational frame of the news about the Eastern Question aimed at was to encourage the readers' interest in the still little-known East. In the collection of news about the ongoing events in the British Empire, published in *The Daily Telegraph* on 22 December 1877, the notion about the development of “this infernal Eastern tragedy” appeared. Later in the text an

³⁸⁰ On the intentional sensationalization of news, see Chalaby, *The Invention of Journalism*, 97–98.

³⁸¹ On the role of special correspondents in the 1870s, see Andrew Griffiths *The New Journalism*, 26–27, Wiener, *The Americanization of the British Press*, 96.

³⁸² “Russia and the East,” *The Daily Telegraph*, February 1, 1875, 5; “The study of various telegrams...” *The Manchester Guardian*, September 14, 1875, 5; “We are told that...” *The Daily Telegraph*, January 22, 1875, 5; “France.,” *The Standard*, August 31, 1875, 5.

³⁸³ Fairclough points out that the sensationalist texts produce the sense of alarm, stressed by particular words (e.g. deadly, dangerous or toxic). The authors of these texts play the role of entertainers whose works are “simultaneously representing, setting up identities, and setting up relations” (see Norman Fairclough, *Media Discourse* (London: Arnold, 1995), 4–5).

anonymous author reflected on the Russo-Ottoman war and the difficulties that the war presented before the British government.³⁸⁴ A similar approach of making the news more sensitive appeared in the editorial article published in *The Standard* on 24 December. Focusing on Germany's involvement in the attempts to solve the conflict in the East, the author presumed that Germans hardly could enjoy their role in the “Eastern drama.”³⁸⁵ Sensational news was typical for capital and provincial newspapers in the 1870s. Edward Lewi, the owner of *The Daily Telegraph*, was a pioneer when he made the principle of human interest a cornerstone of the newspaper from the very beginning that correlated with the ideas of New Journalism that emerged at the time.³⁸⁶ However, as Martin Conboy claims, additional accents that were attached to the important news became quite ordinary in the 1870s.³⁸⁷ Thus, the editorial decisions to make information sound more appealing led to the shape of the concept, creatively adapted in the press, which detached it from the context of politics where it originated.³⁸⁸

The variety of possible formulations coexisted with the idea that multiple Eastern questions could exist amidst the crisis. In summer 1875, *The Morning Post* published an article whose author pointed out that “all the Eastern Questions are less interesting to France than to England.”³⁸⁹ By referring to the Eastern questions, he mentioned Constantinople as the key to the Mediterranean, the loans for the Ottoman empire, Egypt and the Suez Canal. The last two ‘questions’ represented a spatial dimension of the issue that was even more vivid with the case of Syria and Levant. Some observers included these territories in the Eastern Question, while others put it aside.³⁹⁰ Therefore, the authors defined the spatial marks of the concept differently, sometimes presenting them as related to several eastern questions. What then constituted those “questions”?

³⁸⁴ “«Fair Play» writes...,” *The Daily Telegraph*, December 22, 1877, 3.

³⁸⁵ “That in official...,” *The Standard*, December 24, 4.

³⁸⁶ Jean K. Chalaby, *The Invention of Journalism*, 147–155.

³⁸⁷ Martin Conboy *The Language of Newspapers*, 91–92.

³⁸⁸ On the origins of the Eastern Question, *The Eastern Question*.

³⁸⁹ “France.,” *The Morning Post*, June 23, 1875, 6.

³⁹⁰ “Money Market.,” *The Daily Telegraph*, June 9, 1876, 2; “A day like New Year's-day...,” *The Standard*, January 1, 1877, 4; “England and the East.,” *The Standard*, January 1, 1878, 3; “We have reason...,” *The Daily Telegraph*, August 25, 1875, 4.

Attempting a Definition: What Was the ‘Eastern Question’?

An anonymous article published in *The Standard* on 1 June 1878, a couple of weeks before the Congress of Berlin started, presents one of the clearest examples of the ambiguities germane to the discussions around the ‘Eastern Question.’ Reflecting on the issues connected to the definition of the question, the author pointed out that it was indeed difficult to find a single explanation for it:

At one time, even Englishmen persuaded themselves that it was only a Bulgarian question. Russia, in the levity of ambitious impulses, conceived that it was only a question between herself and Turkey. These and other kindred mistakes are now recognised as such by the slowest intelligences. We have before us a Christian question, a Mahometan question, a Slav question, a Hungarian question, an Austro-Hungarian question, a Servian question, a Montenegrin question, a Roumanian question, a Greek question, an Italian question, a Europo-Turkish question, a Turco-Asiatic question, a British Empire question. It is enough to take away one's breath. Yet we have by no means exhausted the list of questions which are embraced in those brief and familiar words, the Eastern Question. *We have named only the most conspicuous and most urgent.*³⁹¹ (emphasis added)

The variety of the components that, in the author’s opinion, constituted the Eastern Question, was only one attempt to reflect on the undefined concept. At the peak of Bulgarian agitation, an anonymous author concluded that people in the British Empire might “know really as much now about the Eastern Question as many professional diplomats.”³⁹² This knowledge was regularly presented to a wider public but simultaneously was atomized by the daily press. Yet there were three prominent themes raised by the authors when they referred to the concept, namely morality and religion, the Balkans, and domestic politics.

Historians have shown that the religious component was an important part of the Eastern Question throughout the nineteenth century.³⁹³ The idea of struggle between the Christians and

³⁹¹ “Although no statement...,” *The Standard*, June 1, 1878, 4.

³⁹² “Events must decide...,” *The Daily Telegraph*. 1876. September 28, 4.

³⁹³ See., e.g, Marriott, *The Eastern Question*; Milos Ković, “Disraeli’s Orientalism Reconsidered,” *Serbian Political Thought*, no. 1 (2016): 5-14; Zoran Grijak, “Croatian – British views of the Eastern Question: The

Muslims was easily implemented into the history and the present of the Eastern Question within Victorian intellectual culture. Still, the authors of daily newspapers presented ambiguous views on the concept's connection with religion. Some of them pointed out that the Eastern Question was a religious question, while the Russian Empire transformed it into a political one.³⁹⁴ Others mentioned directly that the question did have a religious component.³⁹⁵ In particular, a priest Canon Liddon mentioned that it was not a question of religion, but rather a question of humanity. He referred to the oppression that the population of the European part of the Ottoman empire experienced from "one of the most barbarous despotisms that ever oppressed any portion of the human race."³⁹⁶ Such a humanitarian perspective was not exclusive.³⁹⁷ On 27 November 1876, *The Daily Telegraph* published an article whose author argued that the Eastern Question was a question of "response of Europe, general prosperity, and Christian civilization."³⁹⁸ Leslie Schumacher defines similar interpretations as a new version of the Eastern Question that emerged as a reaction from the British population to the 'Bulgarian atrocities' that occurred in spring and summer 1876.³⁹⁹ However, its 'new version' was, in fact, one of many possible interpretations of the concept that emerged between 1875 and 1878. The discussion about the humanitarian aspect of the question indeed appeared after the news from Bulgaria reached the British Empire and provoked the 'Bulgarian agitation.' Yet, within the newspapers' texts it was only an addition to the previous interpretations of the connections between morality, religion and the concept itself.

At the same time, the view on the Eastern Question as an issue of the ongoing disturbances in the Balkans appeared regularly in all daily newspapers throughout the crisis. In general, the greatest number of mentions of the concept was connected to this region, but naturally no consensus was established between the authors. *The Standard's* editors revealed their complex

correspondence of William Ewart Gladstone and Josip Juraj Strossmayer (1876-1882)." *Review of Croatian History* V, br. 1 (2009): 47–84.

³⁹⁴ "The lamentable bloodshed..." *The Standard*, August 20, 1878, 4; "As soon as the Russian troops..." *The Standard*, August 21, 1878, 4. See also "Old Catholic Conference..." *The Daily Telegraph*, August 14, 1875, 5.

³⁹⁵ "Nothing more untoward..." *The Daily Telegraph*, May 9, 1876, 5.

³⁹⁶ "Canon Liddon on the Eastern Question..." *The Standard*, February 2, 1877, 6.

³⁹⁷ The discourses of 'humanitarianism' were prominent in the British Empire in the second half of the nineteenth century. See Abigail Green, "Humanitarianism in Nineteenth-Century Context: Religious, Gendered, National," *The Historical Journal*, Vol. 57, No. 4 (December 2014): 1157–1175; Abigail Green, "The British Empire and the Jews: An Imperialism of Human Rights?," *Past & Present* 199, Issue 1 (May 2008): 175–205; Michelle Tusan, *Smyrna's Ashes: Humanitarianism, Genocide, and the Birth of the Middle East* (Berkeley and Los Angeles, CA: University of California Press, 2012).

³⁹⁸ "If the special telegram..." *The Daily Telegraph*, November 27, 1876, 4.

³⁹⁹ Leslie R. Schumacher, "A «Lasting Solution»," 98–99.

views in the column “The Eastern Question” that was introduced in autumn 1875. For instance, the telegram from Paris published in the column on 10 November 1875, contained reports about the attempts to cope with the situation in the Balkans made by the League of the Three Emperors.⁴⁰⁰ In this case, the Eastern Question was presented as the question of relation between the Great Powers and the Ottoman Empire and as the direction of those powers’ foreign policy. Therefore, the meanings of the concept could be changed depending on the editors' arrangement of the texts that they decided to publish.

Other authors also had a flexible approach to interpreting the Eastern Question in relation to the Balkans. In April 1875, *The Standard* published an article about the increased tensions between the Ottoman Empire and Serbia where the author argued that the Eastern Question became a Serbian question.⁴⁰¹ In a different article two years later, the Eastern Question was connected with the “new Bulgarian Question.”⁴⁰² The article’s author defined the presence of the Ottomans in Europe as only one among many factors that influenced an unstable situation in the Balkans and pointed out that the “Hellenic factor” was also a part of the Eastern Question.⁴⁰³ He claimed that Greeks had their interests and put themselves against Turks and Bulgarians that also caused the tensions on the peninsula.⁴⁰⁴ Similar thoughts about Greeks and Greece as a part of or an independent side in the Eastern Question also appeared on the pages of the daily press.⁴⁰⁵ Additionally, after the Congress of Berlin opened, *The Standard* published an article titled “The Roumanian Question.” The author identified a new phase of the Eastern Question related to the question of the future fate of Bessarabia, for which the Russian Empire expressed its claims.⁴⁰⁶ Although other authors mentioned Romania in the context of the question earlier, it was the first time in four years when the country was presented as an independent part in relation to it.⁴⁰⁷

⁴⁰⁰ “Paris, Tuesday Evening,” *The Standard*, November 10, 1875, 5.

⁴⁰¹ “Russia,” *The Standard*, April 19, 1875, 6.

⁴⁰² “What has been euphemistically...,” *The Standard*, January 6, 1877, 4.

⁴⁰³ The argument about the bad governance of the Ottomans as an important factor of the Eastern Question was also mentioned by other contributors (See e.g. “London, Tuesday, Oct. 30.,” *The Daily News*, October 30, 1877, 4; “Mr. W. E. Forster, M. P. on the War,” *The Manchester Guardian*. January 7, 1878, 6).

⁴⁰⁴ “What has been euphemistically...,” 4.

⁴⁰⁵ “Affairs at Constantinople,” *The Daily News*, October 4, 1876, 6; “The Turks have suffered...,” *The Standard*, October 19, 1877, 4; “Greece and Greeks,” *The Daily News*, December 11, 1877, 7; Zante, “Greece and the Eastern Question,” *The Manchester Guardian*, February 18, 1878, 6.; “Greece and Turkey,” *The Daily Telegraph*, August 26, 1878, 5.

⁴⁰⁶ “The Roumanian Question,” *The Standard*, Ju 17, 1878, 6.

⁴⁰⁷ Contin the a is wa v be 1877 n n o i um t s W y p e c s r Gua ian March 15, 1878, 8; “Russia and Ro ania.” *e Manches* 78, 7).

Thus, the concept was like a mosaic put within the frame of the imagined Balkans, where the were are added and taken out depending on the reactions to the changing situation in the region.

The reactive nature of the changes in the meanings was also visible in the coverage of the Balkan politics of the Great Powers. The author of an article published in *The Standard* on February 27, 1877, pointed out that two Eastern Questions existed simultaneously – “pure Turkish question and Russo-Turkish question.”⁴⁰⁸ He thus distinguished the internal problems of the Ottoman Empire from its relations with the Russian Empire, while both were seen as a part of the “European question” and were related to the interests of other European powers. The Paris correspondent of *The Standard* earlier presented a similar opinion arguing that from the point of *raison d'etat*, the Eastern Question was, in fact, the “Western question.”⁴⁰⁹ In this case, European powers preserved the ties with the Balkans, a main stage of the Eastern Question, but were seen as external actors in relation to the question itself.

The envisioned “civilizing mission” of the Europeans made them a part of the Eastern Question on the pages of Victorian dailies. In the report about the Liberal party meeting in St. James Hall in London published in *The Daily Telegraph* on 10 October 1876, the author quoted Sir James Stansfeld, M.P., who argued that “the Eastern Question was ... a European question – a question involving grave responsibility upon the part of Europe.”⁴¹⁰ Later Stansfeld appealed to the thesis about the civilizing mission Europeans had to bring to the East, and that was their visible relation to the Eastern Question. A similar observation was made by a French correspondent of *The Daily News* who reported on 26 November 1876, about his talks with Paris inhabitants on the Eastern Question. Commenting on the ongoing Serbo-Ottoman war, his companions pointed out that France had to send its troops to the Balkans because “Servians will delight in an army of occupation. We shall civilize them, teach them to dance and talk scandal.”⁴¹¹ From their perspective, “[t]his will be the true solution of the Eastern question.”⁴¹² Presented in an engaging tone, the article diluted the ongoing debate around “Bulgarian atrocities” with a less serious but nevertheless appealing civilizing message.

The imagined stage of the Eastern drama could also vary from time to time. On September 30, 1878, *The Standard* reprinted a fragment of an article published in the Russian newspaper

⁴⁰⁸ “During the long, difficult, February 27, 1877, 4.

⁴⁰⁹ “France.,” *The Standard*, August 31, 1875, 5.

⁴¹⁰ “Meeting in St. James’s Hall.,” *The Daily Telegraph*, October 10, 1876, 3.

⁴¹¹ “Coffee-House Bubble.,” *The Daily News*, November 24, 1876, 6.

⁴¹² “Coffee-House Bubble.,” 6.

The Exchange News, in which the author argued that the simplest definition of the Eastern Question was the struggle between Russia and England, and the competition between the empires for the Eastern territories was highlighted. However, in this case, the East was presented not by the Balkans, but by Afghanistan and India.⁴¹³ Such a notion shows that not all the messages presented in the Victorian daily press limited the Eastern Question to South-Eastern Europe, and the imagined boundaries of the question could be flexibly expanded.

Yet, it was the domestic politics that shaped the meaning of the Eastern Question most drastically during the Great Eastern Crisis. On 13 December 1876, *The Daily Telegraph* published an article under the title, “The Eastern Question” where the dinner hosted by the Earl of Mount Edgcumbe was described.⁴¹⁴ Among other remarks an anonymous correspondent paid attention to the words of conservative politician Messis Lopes who was dissatisfied with the attempts to transform the Eastern Question to the “party question.”⁴¹⁵ Lopes believed in the clear motives of Disraeli's government to obtain freedom for the Balkan Christians and was concerned with the attempts of Liberal politicians to discredit the foreign policy of the British Empire.⁴¹⁶ Before the “Bulgarian agitation” led by William Gladstone started in autumn 1876, there was no single mention of the connection between the Eastern Question and domestic party affairs. The huge public campaign against the government's neutrality toward the Ottoman empire shifted the perception sharply.

The shift was felt not only during the gatherings of politicians. On 13 January 1878, *The Standard* published a letter signed as Traveler, who shared his experience about the situation in Canada. He argued that at the time when the people in England “are bringing the Eastern question down to the level of party issues, the Canadians look at it only in its bearing upon national, or rather Imperial interests.”⁴¹⁷ In September 1878, conservative politician Philip Wroughton stated that “unfortunately it [the Eastern Question] had been made a party question.”⁴¹⁸ Even two years after the Bulgarian agitation, the issue of internal party relations was brought into focus.

⁴¹³ “The Indian Crisis,” *The Standard*, September 30, 1878, 5.

⁴¹⁴ Mentioned as Mount Edgcumbe in the original text.

⁴¹⁵ “The Eastern Question,” *The Daily Telegraph*, December 4, 1876, 3. Lopes used the phrase ‘the Eastern Affairs,’ which was framed by the newspaper author as a synonym of the ‘Eastern Question.’

⁴¹⁶ “The Eastern Question,” *The Daily Telegraph*, December 1876, 3.

⁴¹⁷ “Canadian Loyalty,” *The Standard*, January 1, 1877, 3.

⁴¹⁸ “Members of the constituents,” *The Standard*, September 7, 1878,

The more significant sign of the changes in the meanings of the Eastern Question is related to the reappearance of the regular column “The Eastern Question” on the pages of *The Daily Telegraph* on 9 September 1876. The column did not contain any telegrams from abroad this time. Instead, it consisted of several articles about the discussions related to the Bulgarian “atrocities” and the recently published pamphlet by William Gladstone.⁴¹⁹ The events in South-Eastern Europe were not directly mentioned in any of the articles. Rather the Eastern Question marked a discussion about the events that had already happened. In the following months, the editors regularly published the information regarding the public gatherings and speeches, letters from different people, short telegrams from the regions of the kingdom in the column.⁴²⁰ Similar columns were also published in *The Daily News* on 9 September and in *The Manchester Guardian* on 7 October.⁴²¹ The authors of these columns almost completely ignored the situation in the East at that time, leaving them to other contributors. For instance, in the issue published in *The Daily Telegraph* on October 6, the editors put two letters, three short notes, long stories about a speech by a liberal politician, William Forster, and a gathering in Hackney (a part of London), and three telegrams about gatherings in Birkenhead, Edinburg, and Sheffield.⁴²² Only one short note among them contained a direct reaction on the ongoing events in South-Eastern Europe, while all other texts included reflections on the “atrocities” in Bulgaria that had happened several months before.⁴²³ The accusation of Disraeli's government, put together with the responses from the members of Conservative party, and the appeal to the “atrocities,” was seen as more important to underline. Conservative politicians also accused Liberals of undermining the foreign policy of the British Empire but did not always deny the crimes against the Bulgarian population.⁴²⁴

The reflections published in the column uncovered a new meaning of the ‘Eastern Question’ or its “new version,” to use the term proposed by Leslie Schumacher.⁴²⁵ The concept

⁴¹⁹ E t Que io he *Daily Telegraph*, Sept b 9, he ut e B t Empire were also sometime inc ded in e l e . «The Daily Telegraph.»,” *The Daily Tel ra* , pt be 9, 87 3

⁴²⁰ O Fe r 22, 1877, the column “The Eastern Questi egraph for the last time. Among other articles, the editor also included a speech delivered by Marquis Salisbury who had recently come back from the Constantinople Conference (“Speech of Lord Salisbury.”,” *The Daily Telegraph*, February 22, 1877, 3).

⁴²¹ “The Eastern Question.”,” *The Daily News*, September 9, 1876, 3; “The Eastern Question.”,” *The Manchester Guardian*, October 7, 1876, 8.

⁴²² “The Eastern Question.”,” *The Daily Telegraph*, October 6, 1876, 3.

⁴²³ “The Eastern Question.”,” *The Daily Telegraph*, October 6, 1876, 3.

⁴²⁴ P. J. Durrans, “A Two-Edged Sword: The Liberal Attack on Disraelian Imperialism,” *The Journal of Imperial and Commonwealth History* 10, no. 3 (1982): 264–277.

⁴²⁵ Leslie R. Schumacher, “A «Lasting Solution»,” 98–99.

was no longer directly connected to the “East,” but rather circulated in the context of internal British affairs, with headlines appearing across the daily press. (see Figure 5) The discussions about the Eastern Question thus became one of the concept’s referents, to which Victorian media directly contributed. Since summer 1875, by mentioning the concept in the texts about local struggles in the imagined East or international struggles related to the imagined East, they had made the Eastern Question omnipresent for their readers. This time, by placing the concept in the headlines of the columns dealing with day-to-day domestic affairs, the editors of the penny press explicitly domesticated it.

Domestication only added to the controversies about the future of the “pending dilemma.”⁴²⁶ While Bulgarian agitation caused the wave of the public meetings and acute discussions about Disraeli’s foreign policy, the waves of Ottoman attacks put the Serbian and Montenegrin troops in a very uneasy position, and only the intervention of the Russian Empire prevented two principalities from the collapse.⁴²⁷ In December 1876, Marquis Salisbury departed to Stambul to participate in the conference that was supposed to deal with the Eastern Question. The conference did not bring any visible results, and its failure only deepened the crisis, which culminated with the Russo-Ottoman war starting in April 1877 with subsequent attempt to solve the Eastern Question at the Congress of Berlin a year later. The next section of the article will bring the visions on its future that appeared in the newspapers whose editors and authors had to deal with these developments daily, when the prospects of the events were uneven, and the same information could equally provoke the glimpses of hope or prolonged anxieties.

Towards the Solution of the “Eastern Embroglio”: Parallel Visions in the Penny Press

In an article published in *The Standard* on 10 June 1876, the newspaper’s Parisian correspondent wrote a review of an article by French journalist Émile de Girardin on how to bring the Eastern Question to its end. According to the reviewer, Girardin proposed to establish an alliance between the Russian Empire, Italy, France, and the German Empire, isolate the British Empire, and sacrifice the Ottoman and Austro-Hungarian Empires.⁴²⁸ The proposed scenario did not

⁴²⁶ “M. Yhiers and the Suez Canal.,” *The Morning Post*, December 22, 1875, 7.

⁴²⁷ Ković, *Disraeli and the Eastern Question*, 171–172.

⁴²⁸ “France.,” *The Standard*, June 10, 1876, 5.

presume a war but instead offered a lasting peace. Yet, the *Standard's* correspondent concluded that Girardin believed in miracles, for which there was no space in political matters.⁴²⁹

The reference to “belief in miracles” is a clear sign of the situational evaluations of the future of the Eastern Question. In one of his seminal essays, Reinhart Koselleck noted that the experiences and expectations of an individual always intertwine the past and the future, with the connection between the two not necessarily being causal even if the prognostic structure is present.⁴³⁰ Thus, when making a prognosis, a person did not rely entirely on their experience, which is especially visible in the modern era when their expectations have become detached from the lived experience and were more closely connected to the belief in progress. To clarify the potential disparities this shift might have caused, Koselleck introduces the notion of the simultaneity of non-simultaneous, which he also applied to the studies of conceptual history⁴³¹. From his point of view, every concept contains the simultaneity of ambiguities, which is also visible in the case of the Eastern Question, as it was shown in the previous section.⁴³²

The very simultaneity of ambiguities also revealed itself in the expectation about the potential solutions that the penny press presented to its readers. In the context of the commercial daily media, expectations depended on the envisioned interests of the audience targeted by the different parts of the newspapers, which is overlooked in the literature dealing with the development of the press in the British Empire. It was particularly visible in the discussions that took place in the part of the newspapers dealing with commerce. The Ottoman Empire was an essential receiver of the foreign investment from the British Empire, and its internal disturbances affected the London stock exchange.⁴³³ Thus, throughout the crisis, the observers of the respective columns were pragmatically interested in a quick “settlement” of the “Eastern drama” that unfolded in the Balkans that would stabilize the situation in the international markets

⁴²⁹ “France.,” *The Standard*, June 10, 1876, 5.

⁴³⁰ Koselleck, “«Space of Experience»,” 262.

⁴³¹ Koselleck, “«Space of Experience»,” 266.

⁴³² See Reinhart Koselleck, ‘Begriffsgeschichte and Social History,’ in *Futures Past*, 87.

⁴³³ See V. Necla Geyikdağı, *Foreign Investment in the Ottoman Empire: International Trade and Relations 1854–1914* (London & New York: I.B. Tauris Publishers, 2011). The Ottoman Empire was also affected by the economic crisis of 1873, which made the foreign investors change their priorities and also affected the agriculture, which was one of the most important sectors of its export economy. See, e.g., G. Conte, “Defining financial reforms in the 19th-century capitalist world-economy: The Ottoman case (1838–1914),” *Capital & Class*, 46, no. 1 (2021): 33–58, <https://doi.org/10.1177/03098168211022222>; Şevket Pamuk, “The Ottoman Empire in the “great depression” of 1873–1896,” *The Journal of Economic History* 44, no. 1 (1984): 107–118.

previously affected by the economic crisis of 1873.⁴³⁴ For them, to solve the Eastern Question generally meant to restore order in the “East,” with the conditions for that being a secondary issue.⁴³⁵

The expectations about the “settlement” were quite unstable, as the contributors to the “Money Market” or similar columns in the penny dailies approached the Eastern Question based on its perceived momentous current stage. In early November 1875, when the uprising in Bosnia was an apparent event, a reviewer of *The Standard* paid attention to the incoming falls of the stock market, connecting them with vague reports around the Eastern Question.⁴³⁶ A few weeks later, the same newspaper published a few optimistic statements regarding the Eastern Question that appeared in the press of the Russian Empire, which led to the strengthening of the stock exchange in London.⁴³⁷ Yet, on 27 November, when the news about the purchase of the shares of the Suez Channel by the British Empire came through, the *Morning Post*’s author argued twice in the ‘Money Market and City News’ column that this very purchase might lead to the difficulties in relations to the Eastern Question.⁴³⁸ The commercial affairs, sensitive to the news flows, thus created a vivid area for the concept familiar for the British reading public to be assessed and interpreted within a different temporality amidst the developing crisis.⁴³⁹

Additionally, the differences in expectations regarding the “settlement” of the question could appear simultaneously on different pages of the same issue. On 20 January 1877, a few days after the failure of the Constantinople Conference, *The Standard* published two articles with opposite views on the situation. On the one hand, the newspaper put the words of the conservative politician Edward Stanhope who told with hope the British Empire would not be involved in the Eastern question⁴⁴⁰. On the other hand, they presented a report from the gathering

⁴³⁴ See, e.g., “Money Market.,” *The Standard*, April 6, 1876, 6; “Money Market.,” *The Daily Telegraph*, October 12, 1876, 2; “Money Market.,” *The Daily Telegraph*, January 20, 1877, 2; “Money Market.,” *The Standard*, March 15, 1877, 6.

⁴³⁵ The ideas about the need to “settle” the Eastern Question appeared in the texts on commercial affairs even amidst the fights of the Russo-Ottoman war. On July 19, 1877, a reviewer of the *Daily News* noted that there was a need “to arrive to a durable settlement of the Eastern Question,” meaning establishing peace in the South-Eastern Europe, although with the involvement of two empires at war (See “Money Market,” *The Daily Telegraph*, July 19, 1877, 2).

⁴³⁶ “Money Market.,” *The Standard*, November 5, 1875, 6.

⁴³⁷ “Money Market.,” *The Standard*, November 23, 1875, 6.

⁴³⁸ “Money Market and City News.,” *The Morning Post*, November 23, 1875, 2.

⁴³⁹ On January 6, 1876, a contributor to the *Standard* paid attention to the “uneasiness” related to the Eastern Question, while a week later, he formed an expectation that the question “may soon be virtually shelved.” (“Money Market.,” *The Standard*, January 10, 1876, 6 and “Money Market.,” *The Standard*, January 17, 1876, 6)

⁴⁴⁰ “Mr. Stanhope, M. P., on Public Affairs.,” *The Standard*, January 20, 1877, 2.

in Exeter, where one of the participants talked about the difficult Eastern Question that Lord Derby, the head of the Foreign Office, had to deal with.⁴⁴¹ Neither of the correspondents talked about the solution themselves, but by publishing their reports the newspaper nevertheless strengthened the atomized character of the Eastern Question.

Hopes to settle the Eastern Question were brought to the public on the eves of each of the international gatherings in 1875-1878. For instance, such hopes appeared before the meeting of the German, Russian, and Austrian plenipotentiaries in Berlin in April-May 1876.⁴⁴² Two years later, they appeared again before the Congress in the very same Berlin.⁴⁴³ As one of *The Standard's* commentators noted, "if the Congress of Berlin settles the Eastern Question both pacifically and satisfactorily, then let no one again ask what is the use of diplomacy"⁴⁴⁴. The possibility of dealing with the Eastern Question was seen as realistic.

To "settle" the Eastern Questions, however, did not mean to "solve" it in a more long-term sense. In the editorial published on 21 June 1878, a few days after the congress was opened, the *Standard* doubted whether "the Eastern Question will be finally settled at the Congress."⁴⁴⁵ The "final settlement," which for different commentators might have meant different things, never appeared as a real possibility in the penny press throughout the crisis. The indefinite vision of the future culminated first in the speech of Lord Derby in December 1875, which was later widely discussed in the press. Commenting on the purchase of the Suez Canal shares, the minister argued that no one foresaw the "final solution of the Eastern Question," and there was no point to open the whole question.⁴⁴⁶ Neither a solution was envisioned, nor any real factors for it to happen were present for those engaging with it at that moment.

Unclear visions of the question's future also marked its undefined temporality during the crisis and beyond it. At the very same moment when Lord Derby commented on the Suez Canal, he also made a remark that "the eternal Eastern question is before us again."⁴⁴⁷ The reference to

⁴⁴¹ "Agriculturists at Exeter," *The Standard*, January 20, 1877, 2.

⁴⁴² See "The Eastern Question," *The Daily Telegraph*, April 24, 1876, 5; "Money Market," *The Standard*, May 12, 1876, 6.

⁴⁴³ "The prospects of peace..." *The Standard*, April 19, 1878, 4; "It is much to be..." *The Standard*, May 9, 1878, 4; "The Suez Canal Company," *The Standard*, June 12, 1878, 5; "The very moment..." *The Standard*, June 12, 1878, 4.

⁴⁴⁴ "Nothing that has yet..." *The Standard*, June 5, 1878, 4.

⁴⁴⁵ "The Congress has now..." *The Standard*, June 21, 1878, 4.

⁴⁴⁶ "The Earl of Derby at Edinburgh," *The Morning Post*, December 20, 1875, 3. The purchase of the shares was also not seen as a part of the solution (see "London, Monday, Dec. 20, 1875," *The Morning Post*, December 3, 1875, 4).

⁴⁴⁷ "Lord Derby at Edinburgh." *The Standard*, December 18, 1875, 3.

the “eternity” of the question was frequently made in the context of the expectations about the potential solutions of the question, especially at the early stages of the crisis.⁴⁴⁸ On 31 August 1875, the Parisian correspondent of the *Standard* underlined that the “eternal and irrepressible Eastern question will be once more staved off.”⁴⁴⁹ Several days later, the observer of the same newspaper summarized that the question “urgently demands to be solved.”⁴⁵⁰ Evidently, the solution was not found. As one noted, “the strength of the Ottoman Empire lies in the mutual embarrassments of those who would profit by its weaknesses.”⁴⁵¹ The presence of the Eastern Question thus was guaranteed by the existing international order in Europe that, while shaken by the series of uprisings and wars on the Balkan peninsula, remained stable for the contributors of the daily press. After the Congress of Berlin was over, the Eastern Question was still seen as irrepressible.⁴⁵²

The visions of the question’s eternity overlapped with contradicting ideas about the presence of the Eastern Question in the past. William Kelley made a good case to conceptualize the Eastern Question as a “historical question” in British intellectual circles of the time.⁴⁵³ The penny press has also provided some space for the discussions about its history, although it did not always utilize it for political purposes. For example, on 26 June 1878, *The Standard* published a review on a collection of conversations with French politicians that promised to tell their readers about the “the French view of the Eastern Question eighteen years ago, when it did not materially differ from what it was only three years ago.”⁴⁵⁴ The book referred to the times after the Crimean War, a memory which was also a point of reference for a few observers.⁴⁵⁵ Therefore, these were the lived experiences of the present and memory, often still

⁴⁴⁸ It was Karl Marx who is considered to be the first to use the metaphor “the eternal Eastern Question” in one of his letters to Fridrich Engels during the Crimean War (See Karl Marx, “Turkey.” In *The Eastern Question: A Reprint of Letters written 1853-1856 dealing with the Events of the Crimean War*, ed. Eleanor Marx Aveling and Edward Aveling (London: Swan Sonnenschein & Co. Ltd., 1897), 2).

⁴⁴⁹ “France.” *The Standard* August 31, 1875, 5.

⁴⁵⁰ “The announcement made by...” *The Standard*, September 3, 1875, 4.

⁴⁵¹ “Any rumour about...” *The Daily Telegraph*, January 10, 1878, 4.

⁴⁵² See “Sir Michael Hicks Beach and Lord Elcho in Gloucestershire.” *The Standard*, September 21, 1878, 2 and a similar note at “Sir Michael Hicks-Beach, M. P., at Winchcombe.” *The Daily Telegraph*, September 21, 1878, 3.

⁴⁵³ See Kelley, “Intellectuals and the Eastern Question.”

⁴⁵⁴ “Seniors «Conversations».” *The Standard*, June 26, 1878, 2.

⁴⁵⁵ “The speech of Mr. Bright...” *The Standard*, January 4, 1877, 4; “An Imperial signif anc ,” *h D ly Telegraph*, December 4, 1877, 4.

communicative, about the lived experiences of the past that defined the Eastern Question's temporality.⁴⁵⁶

Contrary to the reflections on “eternity,” the roots of the Eastern Question did not preoccupy the contributors to the penny press, and the reflections on that originated mostly from different cited passages published on their pages. On 12 April 1878, *The Standard* quoted the words of the conservative politician George Hamilton who mentioned it as “chronic difficulty for the last fifty years.”⁴⁵⁷ An observer of the *Daily Telegraph* went further in a review on a pamphlet by the Russian general Rostislav Fadeeff, starting his account about the Eastern Question from 1807, the year of the treaty of Tilsit.⁴⁵⁸ The very same treaty appeared in the book of Henry Rawlinson, reviewed in the daily press during the crisis.⁴⁵⁹ Liberal MP Henry James, cited by a few dailies, pointed out that the Eastern Question has been in focus since 1791, when Edmund Burke openly questioned the bad governance and corruption in the Ottoman Empire.⁴⁶⁰ James also referred to the Crimean war among other moments that highlighted the continuity of the question rather than its beginning, thus combining both an event that was still a part of communicative memory of his circles with more distanced cultural memory powered by historical accounts.⁴⁶¹

However, it was the advertisement that went the furthest in marking the age of the unsolved Eastern Question. In mid-1877, a few newspapers published a small piece informing about the work *Key to the Eastern Question*, which offered a number of “[h]istorical Notes on Poland (sic!), Turkey, and Russia, from the year 1650 to the present time.”⁴⁶² Going back to the contestations between the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, the Ottoman Empire, and Moscow in the mid-seventeenth century, the author thus caught the attention of the readers with the omnipresent concept that did not necessary had to deal with the historical context of the

⁴⁵⁶ On communicative , s an sm “Communicative and Cultural Memory,” in *Cultural hi l int of View*, ed. Peter Meusburger, Michael Heffernan, pringer, 2011), 15-27.

⁴⁵⁷ “Middlesex Election,” *The Sta ar A i l* , he e r ce to 50 years of the Eastern Question's history als e Standard published in the end of August 1878 (see “The Impending Impeach ment,” *The Standard*, August 26, 1878, 5).

⁴⁵⁸ “Russia's Real Policy,” *The Daily Telegraph*, October 26, 1876, 3.

⁴⁵⁹ See. Henry Rawlinson, *England and Russia in the East. A Series of Papers on the Political and Geographical Condition of Central Asia* (London: J. Murray, 1875), 18.

⁴⁶⁰ “Sir Henry James on the Eastern Question,” *The Daily Telegraph*, May 23, 1877, 3 and “Sir Henry James at Hereford,” *The Standard*, May 23, 1877, 3.

⁴⁶¹ Henry James was born in 1828.

⁴⁶² “Key to the Eastern Question,” *The Daily Telegraph*, June 7, 1877, 2; “Key to the Eastern Question...,” *The Standard*, June 7, 1877, 8.

book, which served one of the starting points of the contemporary crisis without a clear sign of any possible solutions. The solution was offered in another piece, advertised in London dailies. In February 1878, the readers were encouraged to read the title *The “Last Days” and Things Coming upon the Earth: or, the Eastern Question and the War in the Light of Scripture Prophecy*.⁴⁶³ It was put between a short ad of the biography of Pope Pius IX who died on February 7 and a book on investment. A copy of the “Last Days” cost six pennies, which equaled the price of six apples on London streets, and was certainly targeting the mass audience interested in curiosities.⁴⁶⁴ For an ordinary reader in Victorian Britain, this book might have been more valuable than the reflections on the solutions to the Eastern Question in other parts of the newspaper, as the ubiquitous doubt about the very possibility of the solution marked the pages of the daily press.⁴⁶⁵

Conclusion

The Eastern Question appeared as a mosaic and often atomized concept in the Victorian daily press during the Great Eastern Crisis of 1875-1878. Although the new controversies in the Balkans started in summer 1875, the newspaper authors had not connected them regularly with the Eastern Question until the mid-autumn of the same year. Introducing the column “The Eastern Question” in *The Daily Telegraph* was the only precise attempt to interpret the events in the Balkans through the lens of the question. At the same time, the authors of the column did not explain the meanings of the concept, presuming that the readers were familiar with them. The interpretations of the situation could change quickly, which led to multiple mentions about reopening of the Eastern Question and the presence of opposing views during 1875 and after and also resulted in the gradual inclusion of its disparate geographies.

⁴⁶³ “The «Last Days» and Things Coming upon the Earth...,” *The Standard*, February 14, 1878, 8; “The «Last Days» and Things Coming upon the Earth...,” *The Daily Telegraph*. February 19, 1878, 4.

⁴⁶⁴ Irving Fang points out that the cheap newspapers had to compete with the buns and apples sellers to attract a customer on the streets of London, where the issues were distributed by newspaper boys (Irving Fang, *A History of Mass Communication: Six Information Revolutions* (London & New York: Routledge, 2016), 51–52).

⁴⁶⁵ On February 14, 1878, when the piece of advertisement was published, the *Standard’s* issue had three more articles featuring the Eastern Question, one dealing with the Eastern Crisis, and one – with Eastern affairs. These offered visions on the “crisis in Eastern affairs,” and “difficulties in the Eastern Question,” with only hopes “for peaceful solution” being expressed (see “Although up to yesterday...,” *The Standard*, February 14, 1878, 4; “We are in a pos .,” *The Standard*, February 14, 1878, 4; “The Eastern Crisis.,” *The Standard*, February 14, 1878, 5; “Various idle rumours...,” *The Standard*, February 14, 1878, 6; “G. Hamilton, M.P., on the Crisis.,” *The Standard*, February 14, 1878, 6).

The form of opinions could also be different. There were at least 19 synonyms that replaced the original formulation of ‘the Eastern Question’ on the pages of the daily press, some of which were used to make the texts sound more sensational, nearly always negatively. The newspaper authors referred to the discourse of sensationalism to keep the readers’ attention to the events in the East, and the concept of the Eastern Question in its variation appeared as a useful tool for these purposes.

At the same time, the meanings of the concept were not homogeneous. The authors could refer to several Eastern questions simultaneously, emphasizing either factual or spatial dimensions of the concept. The interpretations were unstable, and sometimes the texts referred to new phases of the Eastern Question that either brought new understandings of the concept or added new connotations to the existing meanings. The concept was temporalized and varied under the influence of external factors or even personal authors’ intentions during the whole crisis. The appearance of the ‘party question’ as a new interpretation of the Eastern Question during the Bulgarian agitation in autumn 1876 was one of the most important signs of this variability. The editors who used the phrase in their headlines dealing with British internal politics contributed to the domestication of the concept that previously belonged almost exclusively to the domain of international relations.

With constantly changing forms and different approaches to placement, the visions on the solution of the Eastern Question also appeared in the penny press on different levels. While for the authors of the parts dealing with the commercial affairs it was a short-term “settlement” of the question that mattered the most, the reviewers of other parts offered more long-term visions on the “solution” of the question. With this simultaneous disbalance of visions, the former were the ones who were more optimistic in the long-term, while the latter almost never expressed their confidence in the solution coming soon during the Great Eastern Crisis. Their anxieties and frustrations led to the notions of the “eternity” of the Eastern Question, which was also historicized, both in main parts of the newspapers and the sections presenting the advertisement. Undefined politically, the concept was commodified and thus further domesticated by the means of daily penny press.

Despite its ambiguous character and the presence of multiple meanings, the Eastern Question was a part of everyday life in Victorian Britain during the Great Eastern Crisis, and it was the crisis that made such a presence possible. Its appearance was not limited to the

newspaper articles or speeches delivered by prominent politicians. In the end of February and in the beginning of March 1877, traditional greyhound racing took place at Ashdown Forest in South-Eastern England. After several rounds, the Irish greyhound, Eastern Question, confidently won the race.⁴⁶⁶

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⁴⁶⁶ “Ashdown Meeting.” *The Standard*, March 1, 1877, 6; “Coursing.” *The Standard*, March 2, 1877, 6; “Coursing.” *The Standard*, March 3, 1877, 6. The newspaper correspondent reported that the greyhound British Queen was a runner-up of the race.

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Figures

Figure 1. The Mentions of the ‘Eastern Question’ in *The Daily Telegraph*, 1875-1878

Figure 2. The Mentions of the 'Eastern Question' in *The Standard*, 1875-1878

Figure 3. The Mentions of the 'Eastern Question' in *The Daily News*, 1875-1878

Figure 4. The Mentions of the 'Eastern Question' in *The Manchester Guardian*, 1875-1878

Figure 5. The column "The Eastern Question" in *The Daily Telegraph*, 1875-1878